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THEORY, PRACTICE
AND INNOVATION**

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MATHEMATICAL EVIDENCE OF THE DIFFERENT SPEEDS OF LIGHT WITHIN THE SPACE OF OUR UNIVERSE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the mathematical demonstration of the variable speed of light within the space of our Universe based on the law formulated by A. N. Belashov. The new law characterizes the velocity of light propagating through the space of our Universe and depends on the power of the light emission source, the diameter of the light beam, and the distance from the light source to the final target. The new law incorporates the attenuation of the light beam as it passes through the substance of cosmic space, accounting for the antigravitational properties of interaction and counteraction among measured objects, as well as the free-fall acceleration of bodies within the medium through which the light source moves. The new law unequivocally refutes the assertion of the constancy of the speed of light and is essential for exposing the profound misconceptions of many scientists on this issue. Through concrete examples, it has been demonstrated how the speed of light varies on the planet Earth, within the space of the Solar system, and inside black holes characterized by differing physical properties. Within certain black holes, not only can the cosmic space substance density be completely absent, but also the free-fall acceleration of bodies in space, as well as the antigravitational properties of the interactions and counteractions of measured objects. In other black holes, there may be not only a high cosmic space substance density but also a significant free-fall acceleration of bodies within this space, or antigravitational properties arising from the interaction and counteraction of measurable objects.*

Keywords: *law defining the speed of light, constant of the inverse speed of light, cosmic space substance, black holes.*

The speed of light has intrigued the minds of many scientists striving to understand the nature of this phenomenon. The history of the discovery of the speed of light dates back to ancient times, and throughout history, numerous scientists have investigated the question of how rapidly light propagates through space.

Nonetheless, a scientific understanding of this phenomenon only emerged in the nineteenth century.

For instance, the British physicist of Scottish descent, James Clerk Maxwell — a leading expert in mechanics, mathematics, and optics, and the founder of statistical physics and classical electrodynamics — asserted that within the ether, both particle velocity and wave propagation speed cannot be infinite, and that the speed of electromagnetic waves may possess a finite value. Other scientists considered that the speed of light is measured with respect to absolute time, which remains unchanged, and that its rate is constant universally and at all times. In 1905, Einstein simply assigned it as an absolute speed, independent of any other factors; however, many other fundamental quantities — such as time, mass, distance, and spatial dimensions — depend on the speed of light...

Currently, numerous scientific journals refuse to accept articles that do not adhere to the principle of the invariance of the speed of light, as established by Albert Einstein's special theory of relativity, which asserts that the constancy of the speed of light is ensured by the immobility of the vacuum.

However, as a metrologist, I raise a pertinent question that the proponents of the special theory of relativity must address: in which dimensional units did Albert Einstein define distances in 1905?

It is established from authoritative sources that the International System of Units (SI) was adopted only at the 11th General Conference on Weights and Measures (CGPM) in 1960 and is founded upon seven base units (meter, kilogram, second, ampere, kelvin, mole, candela) alongside two supplementary units — radian and steradian.

However, contemporary scientists have gone even further, with Wikipedia stating that the speed of light in vacuum is an absolute value of the propagation speed of electromagnetic waves, precisely equal to 299,792,458 m/s.

This raises the question of which metrological laboratory on our planet holds the standard reference for this distance and why modern scientists alter all the old and unreliable axioms and postulates of former thinkers to conform to contemporary scientific discoveries, without providing any citations.

Over many centuries, humanity has established that the Sun is the sole star within our Solar System and is structured similarly to numerous other stars. It is an enormous massive sphere, representing a mass of incandescent gas. It is a powerful source of light and heat radiation, within which hot gases, termed plasma, constantly move and flow, and during its operation emit a substance of cosmic space (traditionally known as ether).

Philosophical perspectives return us to the reflections of Aristotle and Plato, who proposed the concept of ether in an attempt to explain the motion of celestial bodies, the propagation of light, and the nature of matter. During the 17th to 19th

centuries, ether was broadly accepted within the scientific community as the fundamental basis for explaining the propagation of light, electricity, and magnetism. Nonetheless, at the dawn of the 20th century, the concept of ether was mistakenly discarded following the emergence of Einstein's theory of relativity, since it conflicted with the theory's principles of relativity and the absence of an absolute frame of reference. However, I have provided indisputable and concrete evidence based on new laws of physics regarding the reference frame of material substances located within the space of the Solar System, demonstrated through the example of our star and planet Earth.

The Sun possesses antigravitational properties of opposition due to plasma originating from its surface, which later, upon cooling, transforms into a substance constituting cosmic space. This formed substance of cosmic space prevents the planets of the Solar System from approaching the surface of our star and ensures they remain in their orbits owing to the Sun's antigravitational opposition forces.

Planet Earth exhibits gravitational properties as a result of the Earth's core rotating in one direction and the Earth's outer shell rotating in the opposite direction, thereby generating gravitational attraction forces directed toward the center of the Belashov intermediate layer located beneath the Mohorovičić discontinuity.

Following the discovery of distinctive characteristics of the plasma emitted from the surface of our star, which transitions from cosmic ether into a substance of cosmic space through the constant of internal stresses, the substance of cosmic space itself, and the antigravitational forces of interaction and opposition inherent to the Sun, a multitude of physical laws founded on the phenomena of this material world were unveiled.

In outer space, the Sun, during the process of thermonuclear fusion, emits a significant amount of light, heat, radioactive radiation, cosmic dust, and radionuclides — atoms exhibiting radioactivity with specific mass numbers, atomic numbers, and energy states — which collectively constitute the substance of cosmic space within the Solar System. As has already been established, the substance of cosmic space in the Solar System possesses its own composition, mass, density, and energy unified within the forms of its motion, serving as the carrier of this phenomenon.

It is necessary to emphasize that even within the Solar System, the substance of cosmic space is inhomogeneous and varies depending on the distance from the Sun's surface; furthermore, it differs significantly in other systems of our Universe. Hence, referring to it as ether (as in classical physical theories) is no longer relevant.

According to the new laws of physics, it is established that the planets in the Solar System are maintained in their orbits by the substance of the cosmic space of the Solar System combined with minor antigravitational interaction and counteraction forces present in the space surrounding our Sun. The planets of the Solar System revolve around our star by means of forces of antigravitational counteraction

and interaction, which were popularly presented in the journal of current scientific information 'Aspirant and Applicant', No. 1, 2019, page 65. Publishing House 'Satellite +', Moscow.

A new physical quantity defining the substance of cosmic space was popularly presented in the scientific-practical journal 'Higher School', No. 18, 2017, page 27.

Mathematical evidence supporting the existence of the cosmic ether, or the substance of cosmic space, was presented in a popular-scientific format in the information-analytical journal «Actual Problems of Modern Science», No. 1, 2021, p. 33.

A new physical quantity determining the free-fall acceleration of bodies within the space of the Solar System was outlined in accessible terms in the scientific-practical journal «Higher School», No. 19, 2017, p. 33.

The new law for determining the distance from the surface of the Sun to the surfaces of the planets in the Solar system was clearly outlined in the scientific-practical journal «Higher School», No. 17, 2018, page 49.

At present, (ether) or cosmic space substance density = $0.3126005345650193429716951029 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and the new physical quantity defining the magnitude of antigravitational counteraction and interaction originating from the surface of our star = $0.00083675979083612040133779264214048 \text{ m/s}^2$.

It is necessary to emphasize that the strength of the antigravitational counteraction and interaction originating from the surface of our star is unstable and subject to fluctuations, varying depending on the number of prominences, their positions, and their power, which influences the movement of the planets of the Solar System along sinusoidal and elliptical orbits.

The law describing the speed of light propagating through the space of our Universe depends on the power of the light source, the diameter of the light beam, and the distance from the light source to the final target. The new law accounts for the losses in light flux passing through the substance of cosmic space and the free-fall acceleration of bodies within the medium through which the light source moves. This new law entirely refutes the assertion of the constancy of the speed of light and is essential to demonstrate the fundamental misconceptions held by many scientists who maintain that the maximum speed of light applies only to stationary objects situated in cosmic space, while our Universe is infinite in time and space and is in constant motion.

The law defining the speed of movement of luminous flux in the space of various substances within our Universe, discovered by A. N. Belashov, can be expressed as follows:

The speed of movement of luminous flux in the space of various substances within our Universe is directly proportional to the power of the emitted light source minus the power losses occurring in the measured space, and inversely proportional to the product of the density of the substance in the studied space,

the free-fall acceleration of bodies within that space or the antigravitational interaction and resistance of the medium through which the luminous flux travels, the area of luminous flux emission, and the length of the path traversed by the light source.

$$c = \frac{P - \Delta P}{\rho \cdot g \cdot S \cdot l} = \frac{\kappa_2 \cdot M^2}{c^3} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa_2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{1}{M^2} \cdot \frac{1}{M} = \frac{M}{c}$$

where:

- c — speed of the light flux in the space of the investigated substance, m/s
- P — power of the emitted light source, W
- ΔP — power losses of the emitted light source, W
- ρ — density of the substance of the investigated matter, kg/m³
- g — free-fall acceleration of bodies in space or antigravitational interaction and opposition of the medium, m/s²
- S — emission area of the light flux, m²
- l — length of the path traveled by the light source.

The law defining the speed of light propagation in spaces composed of various substances can be verified using the model devised by A. N. Belashov, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

An incandescent lamp of given power 1 is enclosed within a sealed cylindrical housing 2, possessing diameter 3 and length 4. Inside the cylindrical housing is the substance of the studied material 5, supported by a transparent movable base 6 equipped with sensors for measuring the light flux intensity. Using the movable base 6, this device allows determination of the distance at which the light flux from the source propagates without losses, and subsequently enables measurement of the increase in light flux losses as the distance of the transparent base 6 from the light source 1 increases.

Fig. 1

For example, according to the new law, we measure the speed of light propagation within the cylindrical casing situated in the space of the Solar System.

$$c = \frac{P - \Delta P}{p \cdot g \cdot S \cdot l} = \frac{\kappa_2 \cdot M^2}{c^3} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa_2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} = \frac{M}{c}$$

$$c = \frac{1000 \text{ Bm} - 20 \text{ Bm}}{0,312600534565 \kappa_2 / \text{m}^3 \cdot 0,00083675979083 \text{ M} / \text{c}^2 \cdot 0,1 \text{ M}^2 \cdot 5000 \text{ M}} = 7493,169424 \text{ M} / \text{c}$$

where:

c — speed of the light flux in the space of the investigated substance, m/s

P — emitted power of the light source = 1000 W

ΔP — power losses of the emitted light source = 20 W

R — cosmic space substance density of the Solar system = 0.3126005345650193429716951029 kg/m³

g — antigravitational interaction and counteraction within the Solar system space = 0.00083675979083612040133779264214048 m/s²

S — area of luminous flux radiation = 0.1 m²

l — path length traversed by the light source = 5000 m.

Next, we calculate the time in seconds required for a luminous flux of power 1000 W to travel a distance of 5000 m at a luminous flux speed of 7493.169424 m/s within the Solar system substance medium.

$$7493.169424 \text{ m} = 1 \text{ s}$$

$$5000 \text{ m} = X \text{ s}$$

$$X = 5000 \text{ m} \cdot 1 \text{ s} : 7493.169424 \text{ m} = 0.66727 \text{ s}$$

The results of the calculations allow for the conclusion that a light beam within the substance of the Solar System at a power of 1000 W will traverse a distance of 5000 meters in 0.66727438 seconds at a speed of 7493.169424 m/s according to Earth-based time measurements.

For instance, according to the new law, we measure the speed of light propagation inside a cylindrical enclosure located on planet Earth.

$$c = \frac{P - \Delta P}{p \cdot g \cdot S \cdot l} = \frac{\kappa_2 \cdot M^2}{c^3} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa_2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M^2} \cdot \frac{M}{M} = \frac{M}{c}$$

$$c = \frac{1000 \text{ Bm} - 20 \text{ Bm}}{1,2255 \kappa_2 / \text{m}^3 \cdot 9,8 \text{ M} / \text{c}^2 \cdot 0,1 \text{ M}^2 \cdot 50 \text{ M}} = 16,3198694410444 \text{ M} / \text{c}$$

where:

c — speed of the light flux in the space of the investigated substance, m/s

P — emitted power of the light source = 1000 W

ΔP — power losses of the emitted light source = 20 W

p — density of dry air at sea level according to the International Standard Atmosphere = 1.2255 kg/m³

g — free-fall acceleration of bodies in the spatial environment of planet Earth = 9.8 m/s^2

S — area of luminous flux radiation = 0.1 m^2

l — length of the path traveled by the light source = 50 m .

Next, we determine the time in seconds for a luminous flux with a power of 1000 W to traverse a distance of 50 m at a luminous flux speed of $16.319869441044 \text{ m/s}$ in the Earth's atmospheric environment according to Earth's temporal frame of reference.

$$16.319869441044 \text{ m} = 1 \text{ s}$$

$$50 \text{ m} = X \text{ s}$$

$$X = (50 \text{ m} \cdot 1 \text{ s}) / 16.319869441044 \text{ m} = 3.06375 \text{ s}$$

From the performed calculations, it follows that a light beam on the planet Earth, with a power of 1000 W , propagates a distance of 50 meters in an air medium in 3.06375 seconds at a speed of $16.319869441044 \text{ m/s}$ according to terrestrial time standards.

For example, according to the new law, the speed of light propagation is measured inside a cylindrical shell located within a black hole existing in a complete vacuum, without gravitational acceleration affecting bodies in the space inside the investigated black hole.

$$c = \frac{P - \Delta P}{\rho \cdot g \cdot S \cdot l} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M^2}{c^3} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa z} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{1}{M^2} \cdot \frac{1}{M} = \frac{M}{c}$$

$$c = \frac{1000 \text{ Bm} - 20 \text{ Bm}}{0,0 \text{ kg/m}^3 \cdot 0,0 \text{ m/c}^2 \cdot 0,1 \text{ m}^2 \cdot 5000 \text{ m}} = 1,96 \text{ m/c}$$

where:

c — speed of luminous flux in the space of the investigated substance, m/s

P — emitted power of the light source = 1000 W

ΔP — power losses of the emitted light source = 20 W

ρ — density of the black hole substance = 0.0 kg/m^3 .

g — free-fall acceleration of bodies in space within the black hole = 0.0 m/s^2

S — area of luminous flux radiation = 0.1 m^2

l — path length traversed by the light source = 5000 m .

Subsequently, we will determine the time, in seconds, required for a luminous flux with a power of 1000 W to traverse a distance of 5000 m at a luminous flux speed of 1.96 m/s within a black hole in a complete vacuum devoid of free-fall acceleration of bodies in the space of our Universe.

$$1.96 \text{ m} = 1 \text{ s}$$

$$5000 \text{ m} = X \text{ s}$$

$$X = 5000 \text{ m} \cdot 1 \text{ s} / 1.96 \text{ m} = 2551.0204081632653 \text{ s}$$

or 42.517 minutes according to Earth time standards.

Based on the performed calculations, it can be concluded that a light beam located within a black hole, which completely lacks both substance density and free-fall acceleration of bodies in the space of our Universe, with a source power of 1000 W, will travel a distance of 5000 meters in 2551.0204081632653 seconds at a velocity of 1.96 m/s.

According to Earth time measurements, this will amount to 42.517 minutes.

According to the scientific community, a black hole is a region of space characterized by extraordinarily high density and intense gravity. It arises when a massive star expires and contracts into a point of immense density, wherein its entire mass is concentrated within an extremely small volume — a hypothesis about which I harbor significant skepticism.

For instance, applying the new law, we measure the speed of light within a cylindrical shell situated inside a black hole, characterized by a highly dense surrounding environment and substantial acceleration due to the resultant infall of bodies within the space enclosed by the investigated black hole.

$$c = \frac{P - \Delta P}{P \cdot g \cdot S \cdot l} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M^2}{c^3} \cdot \frac{M^3}{\kappa z} \cdot \frac{c^2}{M} \cdot \frac{1}{M^2} \cdot \frac{1}{M} = \frac{M}{c}$$

$$c = \frac{1000 \text{ Bm} - 20 \text{ Bm}}{150 \kappa z / M^3 \cdot 30 \text{ M} / c^2 \cdot 0,1 \text{ M}^2 \cdot 5000 \text{ M}} = 0,000435555 \text{ M} / c$$

where:

c — speed of luminous flux in the space of the investigated substance, m/s

P — emitted power of the light source = 1000 W

ΔP — power losses of the emitted light source = 20 W

ρ — density of the black hole substance = 150 kg/m³

g — free-fall acceleration of bodies in space within the black hole = 30 m/s²

S — area of luminous flux radiation = 0.1 m²

l — path length traversed by the light source = 5000 m.

Next, we determine the time in seconds or days for a luminous flux of power 1000 W to traverse a distance of 5000 m at a luminous flux speed of 0.00043555555555555555 m/s within a black hole characterized by large free-fall acceleration of bodies in space and high density of the surrounding environment in the space of our Universe.

$$0.000435555 \text{ m} = 1 \text{ s}$$

$$5000 \text{ m} = X \text{ s}$$

$$X = 5000 \text{ m} \cdot 1 \text{ s} \div 0.000435555 \text{ m} = 11,479,606.47908989679833 \text{ s}$$

or 132.86 days according to Earth time.

From the performed calculations, it follows that a light beam located in a black hole, characterized by a high medium density and significant free-fall acceleration of bodies in the space of our Universe, with a source power of 1000 W, will traverse a distance of 5000 meters in 11,479,606.47908989679833 seconds at a speed of 0.000435555 m/s, corresponding to 132.86 days according to Earth time. Furthermore, the losses of the light flux in that region will be very large, of which we have no knowledge.

It is particularly important to emphasize that the speed of light inside cylinder 2 will correspond to the length of the cylinder at a given diameter when, on the transparent substrate 6, the resultant power equals the power emitted by source 1.

The new law for determining the speed of the light flux can now be compared with the constant of the inverse speed of light.

The constant of the inverse speed of light is a flexible quantity and depends on a multitude of factors that incorporate numerous physical quantities grounded in new laws of physics:

- strength of the luminous flux source,
- medium through which the luminous flux propagates,
- velocity of the electric charge at the given point of the trajectory,
- distance from the initial measurement point of the luminous flux to the terminal measurement point,
- reduction in strength of the luminous flux source due to variations in the medium or distance traveled,
- free-fall acceleration of bodies in space or antigravitational interaction and resistance of the medium through which the luminous flux passes.
- diameter of the light beam.

The definition for the constant of the inverse speed of light for the planets of the Solar system and the galaxies of our Universe, as discovered by A. N. Belashov, is formulated as follows:

The time interval required for a segment of charged particles to traverse a distance is directly proportional to the magnitude of the electric charge source passing through the conductor and inversely proportional to the power of the electric source.

$$Bl = \frac{F_i}{P} = \frac{\kappa z \cdot M}{c^2} \cdot \frac{c^3}{\kappa z \cdot M^2} = \frac{c}{M}$$

where:

Bl — the constant of the inverse speed of light for the planets of the Solar system, c/m

F_i — the magnitude of the electric charge source passing through the conductor or the energy source strength emitting luminous flux, N

P — power of the electric charge source, W .

In conclusion, it can be stated that our material world is highly diverse, and all processes occurring within it, resulting from randomly arising circumstances unfolding over time, influence each other to varying degrees; hence, a new theory of multifaceted dependence is proposed. In this world, everything is interconnected, and one natural phenomenon depends on another to varying extents. More active material bodies dominate less active ones; consequently, there can be no independent and immutable constants, laws, or physical quantities. For example, the new law of gravitational attraction and cosmic interaction between two material bodies situated within the space of the Solar or another system is closely connected to the new law of gravitational attraction of a single material body located within the space of the Solar system to the central star, the Sun. Simultaneously, the laws of gravitational attraction and cosmic interaction depend continuously on the new law of activity of a material body situated in space and on the new law of free-fall acceleration of bodies within space. The listed laws are closely related to the new law of energy between two material bodies located within the Solar System, as well as the new law of energy of a single material body situated within the Solar System relative to the central star, the Sun, among many others...

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ASSESSMENT AND MINIMIZATION OF MATRIX EFFECTS IN THE DETERMINATION OF FLUDIOXONIL RESIDUES IN CARROT ROOTS BY GC–MS

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Abstract. *Capillary gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC–MS) was employed to determine residual levels of fludioxonil in carrots. Due to a pronounced matrix effect (ME) caused by the high content of co-extractives in carrots, the standard QuEChERS sample preparation protocol proved ineffective. As a solution to the identified issue, an alternative approach was proposed, involving acetone-water extraction, clean-up using Oasis HLB cartridges, and a freezing step. Optimization of sample preparation conditions and the transition to more selective ions in SIM mode (m/z 248, 182, 249) enabled the achievement of a quantitative determination limit of 0.01 mg/kg. The method provided high accuracy (recovery 98%, RSD 4.4%) and selectivity, attributed to the use of Oasis HLB cartridges and characteristic ions, thereby broadening its applicability for the analysis of phenylpyrrole class compounds.*

Keywords: *fludioxonil, carrot, matrix effect, QuEChERS, SPE, Oasis HLB cartridges, GC–MS.*

The application of chemical plant protection agents to vegetable crops poses a potential risk of elevated accumulation of biologically active substances in plant-derived products and their subsequent intake by humans.

Analytical monitoring of chemical contamination plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety of food products cultivated with the use of pesticides. The development and validation of novel sample preparation and pesticide identification methods remains a pertinent challenge for analysts. The levels of pesticide

residues in food products supplied to the consumer market must not exceed the maximum permissible levels (MPL) established by the legislation of the Russian Federation (RF).

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crops cultivated across various climatic zones of the RF, owing to its high nutritional value and extensive application in the food industry. Carrot is susceptible to a wide range of fungal diseases during the growing season, among which the most significant are alternaria leaf blight (*Alternaria dauci*), phoma leaf spot (*Phoma* spp.), cercospora leaf spot (*Cercospora carotae*), and rhizoctonia root rot (*Rhizoctonia solani*). These diseases affect leaves, petioles, and carrot roots, reducing yield and deteriorating the marketable quality of the produce [1]. The use of contact and systemic fungicides is an important component of integrated plant protection for managing phytopathogens.

A new class of fungicides is represented by phenylpyrroles, which exhibit high efficacy against a range of pathogens and are widely applied for seed treatment as well as for foliar application during the vegetation period to control snow mold, root rots, and other diseases. The mode of action of phenylpyrroles involves disruption of osmotic regulation processes in pathogen cells, resulting in suppressed mycelial growth.

Currently, fludioxonil, an active ingredient from the phenylpyrrole group, is used as a broad-spectrum contact fungicide with prolonged activity that inhibits mycelial growth. Formulations containing fludioxonil exhibit translaminar activity, are rainfast, and are effective against a broad range of necrotrophic fungi [2]. Their application by spraying carrot crops enables control of alternaria and other leaf spot diseases, particularly during periods of elevated humidity and temperature stress.

The determination of LOQ in vegetable products constitutes an analytically complex challenge, primarily during the sample preparation and identification stages. The greatest difficulties encountered with plant samples are linked to pronounced matrix effects (ME), which can substantially distort the quantitative determination of the DV [3].

Carrot is a chemically complex matrix containing a broad spectrum of natural constituents — sugars, organic acids, carotenoids, flavonoids, and essential oils — which significantly complicates the analytical determination of LOQ. The presence of a large amount of co-extracted substances contributes to an increased background signal and the occurrence of chromatographic interferences.

The objective of this study was to identify approaches to reduce ME in the determination of the LOQ for fludioxonil in carrot roots by the capillary GC–MS method.

Taking into account the performance criteria set forth in the European Commission documents (Codex Alimentarius), it is recommended to ensure a LOQ at the level of 0.01 mg/kg [4].

The control of the LOQ for fludioxonil in specific types of plant products (such as peppers, watermelons, zucchinis, and cucumbers) in the Russian Federation is conducted according to an approved official method [5]. In this method, sample preparation is based on the QuEChERS approach [6,7], which integrates extraction, partitioning, and clean-up steps into a single unified procedure, thereby ensuring promptness and reliability of the results obtained. Fludioxonil determination, including identification and quantitative analysis, is carried out by GC–MS (electron ionization) in Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode using mass-to-charge ratios (m/z) of 248 (for quantification), 154, and 127.

According to the European Commission Guidance Document on Quality Control and Method Validation Procedures for the Determination of LOQ in Food and Feed, carrots are classified as group 1 products (high water content) [8], which justified the initial use of the QuEChERS technique. However, during the trials, a significant manifestation of ME was observed, expressed as interference in the analytical signal that could not be eliminated either by selecting buffer systems and salts during the extraction phase or by applying specialized sorbents designed for the cleanup of extracts from pigmented matrices. This is attributed to the abundance of co-extracted compounds typical for carrot roots and the presence of prominent background components in the extracts, including carotenoids and polyphenols.

Preliminary tests demonstrated that the QuEChERS method does not provide adequate selectivity and extract purity for fludioxonil analysis in carrot roots, which prompted the development of an alternative approach [9] tailored to the specific characteristics of this matrix (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chromatogram of the control sample extract from carrot roots, GC–MS method (electron impact):

- A — obtained during QuEChERS sample preparation, selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode with mass-to-charge ratios (m/z): 248 (quantitative analysis), 127, 154;
- B — liquid extraction with acetone-water (1:1, v/v), cleanup on an Oasis HLB cartridge, confirmatory ions with m/z 182, 249.

Carrot roots were stored frozen for 15 days in a freezer under controlled conditions at a temperature not exceeding -18 °C. Prior to analysis, samples were

thoroughly ground to ensure homogeneity. Fludioxonil was extracted from 10 g of homogenized carrot sample with 30 cm³ of an acetone–water mixture (1:1, v/v), followed by shaking (1 min) and centrifugation (6000 rpm, 5 min). A 15 cm³ aliquot of the extract was purified by solid-phase extraction (SPE) using Oasis HLB cartridges (Waters), containing a hydrophilic-lipophilic sorbent based on a copolymer of N-vinylpyrrolidone and divinylbenzene. After washing the cartridge with 5 cm³ of an acetone–water mixture (2:8, v/v), fludioxonil was eluted with 6 cm³ of methanol, evaporated under a stream of inert gas (≤ 35 °C), and the residue was dissolved in 5 cm³ of acetone. An additional purification step involved freezing the extract at a temperature not higher than -18 °C to remove co-extracted water-soluble impurities and pigments.

The efficiency of the sample preparation, encompassing homogenization, extraction, and purification stages, was assessed during method validation based on fludioxonil determination in model samples prepared from control carrot specimens, spiked with fludioxonil at five concentration levels: the lower limit of quantification (LOQ), 2x, 5x, and 10x LOQ, and a level 50 times above the upper calibration range. The validated method for determining the LOQ for fludioxonil in carrots covered a concentration range from 0.01 to 5.0 mg/kg and provided the capability to monitor both trace concentrations and exceedances of established regulatory limits.

The extraction conditions and purification parameters selected during the experiment enabled a high recovery rate of fludioxonil-94% with a standard deviation of 4.4%.

Despite the optimization of sample preparation, residual ME remained at the detection stage. An additional contribution to interference was caused by confirmatory ions with m/z 154 and 127, used in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode, which required adjustments to the chromatographic analysis conditions. Consequently, the ion set was modified: masses with m/z 182 and 249, which are less affected by matrix influences, were employed as confirmatory ions (Figure 2).

To identify impurities interfering with the analysis, blank reagent control samples (n = 3) were analyzed following the full sample preparation procedure without matrix, using only solvents and auxiliary materials. Additionally, control samples of the carrot matrix (n = 3) were analyzed.

The contribution of potential matrix interferences caused by the conventional influence of phthalates, which are readily extracted during laboratory procedures [10], was also experimentally assessed.

Even under optimized sample preparation conditions, the comparison of the signal response of the standard at a concentration of 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (corresponding to the lower limit of quantification — LOQ), prepared in solvent, with that of the corresponding matrix-matched standard (carrot root samples) demonstrated that the matrix effect exceeded 20%, reaching 34.7%.

Figure 2. Mass spectrum and structural fragments of fludioxonil ions used in SIM mode: A — fragments with m/z 154 and 127, which are sensitive to matrix interferences; B — fragments with m/z 182 and 249, which are resistant to matrix background interference

The observed ME served as the basis for constructing the calibration curve using solutions prepared in the matrix. The calibration curve constructed over the range of 0.01–0.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ using standards prepared from carrot root extract demonstrated effectiveness in compensating for ME and ensured the accuracy of the quantitative analysis.

For the control of agricultural product safety in the Russian Federation, the MRL for fludioxonil in carrots is set at 0.7 mg/kg [11].

A rational selection of the extraction and purification scheme for the analyzed carrot matrix, combined with mass spectrometric detection in SIM mode, enabled reaching a limit of quantification at 0.01 mg/kg and ensured the reliability of analytical results.

Reduction of ME to an acceptable level was achieved through the optimization of sample preparation conditions and the transition to using more selective ions.

The obtained metrological characteristics confirm the suitability of the developed approach for the determination of the LOQ for fludioxonil in carrot roots. The developed approach can be applied in laboratory practice for the sanitary-hygienic safety evaluation of food products.

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MODERN CYBERSPORTS — RISKS AND BENEFITS

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Cybersport, compared to other fundamental types of sport such as athletics, artistic gymnastics, swimming, and others, is a relatively young and rapidly developing sport.

In 2008, the International e-Sports Federation (IeSF) was established. In 2009, the first international-level competitions were held, in which 180 participants from 20 countries worldwide took part [5].

At one of the most recent International cybersport competitions held in Seoul, South Korea, in 2019, 500 participants took part, which is five times more than at the first International competition [5].

In Russia, cybersport was recognized later: on April 29, 2016, by Order No. 470 of the Ministry of Sport of Russia, cybersport was officially recognized as a sport and included in the all-Russian register of sports. From that point onward, cybersport in our country ceased to be merely a form of entertainment and leisure and became an official sport. This enabled cybersport athletes in our country to participate in and organize official competitions, obtain sports ranks and refereeing categories, and develop refereeing programs and coaching staffs for referees [1].

According to published data for 2022, 290,880 individuals in Russia were engaged in cybersport, of whom 20 athletes held the Candidate Master of Sport rank and 239 held the first sports rank; thus, cybersport is actively developing and attracting an increasing number of athletes both abroad and within our country [6].

When analyzing the prospects for the further development of cybersport activities, it is also important to consider the question of what influence cybersport can have on the athlete's body as a whole and on brain activity in particular.

Professional sports organizations in cybersport, such as Natus Vincere, Astralis, and Team Spirit, whose athletes regularly participate in international competitions, incorporate into their athlete preparation programs not only computer training sessions but also physical training, nutrition management, and psychological support [7].

Cybersport requires of the athlete high intellectual and communicative abilities, fine motor skills of the hands, and the ability to quickly analyze situations and make

strategically sound decisions. However, in the absence of compensatory measures within the training process, cybersport can have a negative impact on the athlete's body [3].

There are known scientific studies confirming the development of pathological changes among professional cybersport athletes, such as carpal tunnel syndrome, associated with the intensive use of fingers and hands by the athlete, which can lead to complete loss of functionality of the hand and wrist; dry eye syndrome caused by the impact of monitor exposure on vision, which can subsequently lead to visual impairment and an increased incidence of infectious eye diseases; musculoskeletal disorders arising from prolonged periods spent at the computer in a fixed seated position [8].

The same study demonstrated that many disciplines within cybersport are team-based, and intense competition among athletes invariably leads to significant stress and emotional strain, which can result in anxiety, social phobia, and emotional burnout. Similarly, failures within the team may be subject to criticism, potentially resulting in lowered self-esteem and the development of depression [8]. Moreover, since cybersport partially duplicates computer games, it can be presumed that cybersport activities affect cognitive functions. It is known that computer games exert a generally ambivalent effect on human cognitive abilities [2]: regular gaming practice induces structural and functional brain changes (negative changes include an increase in gray matter in the hippocampus (spatial memory) and prefrontal cortex (executive functions); strengthened connectivity within the default mode network (DMN) and central executive network (CEN); improved efficiency of the dopaminergic system that regulates attention and motivation; with excessive or dysfunctional gaming activity, neuroadaptations characteristic of addictive states arise — reduced density of D2 receptors in the striatum, dysregulation of dopamine; compulsive behavioral patterns accompanied by weakened cognitive control; increased rigidity of neuronal networks, a decrease in cognitive flexibility; conscious reflection on the gaming experience is observed with measured and diverse gameplay activity; the combination of gaming practice with other types of cognitive activity) [2]. It is known that games, especially action games, train: the distribution of attention among multiple stimuli; rapid shifting of focus between the periphery and the center; suppression of irrelevant distracting factors. Excessive engagement in games can lead to increased distractibility when solving real-life tasks; difficulties in maintaining sustained attention; habituation to a high level of stimulation, which renders everyday tasks boring. Moreover, attention training in games transfers to the real world only through conscious skill application; the similarity of cognitive demands between the game and real-life tasks; an optimal gaming time dosage [2]. It is evident that the negative impact of computer games can be offset by their positive effects on brain activity, provided that certain organizational conditions, dosage, mindfulness, the use of gaming experience as a complement to primary activities, and social integration are observed. In this context,

the dialectics of cognitive development in games constitute a dynamic equilibrium between adaptation and maladaptation [2]. By extrapolating the results of such studies and considering them in the organization of cybersport activities alongside traditional sports activities, a positive outcome can be anticipated, as confirmed by experimental data [4]. Research into the development of cybersport within the student community demonstrates the benefits of its integration into educational institutions and the successful experience of implementing cybersport activities in the universities of our country. Such activity contributes to the development of many useful skills among students, including teamwork and communication; tactical thinking and analytical abilities; fast reactions and stress tolerance; time management and discipline [5]. Positive examples of integrating cybersport into the higher education process are demonstrated by the Far Eastern Federal University, where the cybersport organization “PINGWIN” was established, uniting students passionate about the gaming industry and promoting cybersport in the Far East [4].

Therefore, cybersport in Russia is a relatively young yet rapidly developing sport. The positive influence of cybersport is achievable only under certain conditions and with further research on the effects of cybersport activities on the athlete’s body.

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RECOMBINANT PROTEIN BET V 1: CONFIRMATION OF ANTIGENIC SPECIFICITY OF THE OBTAINED POLYPEPTIDE

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Abstract. *The antigenic specificity of the recombinant protein Bet v 1 has been confirmed in a developed immunoassay test, which is based on the allergen expressed in the bacterial system Escherichia coli strain BL21(DE3) and applied to a nitrocellulose membrane. Incubating the membrane with sera containing specific IgE results in the appearance of precipitation bands in the area where the recombinant allergen is applied (n = 30) and the absence of such bands when using sera from patients sensitized to household allergens (Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus, Dermatophagoides farinae; n = 7) and epidermal allergens (cat, dog; n = 8), as well as sera from patients confirmed to be non-allergic (negative control, n = 15).*

Keywords: *Bet v 1, main allergen, birch pollen, Escherichia coli prokaryotic system, protein synthesis*

Introduction

The main allergen of birch pollen Bet v 1 provokes an IgE-mediated immune response in more than 90% of people with sensitization to birch pollen [1; 2]. It is known that Bet v 1 is characterized by significant genetic diversity, the consequence of what is variability in the ratio of isoforms in pollen between trees even within the same range. According to the allergen nomenclature, 27 variants of Bet v 1 are distinguished, among which Bet v 1.0101, an isoform with high IgE-binding activity, prevails in some European countries [3–7]. During our studies, it was found that the Bet v 1 variant is also the predominant allergen isoform of birch pollen in the Republic of Belarus [8].

Further, using the strain Escherichia coli BL21 (DE3), recombinant Bet v 1 (isoform Bet v 1.0101) purified from bacterial protein impurity was obtained. Using the

developed enzyme-linked immunosorbent LIA, the ability of the obtained polypeptide to bind specific IgE in the blood serum from patients with proven sensitization to birch pollen was confirmed. To assess the antigenic specificity of the obtained recombinant protein in the developed test, both sera from patients with a high content of antibodies to birch pollen and sera in which the content of allergen-specific IgE was not detected or absent (as a negative control) were used [9; 10].

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the allergenic specificity of the obtained resulting recombinant polypeptide (antigen) with allergen-specific antibodies to allergens other than those contained in birch pollen.

Materials and methods

Production of the recombinant Bet v 1 polypeptide (Bet v 1.0101 isoform) was carried out using genetic engineering methods as described earlier [10].

To confirm the specificity of recombinant Bet v 1, the developed enzyme-linked immunosorbent LIA was used, which is based on an “antigen-antibody” reaction, where the antigen is a Bet v 1.0101 polypeptide sorbed on a nitrocellulose membrane with a 0.45 μm pore size (ADVANTEC, Japan) at a concentration of 1.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Biotinylated anti-human goat IgE and streptavidin conjugate with horseradish peroxidase (R-Biopharm AG RIDA qLine® Allergy, Germany) were used for immunodetection. The results were interpreted according to the presence/absence of specifically colored precipitation bands in the Bet v 1.0101 protein application area.

The level of specific IgE antibodies in serum samples from patients was determined by immunoblotting using the R-Biopharm AG RIDA qLine® Allergy test system (Germany), the level of serum total IgE antibodies was determined by ELISA using the Multiple™ Immunoglobulin kit E (IgE) Abbot (Japan).

Results

At this stage of work, the absence of specific binding of the recombinant Bet v 1 allergen to antibodies contained in the sera from patients with proven sensitization to household (Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus, Dermatophagoides farinae; $n = 7$) and epidermal allergens (cat, dog; $n = 8$), but without sensitization to birch pollen. The study also included sera from patients with no allergies (negative control, $n = 15$) and sera from patients with sensitization to birch pollen (positive control, $n = 30$). The absence of specific staining in the area of protein application on all strips treated with sera with a high content of antibodies to household and epidermal allergens and the presence of staining when treated with sera with a high content of antibodies to birch pollen further confirmed the specificity of the obtained recombinant allergen. The control confirming the functioning of the test components and the specificity of the conjugate was the LIA with the research participant’s serum with a high content of total IgE ($> 100 \text{ IU}/\text{ml}$), applied to the nitrocellulose membrane (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Evaluation of antigenic specificity of the recombinant Bet v 1.0101 polypeptide: 1–5 — strips treated with sera with a high content of antibodies to birch pollen; 6–10 — strips treated with sera that do not contain specific antibodies to birch pollen; 11–15 — strips treated with sera with a confirmed absence of allergies; K — control

Discussion

The use of recombinant technology and molecular cloning methods in allergology has allowed scientists to identify the protein components that cause allergic reactions. In particular, it became possible to produce the characterized Bet v 1 peptide with known allergenic, immunogenic, and tolerogenic properties in comparison with native extracts, which can vary widely in their biological activity and concentration. To analyze the specificity of these recombinant polypeptides, enzyme immunoassays, which are based on the formation of antigen-antibody complexes, can be applied.

As a result of the work, the absence of specific interaction of the obtained recombinant polypeptide (antigen) with allergen-specific antibodies to household and epidermal allergens was confirmed.

The use of this method allows further study of the properties of the produced protein, and also makes it possible to use it as an antigenic component for creating enzyme-linked immunosorbent diagnostic test systems.

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WHEY AS A VALUABLE AND PROMISING RAW MATERIAL FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ENRICHED BIOTECHNOLOGICAL FOOD PRODUCTS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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ABSTRACT: *this study demonstrates the unique physico-chemical properties and vitamin and mineral composition of milk whey. The necessity of protein enrichment in products derived from milk whey for the development of new biotechnological products is substantiated. The purposeful preservation of milk whey as a secondary processing product is confirmed. Methods and approaches for processing milk whey to obtain high-protein raw materials with enhanced nutritional characteristics are reviewed.*

Keywords: *biotechnology, milk whey, milk whey processing methods, physico-chemical properties and vitamin–mineral composition of milk whey, baromembrane processing technologies.*

Over a long historical period, milk and its processed products have held a vital place in the human diet, significantly influencing the health and physical development of the population. The relevance of this trend continues in the modern world [52, 53].

In the Russian Federation, dairy products are included in the diet of approximately 80% of the population and are among the most widely consumed categories of food products. Milk is characterized by a balanced chemical composition, comprising proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, as well as a complex of vitamins and mineral elements, present in physiologically favorable proportions. On an annual basis, dairy products account for approximately 16% of the total food consumption [19, 23, 26].

According to the data of the Analytical Center of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation, the volume of industrial milk production (excluding raw milk) for January–October 2024 amounted to 4,528.2 thousand tons, which is 2.9% higher than the indicator for the corresponding period of 2023 (4,398.6 thousand tons). Cheese production demonstrated an increase of 3.0%. At the same time, the production of fermented dairy products decreased by 2.2% (2,385.4 thousand tons in 2024 compared to 2,439.0 thousand tons in 2023), which places this category within the segment of decline [26, 27, 28, 29]. Despite observed trends, the volume of milk and dairy product consumption showed a growth of 0.6% compared to the same period in 2023 [32, 33, 36].

The average annual consumption of dairy products in Russia is approximately 250 kg per person. However, this figure does not meet the recommended standard set by the Ministry of Health — 325 kg/year per person [12, 13, 32].

In the production of dairy products, as in most sectors of the food industry, the rational processing of by-products assumes strategic importance. However, practice shows that the potential of secondary resources is not utilized efficiently enough. Thus, during the production of cheese, cottage cheese, and casein, milk whey is generated — a product containing valuable nutrients. Its processing enables the production of protein and lactose concentrates, as well as the development of novel high-protein products applicable in the manufacture of various dairy goods.

The production of cheese, cottage cheese, and casein is accompanied by the formation of a by-product — milk whey, which is separated from the coagulated protein mass during milk coagulation (see Figure 1). The quantity of whey produced depends on the type of product being manufactured. For example, during the production of 1 kg of cottage cheese, between 1.5 and 4 kg of whey is generated, whereas in the production of 1 kg of cheese, its volume reaches 8–10 kg.

Figure 1. Whey production during the manufacturing of:
A — cheese, B — cottage cheese, C — casein.

A significant portion of the soluble components of the original milk is transferred into the whey, the chemical composition of which is presented in Table 1 [4, 5,

6, 7, 9, 12, 29]. On average, 48–52% of the substances in milk are transferred to the whey fraction, of which 24.3–25% are protein components and approximately 5.5% correspond to milk fat. Mineral elements and milk sugar almost completely transfer to the whey — their content reaches 96–98% of the original level in milk [44, 45, 46]. The majority of the dry residue of whey consists of lactose, which comprises approximately 70%, defining its carbohydrate nature and making it a valuable raw material for subsequent processing [23, 24, 34, 35, 39]. Milk whey is characterized by a significant content of biologically complete whey protein, essential amino acids, carbohydrates, minerals, and vitamins, which determines its high nutritional and functional importance. It is necessary to consider that the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of whey products are unstable. Their variability is caused by seasonal variations in milk production, specific properties of the initial raw material, as well as by the type of coagulation agent used and the method of fractionation.

Table 1 — Physico-chemical characteristics of milk whey

Parameters	Type of whey		
	Sweet whey	Acid whey	Casein whey
Dry matter, %	4.5 – 7.2	4.2 – 7.7	4.5 – 7.5
Total protein, %	0.5 – 1.1	0.5 – 1.4	0.5 – 1.5
Lactose, %	3.9 – 4.9	3.2–5.2	3.2 – 5.2
Fat, %	0.3 – 0.8	0.5 – 0.8	0.3 – 0.9
Mineral substances, %	0.05 – 0.5	0.05 – 0.4	0.02 – 0.1
Acidity, °T	15 – 25	50 – 85	50 – 120

Milk whey proteins occupy a leading position among dietary proteins in terms of biological value and are characterized by a degree of digestibility of up to 98%. Unlike many other dietary protein components, they undergo enzymatic hydrolysis more rapidly in the gastrointestinal tract, do not significantly influence the acidity of gastric juice, and consequently do not cause functional digestive disorders or excessive gas formation. It has also been established that the transport of amino acids and peptide compounds in blood plasma is observed within the first hour after consumption of products derived from milk whey [29, 37, 38, 39].

The mineral composition of liquid whey includes substances present in dissolved, molecular, and colloidal forms, predominantly as salts and inorganic acids. Among the macroelements, calcium, potassium, magnesium, and sodium predominate; Compounds of citric, phosphoric, lactic, and hydrochloric acids are also present [29].

A portion of the mineral substances used in the production of the primary dairy product also transfers into the whey phase.

In addition to the primary components of milk, whey contains phosphatides, non-protein nitrogenous compounds, enzymes, hormonal substances, and vitamins. Although milk whey can occasionally serve as an independent source of vitamins in the human diet, these vitamins are present in limited amounts in this product. The vitamin content in milk whey is presented in Table 2 [28, 29, 30, 31].

Table 2 — Vitamin content in milk whey

Vitamins	Vitamin abbreviation	Content, mg/100 g
A	Retinyl acetate	0.04
B1	Thiamine	0.37
B2	Riboflavin	2.0
B6	Pyridoxine	1.30
B12	Cyanocobalamin	0.026
C	Ascorbic acid	4.70
E	Tocopherol	0.29

MODERN BIOTECHNOLOGICAL METHODS FOR WHEY PROCESSING

Several key approaches are employed in the modern dairy industry for whey processing [15, 16, 18, 23]:

- preliminary raw material purification;
- heat treatment;
- moisture evaporation;
- electro dialysis separation;
- dehydration by drying;
- separation processes;
- denaturation followed by protein fraction extraction;
- Concentration and hydrolytic cleavage of lactose;
- Application of biotechnological methods;
- Use of baromembrane technologies.

Figure 2. Biotechnological line for the processing of dairy whey. The photograph shows the Molvest enterprise.

THERMAL PROCESSING OF DAIRY WHEY

The thermal processing method includes cooling and pasteurization stages.

It is recommended to send dairy whey for processing as soon as possible after its collection, since its chemical composition creates favorable conditions for intensive microorganism proliferation. If temporary storage is required, the product is cooled to approximately 5 °C, which inhibits the development of bacterial microflora [13, 14].

The combination of cooling with preliminary pasteurization is considered the most effective method. The primary objective of pasteurization is to suppress pathogenic microorganisms, which may originate from starter cultures used in the production of principal dairy products, as well as from secondary contamination during the collection and storage of whey. Additionally, thermal processing facilitates the inactivation of residual rennet enzyme, the presence of which is undesirable in further processing.

Pasteurization of dairy whey is performed in tubular systems at temperatures generally not exceeding 60–65 °C. In cases where the technological process demands intensified heating, such as in the production of milk sugar (lactose), steam is introduced through a sparger, ensuring an increase in temperature up to 93±2 °C. However, the exclusive use of bubbling for pasteurization is not considered rational, since the steam condensate dilutes the whey, which subsequently increases the duration and energy consumption for its evaporation, thereby affecting the production cost of the final product [37, 38, 39, 40, 54].

In processing practice, two methods of pasteurizing milk whey are applied, the choice of which is determined by production conditions and technological requirements; Each of them is characterized by specific advantages and limitations:

1) Low-temperature (slow) — holding the product for 30 minutes at 63–67 °C. This method requires considerable time resources and the availability of additional vessels to conduct the process;

2) Fast — holding for 15–20 seconds at 70–74 °C. Simultaneously, intensive fouling formation occurs on the heat exchange surfaces of pasteurization equipment, necessitating more frequent sanitary cleaning of the installations [1, 7, 8, 11, 37, 38, 39].

SEPARATION OF WHEY

Whey separation is performed to extract milk fat, casein fines, whey proteins, as well as to remove non-sugar impurities during lactose production. This process is conducted immediately after whey collection, which helps preserve the original temperature and acidity parameters inherited from the primary technological cycle.

Removal of casein fines can be achieved by settling, filtration, or centrifugation; The maximum effectiveness is achieved by the latter method, particularly when employing self-cleaning separators.

Milk fat extraction is performed exclusively through centrifugation at temperatures ranging from 35 to 40 °C. This process yields a product with a consistency similar to cream, which is immediately cooled to 3–5 °C after the separation stage. An increase in temperature during the separation positively influences the qualitative characteristics of the obtained fraction; however, even under optimal processing parameters, the residual fat content in whey remains around 0.1 %, due to the more complex extraction mechanism compared to that of milk. Coagulated protein fractions are also separated by centrifugation at 40–60 °C; The obtained protein concentrate, similarly to the fat fraction, is subjected to immediate cooling [2, 3, 20, 21, 22, 37, 38, 39].

BIOLOGICAL METHODS FOR WHEY PROCESSING

Biotechnological methods for whey processing are aimed at enhancing its nutritional value through additional nutrient enrichment, as well as producing products with predefined functional properties.

In this approach, microorganisms employed for the biotransformation of both whey itself and other types of dairy raw materials play a pivotal role. The use of starters prepared from pure cultures enables the production of a diverse range of products and semi-finished items intended for food, feed, and technical applications.

Biological processing methods facilitate the synthesis of protein substances, individual amino acids, and simple sugars, as well as the production of vitamins, enzymatic preparations, antibiotic compounds, and lipid components [36]. Moreover, milk whey is utilized as a substrate for the production of ethanol and a range of organic acids, including lactic, citric, propionic, and acetic acids. The production of these compounds is based on lactose fermentation processes or its oxidative transformations [33].

Lactic acid is produced from various types of whey — sweet whey, curd whey, casein whey, as well as from milk ultrafiltrates. The core of the technological process involves lactose fermentation mediated by lactic acid bacteria, primarily *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus*. A schematic diagram of the product manufacturing process is presented in Figure 3.

At the first stage of the technological process, milk whey is directed to fermentation vessels, where the temperature conditions optimal for the specific microorganism strain used are maintained. The starter culture is introduced at 3–5 % of the volume of the processed substrate. During lactic acid fermentation, lactose is initially hydrolyzed into monosaccharides — glucose and galactose, which then undergo further biochemical transformations culminating in lactic acid formation. At high concentrations, lactic acid exerts an inhibitory effect on microorganisms; therefore, it is periodically neutralized by adding lime or chalk, resulting in the formation of calcium lactate. Calcium lactate is then decomposed using sulfuric acid to obtain free lactic acid.

Figure 3 — Diagram of the technological process for lactic acid production

Milk whey is regarded as a promising raw material for ethanol production, capable of replacing traditional food sources (e.g., corn) and not requiring complex pretreatment such as high-temperature acid hydrolysis typically applied in the processing of cellulose-rich raw materials [53, 54, 55, 56, 57].

The ethanol production technology includes a series of fundamental stages. After whey is collected, yeast cultures are introduced, initiating the alcoholic fermentation of lactose at 33–34 °C for a duration of 48–72 hours. Ultrafiltrates are considered the optimal medium for the progression of this process. Producer microorganisms may include *Kluyveromyces fragilis*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* (including for concentrated whey), *Candida pseudotropicalis*, as well as *Streptococcus fragilis*. After the completion of the fermentation process, the yeast biomass is separated from the mash, which is then directed to the distillation stage. The technological flowchart for ethanol production is presented in Figure 4 [41, 42, 43, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 58, 59].

During the production of ethyl alcohol, by-products are formed — whey proteins and post-alcohol distillers’ grains. Protein fractions can be utilized further in the food industry, whereas distillers’ grains are applied as a feed additive for livestock [37, 38, 39].

Bioconversion of whey to produce ethanol is considered a promising approach; however, under current economic conditions, this method is less competitive compared to ethanol production technologies from alternative raw materials, including sugarcane biomass, corn grain, and lignocellulosic materials.

Research is also being conducted on the production of biobutanol from whey. Compared to ethanol, biobutanol has several operational advantages, as it can be

used in standard gasoline engines without design modifications, whereas the use of ethanol often requires technical changes to the fuel system [41, 47, 58, 59].

Figure 4 — Technological process scheme for the production of ethyl alcohol

ELECTRODIALYSIS

Electrodialysis is an electrochemical separation process in which ions are transferred through selective semipermeable cation- or anion-exchange membranes from one solution to another under the influence of an electric field generated by the passage of direct (or rectified) electric current [40, 41, 43].

Electrodialysis is utilized in the food industry for concentrating, purifying, and modifying products [43, 44, 45]. For example, electrodialysis is employed to demineralize ultrafiltration concentrate in order to obtain whey protein concentrate [44, 45, 46, 47].

An electrodialysis unit consists of sections composed of alternating anion and cation membranes stacked together. The membranes have pore sizes of 10–20 μm and are arranged at distances of approximately 1 mm or less. Two electrodes are positioned at each end of a battery composed of multiple sections. A single battery can contain up to 500 sections.

Whey and the working ionic solution (typically acidified with a 5% saline solution) are fed into channels for dilution and concentration, respectively. When direct current passes through the battery, generating a weak electric field, ions tend to migrate towards the electrode bearing the opposite charge. However, ion migration is limited by membranes acting as selective barriers to ions possessing the same charge. Anions can migrate exclusively through the anion-exchange membrane, while their further migration is inhibited by the cation-exchange membrane. Cations, conversely, migrate through the cation-exchange membrane but are retained

by the anion-exchange membrane. This restricted ion migration under direct current results in the transfer of ions from whey to the working solution, thereby inducing whey demineralization and concentration of the working solution. The degree of demineralization depends on the following factors: ash content and whey viscosity, current density, and residence time in the electro dialysis unit. If the direction of the electric current is reversed, the process will proceed in the opposite order [13, 14, 40, 43, 44, 45]. The electro dialysis process is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 — Schematic of the electro dialysis process

Electrodialysis can operate both in batch mode (typically applied for demineralization of 70% or higher) and in continuous mode (with a demineralization level ranging from 60 to 70%) [40, 47, 49, 51].

The use of this whey processing method allows for a reduction in mineral content, without significantly affecting the quality and quantity of whey proteins, lactose, and vitamins. At high demineralization (90%), lactose losses amount to 6%, and protein losses to 2–3% [10, 13, 16].

Electrodialysis can also be applied for the purification of whey from organic acids (e.g., lactic acid) formed during the fermentation process.

The main disadvantage of this process is its susceptibility to mineral contamination on cation membranes and protein contamination on anion membranes; therefore, the system requires frequent cleaning [43, 44, 45].

CONCENTRATION AND DRYING

Concentration and drying are among the most rational methods for processing dairy whey, as they enable long-term storage by reducing moisture content to a minimum, thereby inhibiting microbial activity; however, it is crucial to maintain proper storage conditions to prevent moisture ingress and contamination by foreign microflora in the final product. The application of these methods allows for a significant reduction in the volume of the initial raw material.

Concentration of milk whey is carried out using the following methods: evaporation, freezing, reverse osmosis (hyperfiltration). At present, enterprises produce the following types of whey concentrates: concentrated milk; concentrated milk with sugar; condensed milk; condensed milk with sugar; purified condensed milk. demineralized, electrodialysis, concentrated [37, 38, 39].

The technological process of whey concentration includes the following main stages:

1) Reception and preparatory stage — assessment of the quality of the incoming whey is conducted, along with its purification from casein dust particles and residual milk fat. If the acidity exceeds the regulatory limits, deacidification is performed using a sodium bicarbonate solution. Then pasteurization is carried out either by the rapid or the low-temperature (slow) method, as described in section 1.2.2.1;

2) Concentration — the process is conducted in vacuum evaporation units at a temperature of 55–65 °C until the specified concentration of dry matter is achieved;

3) Cooling and standardization — carried out in heat exchange equipment by reducing the temperature of the concentrated whey to 6–10 °C; If necessary, the mass fraction of dry matter is adjusted by adding natural pasteurized whey. A preservative is additionally introduced in an amount of 0.05–0.10%;

4) Filling and packaging of finished products — stainless steel canisters or specialized tanker trucks are used.

Production of dry concentrates is based on drying of pre-concentrated whey at the following dry matter content levels:

- 18–20% — when using film drying;
- 32–36% — with conductive drying or treatment in a fluidized bed;
- 38–40% — with spray drying without the stage of lactose crystallization;
- 46–52% — in the spray drying method with preliminary lactose crystallization [33].

Concentrated cheese whey is subjected to drying in spray dryers, film dryers, as well as in fluidized bed equipment; curd and casein whey are processed exclusively in spray dryers until the dry matter content reaches at least 95%. During the process, the key parameters determining the volume of moisture removed are the temperature conditions and drying duration [37, 38, 39]. Moreover, there is dry whey characterized by the following degrees of demineralization (GOST R 56833–2015):

25%, 50%, 70%, and 90%, produced by electro dialysis and distinguished from conventional dry whey by a lower ash content.

Paper bags or plywood-stamped barrels with polyethylene liners are employed for the packaging of dry concentrates. The product's shelf life can extend up to 6 months provided the following storage conditions are maintained: ambient temperature at 18 ± 2 °C and relative humidity not exceeding 80%.

Dry whey concentrates are used in food production as protein-carbohydrate supplements, in the manufacture of whole milk replacers, in the compound feed industry, and as other feed materials.

BAROMEMBRANE TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PROCESSING OF MILK WHEY

Currently, baromembrane technologies represent some of the most widespread and effective methods of processing.

In the processing of milk whey, microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF), and reverse osmosis (RO) are predominantly utilized. These processes occur under elevated pressure using semipermeable membranes and aim to separate solution components into distinct fractions [10, 24].

Microfiltration is a type of membrane filtration performed at relatively low pressure. This method is appropriately applied at the stage of preliminary raw material preparation to reduce bacterial contamination of whey and remove residual fat [23]. Membranes have pores ranging in diameter from 100 nm to 10 μ m.

Membranes are characterized by pore diameters ranging from 100 nm to 10 μ m. The application of ultrafiltration allows the production of protein concentrates with protein content in dry matter ranging from 30 to 95% by separating lactose and mineral salts through membranes, which can subsequently be used in the production of various dairy products [23]. Membranes possess pores ranging in diameter from 10 to 100 nm.

Nanofiltration is utilized to concentrate the main components of the solution and to separate comparatively small molecules. Enables retention of proteins, lactose, and salts in the whey. Conducted at lower pressures compared to reverse osmosis. Membrane pores have diameters ranging from 1 to 10 nm.

Reverse osmosis is employed for concentrating solutions and ultrafiltration permeates by removing the solvent. On one side of the membrane is the solution, and on the opposite side — the solvent. Thin porous membranes with pore diameters ranging from 0.1 to 1.0 nm are used.

Table 3 presents a comparative characterization of various baromembrane processes [29, 32].

Table 3 — Characteristics of membrane filtration methods

Process	Pressure, MPa	Size of semipermeable pores
Microfiltration (MF)	up to 0.3	100 nm – 10 μ m
Ultrafiltration (UF)	0.3–1.0	10 – 100 nm
Nanofiltration (NF)	1-3	1 – 10 nm
Reverse osmosis (RO)	3-10	0.1 – 1.0 nm

Thus, baromembrane technologies enable the separation of components dissolved in solution based on membrane pore size, resulting in two solutions with different constituents as output.

In the processing of whey using membrane technologies, both ceramic (tubular) and polymeric elements (of roll or spiral type) are utilized. Polymeric membranes exhibit greater sensitivity to mechanical contaminants and elevated fat content in the processed medium, which accelerates their degradation and necessitates more frequent replacement [33, 34, 35].

Membrane technologies hold a pivotal role in the modern dairy industry, as they enable the transformation of whey from a milk processing by-product into a commercially valuable and economically efficient resource. The application of these methods contributes to the reduction of energy resource consumption, water, and consumables, enables the maximal utilization of raw material potential, and thereby enhances the production efficiency and profitability of whey processing in comparison with alternative approaches [23, 24].

STATUS AND TRENDS IN THE PROCESSING OF DAIRY WHEY

Over the past decade, global interest in the efficient and rational utilization of dairy whey, with an annual production volume of approximately 80 million tons, has increased significantly. In several countries, 80 to 90% of the whey produced is processed, with up to half of this quantity allocated to the production of food and feed products [21]. In the Russian Federation, the share of industrial processing is approximately 21%; about 20% is disposed of by spreading on fields or discharged into wastewater, while around 59% is utilized for feeding agricultural animals [18].

In European countries, large specialized complexes operate that focus on manufacturing a broad assortment of products derived from whey [15, 22, 26].

The scale of whey processing in Russia is substantially lower compared to European levels. This is associated with a shortage of modern production capacities and insufficient investment volumes, as the return on investment for such projects requires the application of costly equipment and significant quantities of raw material sourced from the primary production. There are numerous dairy processing enterprises in the country, characterized by relatively small volumes of whey generation and the use

of outdated technological lines. Moreover, there is an absence of a well-developed network of centralized processing facilities to which small-scale plants could deliver the by-product; considerable distances between production sites complicate transportation and pose risks of whey quality degradation [25].

In European countries, specialized enterprises already exist that process milk whey and produce a wide range of products from it [22, 25]. For example, in the Netherlands, two enterprises operate with an annual capacity of 2.0 million tons and 2.5 million tons, processing whey supplied from northern France, Germany, and Ireland. In southern Germany, there is an enterprise with an annual capacity reaching 4.5 million tons, which receives whey from the eastern part of France, Austria, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia. Cheese factories in northern Italy have established an enterprise enabling them to jointly process cheese whey [17, 18, 19].

Domestic processing volumes do not fully cover the existing demand for milk whey. According to the Ru-Stat statistical portal, based on data from the Federal Customs Service of the Russian Federation, the foreign trade volume for the commodity category ‘milk whey’ from August 2023 to August 2024 amounted to 54 million US dollars (Figure 6). The total shipment volume reached 68.6 thousand tons, with imports accounting for 65.4 thousand tons, while export shipments amounted to only 3.25 thousand tons (Figure 7).

Figure 6 — Russia’s foreign trade turnover for the product category “Milk whey”, USD

Figure 7 — Russia's foreign trade turnover for the product category “Milk whey”, tons

In the geographical structure of foreign trade turnover for the product category “milk whey”, Belarus holds the leading position with a 64% share, followed by Argentina with 22% [29, 30].

Conclusions

The relevance and necessity of processing dairy whey, a by-product of cheesemaking, curd production, and other fermented milk products, into valuable high-protein raw materials for the biotechnological industry in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and sports sectors are continually increasing. This processing is essential both for mitigating environmental pollution and transforming waste into profit, as well as for obtaining highly valuable protein components, such as isolates and milk proteins, amino acids, and peptide molecules. Milk whey has a high nutritional value. It contains up to 50% of the dry matter of milk, including valuable whey proteins (albumin, globulin), lactose, vitamins, and minerals. All biotechnological products derived from milk whey as raw material exhibit enhanced probiotic and prebiotic effects, and consequently, individuals using milk whey show restoration of immune function.

An economic advantage is also noted due to the transition to waste-free production, which enhances the overall profitability of the dairy facility. Obtaining additional revenue from the sale of dry whey, lactose, or components used in sports nutrition.

Environmental preservation, as whey discharge into sewage systems causes significant harm due to its high biological oxygen demand. Whey processing reduces environmental impact and transforms waste into a valuable product.

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IMMUNOMORPHOLOGICAL REMODELING OF LYMPH NODES IN COVID-19 INFECTION

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Abstract. *Introduction.* Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is associated with profound disturbances of immune homeostasis affecting both innate and adaptive immunity. The severity of the disease course is largely determined by the nature of the immune response, including the degree of innate immune activation, the status of T- and B-cell populations, and the effectiveness of the humoral arm. Despite a substantial number of clinical and immunological studies, the morphological and immunomorphological mechanisms of immune response dysregulation in lymph nodes during COVID-19 remain insufficiently investigated. Of particular interest is the condition of lymphoid tissue as a key site for the coordination of systemic immune responses, since adaptive antiviral immunity is formed within lymph nodes. The lack of data on structural and functional alterations of lymph nodes limits the understanding of the pathogenesis of immune deficiency and impaired antiviral defense in this infection. *Objective.* To perform a comprehensive immunomorphological assessment of the cellular composition, functional activity, and coordination of innate and adaptive immune responses in lymph nodes of patients with COVID-19. *Methods.* An immunohistochemical study of lymph nodes was conducted using a panel of markers for innate immunity, T- and B-cell compartments, proliferative activity, and immunoglobulin production. The expression of markers for antigen-presenting cells, macrophages, T-lymphocyte subpopulations, and the B-cell lineage was evaluated. Quantitative analysis was performed using morphometric assessment of the relative area of DAB-positive staining using Fiji (ImageJ) software, ensuring objectivity and reproducibility of the results. Results

and discussion. Pronounced diffuse activation of antigen-presenting cells and macrophages was observed, accompanied by disruption of lymph node architecture. A marked imbalance of T-cell subpopulations was identified, characterized by a predominance of CD8⁺ cytotoxic lymphocytes and a reduced coordinating role of CD4⁺ T cells. Functional impairment of germinal centers was detected, along with the predominance of an extrafollicular polyclonal humoral immune response. Conclusions. The immune response in lymph nodes during COVID-19 is characterized by profound discoordination between innate and adaptive immunity, which may underlie the development of immune deficiency and impaired antiviral defense in this infection.

Keywords: COVID-19, lymph nodes, immunohistochemistry, immunomorphology, innate immunity.

Introduction. COVID-19 is a systemic infectious disease in which damage to the immune system plays a key role in shaping the clinical picture and disease outcomes [1,2]. However, the morphological basis of these changes, particularly at the level of secondary lymphoid organs, remains the subject of active research [3,4]. Lymph nodes are central to the immune response, providing antigen presentation, activation of T and B lymphocytes, formation of germinal centers, and plasma cell differentiation [5,6]. Disruption of coordination between these processes can lead to a functionally defective immune response [6]. Clinically, patients exhibit lymphopenia, impaired T-cell immunity, and atypical humoral responses [3,4]. Therefore, comprehensive immunohistochemical examination of lymph nodes in COVID-19 is of particular interest for understanding the pathogenesis of the disease.

Objective. To perform a comprehensive immunomorphological assessment of the cellular composition, functional activity, and coordination of innate and adaptive immune responses in lymph nodes of patients with COVID-19.

Methods. The study material consisted of lymph nodes from patients with laboratory-confirmed novel coronavirus infection (COVID-19). Histological sections were stained using standard methods and also subjected to immunohistochemistry using the innate immunity markers CD68 and S100. Photomicrographs of immunohistochemically stained specimens were obtained using a Leica light microscope with specialized digital imaging software. The immunohistochemical reaction was visualized using the chromogen 3,3'-diaminobenzidine (DAB). Quantitative assessment of marker expression was performed by morphometric analysis of the relative area of DAB-positive staining (%) using Fiji software (ImageJ, NIH, USA). Analysis was performed on digital micrographs obtained at $\times 20$ magnification, chosen as optimal for morphometric assessment of immunohistochemical marker expression. For each drug, at least two visual fields were

analyzed, after which the mean values were calculated. Statistical data processing was performed using GraphPad Prism version 10.4.1 (GraphPad Software Inc., USA). Quantitative data are presented as mean values with ranges.

Results. Macroscopically, the lymph nodes of patients who died from severe COVID-19 were enlarged, edematous, gray-red, and encapsulated. Microscopically, follicular involution with lymphocytic depletion was observed in both the cortical and paracortical zones. Characteristic findings included signs of disruption of the lymphoid tissue histoarchitecture: absence of germinal centers, dilated sinuses, and isolated areas of necrosis. Furthermore, in most cases, pronounced vascular changes were detected in the lymph node tissue: vascular congestion and dilation, erythrosthiasis, diapedetic hemorrhages, microangiopathy with the presence of red blood cell thrombi, and mucoid swelling of the vascular wall. Markers of innate immunity and antigen presentation were included in the analysis. This approach allowed us to characterize not only the cellular composition of lymphoid tissue but also the functional state of individual immune compartments, as well as identify the specific features of their coordination during the novel coronavirus infection. Immunohistochemical and morphometric studies of the lymph nodes of COVID-19 patients revealed significant changes affecting key components of the immune system. The list of immunohistochemical markers used and their biological significance are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Immunohistochemical characteristics of lymph nodes in COVID-19

Marker	Average expression value, % (min–max)	Expression pattern	Cellular and immune compartment	Biological significance
CD68	~34,0 (33,2–34,8)	Moderately high, stable	Macrophage component of innate immunity	Phagocytosis, inflammatory activation
S100	~46,5 (43,3–48,6)	High, uniform	Antigen-presenting cells (dendritic, interdigitating)	Antigen presentation and activation of adaptive immunity

Analysis of innate immunity markers revealed diffuse activation of the macrophage and antigen-presenting apparatus in the lymph nodes. CD68 expression reflects activation of the macrophage component of innate immunity and was characterized by a stable and relatively high area of DAB-positive staining, indicating a generalized macrophage response. Concurrently, high and uniform S100 expression indicated activation of dendritic and interdigitating cells involved in antigen presentation. The combination of morphological features reflects constant

and intense antigen stimulation of lymphoid tissue, indicating diffuse activation of innate immunity and antigen presentation in the lymph nodes in COVID-19.

Figure 1. Immunohistochemical expression of CD68 and S100 in lymph nodes in COVID-19: A — CD68, B — S100. Immunohistochemical staining, DAB chromogen, magnification $\times 200$.

Discussion. The obtained results allow us to consider lymph nodes in COVID-19 as a morphological substrate for profound immune dysregulation, in which immune system activation is not accompanied by the formation of an effective and coordinated adaptive response. The identified diffuse activation of the macrophage and antigen-presenting apparatus reflects persistent antigen load and chronic stimulation of the innate immune system. However, this activation does not translate into a full-fledged adaptive response, which is likely due to the depletion and functional failure of the lymphoid tissue. Thus, the combination of the identified changes reflects systemic immune dysregulation, in which intense antigen stimulation and activation of individual immune systems do not lead to the formation of a complete, coordinated, and long-lasting immune response.

Conclusions. An immunomorphological study of lymph nodes in COVID-19 patients revealed that the immune response during this infection is characterized by a marked discoordination between innate and adaptive immunity. These changes may be considered the morphological basis for immune deficiency in COVID-19 and are important for understanding the pathogenesis of the disease.

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THE STAGES OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE SKIN IN RESPONSE TO THE INTRODUCTION OF TATTOO PIGMENT: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Abstract. Introduction. Tattooing is an increasingly common procedure involving artificial disruption of skin integrity and pigment impregnation into the dermis. Despite its popularity, the detailed pathomorphological changes in skin following exogenous pigment administration require systematic experimental investigation. Understanding the dynamics and staging of these changes at macro- and microscopic levels is fundamental for assessing pigment biocompatibility and potential risks. **Materials and Methods.** The experimental study was performed on 40 male white outbred rats divided into an experimental group (n=30) and a control group (n=10). Under inhalation anesthesia, a standardized tattoo with black pigment was applied to the dorsal skin using a sterile tattoo machine with a standard caliber needle. Animals were euthanized on days 7, 14, and 21 post-procedure. Skin fragments were fixed in 10% neutral formalin, embedded in paraffin, sectioned (4–5 μm), and stained with hematoxylin-eosin and Van Gieson's method. Histological examination was conducted using a light microscope. **Results.** Histological analysis revealed a distinct staging of morphological changes. On day 7, acute inflammation was

observed: marked dermal edema, marginal leukocyte stasis, and focal neutrophilic infiltration in the reticular dermis. Pigment was distributed diffusely, predominantly perivascularly. By day 14, the inflammatory response had significantly decreased; pigment granules migrated from the papillary layer and began integrating into the intercellular space of the reticular dermis. On day 21, active inflammation had completely regressed. The pigment was definitively localized in the reticular dermis, forming stable clusters, with only single granules visible in the papillary layer. A final phase of phagocytosis with resident macrophage infiltrates around pigment particles was noted. **Conclusion.** This experimental study established that tattoo pigment administration triggers a regular staged process of morphological restructuring. Three consecutive phases were identified: 1) acute inflammatory (up to 7 days); 2) incomplete phagocytosis and pigment migration (14 days); 3) integration and final fixation of pigment in the reticular dermis (21 days and beyond). The data indicate that even technically correct tattooing leads to profound structural skin transformation due to exogenous pigment persistence, which must be considered when assessing long-term effects.

Keywords: tattoo, experimental study, morphological changes, skin, pigment, inflammatory response, phagocytosis.

Introduction

The practice of tattooing, defined as the deliberate introduction of exogenous pigments into the dermis to create permanent designs, has seen a significant rise in global popularity. This procedure involves breaching the skin's protective barrier and depositing pigment particles within the dermal layer, initiating a complex cascade of biological responses [1]. While the aesthetic and cultural aspects of tattooing are widely discussed, the fundamental biological interactions between the skin and tattoo pigments remain incompletely understood. The long-term consequences of pigment persistence, the dynamics of the inflammatory response, and the precise mechanisms of pigment encapsulation are critical areas of investigation. The need for systematic experimental studies is underscored by clinical reports of various adverse reactions, ranging from chronic inflammation and allergic responses to more complex dermatological complications [2, 3, 4]. Furthermore, the increasing use of laser techniques for tattoo removal necessitates a deeper understanding of the baseline morphological state of the tattooed skin to predict treatment outcomes and potential adverse effects [5, 6, 7]. This study aims to delineate the temporal staging of morphological changes in the skin following the intradermal administration of tattoo pigment, using an established experimental model.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on 40 male white outbred rats, weighing 250–300 g. The animals were housed under standard vivarium conditions with free access to

food and water. All experimental procedures were carried out in accordance with the ethical guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals. The animals were divided into two groups: an experimental group (n=30) and an intact control group (n=10).

In the experimental group, under general inhalation anesthesia, a standardized area on the dorsal skin was shaved and disinfected. A sterile tattoo machine equipped with a standard caliber needle was used to introduce a commercially available black tattoo pigment into the dermis. The procedure was performed in a standardized manner to ensure consistent pigment depth and density. The control group animals did not undergo any procedure.

Animals from the experimental group were euthanized by anesthetic overdose at three time points post-procedure: 7, 14, and 21 days (n=10 per time point). The control group animals were sacrificed at equivalent time points. Full-thickness skin biopsy specimens, including the tattooed area and the corresponding area from control animals, were harvested. The samples were immediately fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 hours. After fixation, the tissues were dehydrated, cleared, and embedded in paraffin blocks. Serial sections of 4–5 μm thickness were cut using a rotary microtome. The sections were routinely stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) for general morphological assessment. Additionally, Van Gieson's staining method was employed to visualize collagen fibers and connective tissue architecture. Histological examination and microphotography were performed using a Micros light microscope (Germany).

Results

Histological analysis of the skin samples from the experimental group revealed a distinct temporal staging of the morphological response to the tattoo pigment, which was consistent across all animals at each time point.

Day 7: Acute Inflammatory Phase. Microscopic examination of the skin on the 7th day post-procedure revealed a pronounced acute inflammatory reaction. The dermis exhibited marked edema, with significant widening of the intercellular spaces. The microvasculature in the superficial and deep dermis showed margination and stasis of leukocytes. The predominant inflammatory cell type was neutrophils, which formed focal infiltrates primarily within the reticular layer of the dermis, surrounding the deposits of pigment. The tattoo pigment appeared as black, granular material distributed diffusely throughout the upper and mid-dermis. A notable feature was the perivascular localization of the pigment granules. The epidermis overlying the inflammatory focus showed mild acanthosis but was otherwise intact. In contrast, the control skin samples from the same time points displayed the typical histological architecture of rat skin, with a well-defined epidermis, dermis, and subcutaneous layer, devoid of any inflammatory infiltrates or structural abnormalities.

Day 14: Phase of Incomplete Phagocytosis and Pigment Migration. By the 14th day, a significant reduction in the acute inflammatory response was observed. The

dermal edema had subsided, and neutrophilic infiltration was markedly decreased. The most striking changes were related to the redistribution of the pigment granules. While some pigment remained in the superficial papillary dermis, the majority had begun to migrate into the deeper reticular layer. The pigment particles were no longer diffusely scattered but were becoming localized within the intercellular space of the reticular dermis. The cellular response shifted from a neutrophilic predominance to a mononuclear cell infiltrate, including macrophages, which were observed in close proximity to pigment aggregates. This finding suggests the initiation of an incomplete phagocytic process, where pigment particles were internalized but not cleared.

Day 21: Phase of Integration and Fixation. At the 21-day time point, all signs of active inflammation had completely regressed. The epidermis and dermis were clearly delineated, with a return to a normal structural organization. The tattoo pigment had reached its final anatomical localization, forming stable, well-defined aggregates and clusters exclusively within the reticular layer of the dermis. In contrast, the papillary layer contained only occasional, isolated pigment granules. The cellular response was characterized by the presence of resident macrophages forming distinct infiltrates around the pigment aggregates, representing the final phase of phagocytosis and encapsulation. This stable integration of the pigment into the dermis, without ongoing inflammation, defines the morphological endpoint of the uncomplicated tattooing process. The control skin samples remained histologically unremarkable throughout the entire study period.

Discussion

The results of this experimental study clearly demonstrate that the introduction of tattoo pigment into the skin initiates a predictable and sequential process of morphological transformation. The three distinct phases identified — acute inflammation, followed by a transitional phase of migration and incomplete phagocytosis, and culminating in a stable integration phase — reflect the skin's complex response to a persistent exogenous material. This staged response aligns with known principles of tissue reaction to foreign bodies but provides specific temporal and histological details relevant to tattooing.

The initial acute inflammatory phase (day 7) is a direct result of the mechanical injury caused by the tattooing needle and the immediate deposition of the pigment, which is recognized as a foreign substance. The neutrophilic infiltration is characteristic of this acute response. The subsequent phase (day 14) is critical, as it marks the transition from inflammation to resolution. The migration of pigment from the papillary to the reticular dermis is a key finding, as the reticular dermis provides a more stable, less dynamic environment for long-term pigment retention. The shift to a macrophage-dominated response highlights the role of these cells in attempting to clear the foreign material, a process that is ultimately incomplete due to the pigment's physicochemical properties [8].

The final phase (day 21 and beyond) represents the establishment of a persistent, stable state. The formation of resident macrophage infiltrates around pigment aggregates indicates that the body has achieved a state of equilibrium with the exogenous pigment. This encapsulation serves to isolate the foreign material, preventing further inflammatory insult. This morphological state is likely maintained indefinitely, although it can be disrupted by external factors such as sunlight or laser irradiation [9, 10]. The clinical implications of this deep structural transformation are significant. Even in the absence of visible complications, the skin has undergone a permanent alteration. This altered state may be a contributing factor in the pathogenesis of delayed hypersensitivity reactions, infections, or even neoplastic transformations that have been reported in the literature. The present study provides a fundamental morphological framework for understanding these potential long-term risks.

Conclusion

This experimental study on a rat model demonstrates that the intradermal administration of tattoo pigment induces a strict, time-dependent staging of morphological changes. The process evolves through three distinct phases: an acute inflammatory response, a transitional phase characterized by pigment migration and incomplete phagocytosis, and a final phase of stable integration where pigment is permanently fixed within the reticular dermis. These findings underscore that even an uncomplicated tattooing procedure results in profound and permanent structural reorganization of the skin. This foundational knowledge is essential for clinicians and researchers to better understand the long-term tissue response to tattoo pigments and to evaluate the safety and potential complications associated with both the application and removal of tattoos. Further research is warranted to explore the underlying biochemical and immunological mechanisms of these staged processes.

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NEUROREFLEX MECHANISM OF ARTERIAL PRESSURE CORRECTION

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Abstract. *An innovative non-pharmacological method therapy for arterial hypertension (AH) P-DTR is presented. It targets the key mechanism of AH pathogenesis — the neurogenic mechanism, with the leading executive factor being increased activity of the sympathetic nervous system. The method is characterized by safety, non-invasiveness, and high efficacy with a procedure duration of 15–30 minutes. To obtain evidence of efficacy, a randomized clinical trial, which is the “gold standard” of evidence-based medicine, has been initiated.*

Keywords: *Arterial hypertension, neurogenic mechanism of pathogenesis, treatment with method P-DTR.*

Introduction

Arterial hypertension (AH) remains one of the most significant medical and social problems of our time. This disease is widespread, poorly controlled in many patients, and is a leading risk factor for life-threatening cardiovascular complications such as myocardial infarction and stroke [1].

Despite the achievements of recent decades — detailed study of risk factors and pathogenesis, neurohumoral and molecular mechanisms of blood pressure (BP) regulation, and the development of international clinical guidelines — key issues in AH treatment remain unresolved. A fundamental problem in the treatment of arterial hypertension is that temporary pressure reduction with medications does not restore its natural regulatory mechanisms [2].

The article considers the key mechanism of arterial hypertension pathogenesis — the involvement of the central nervous system (CNS) — the neurogenic factor, particularly the increased activity of the sympathetic nervous system, in triggering and maintaining high blood pressure levels. Correction of this neurogenic

mechanism is carried out by the method of neuroreflex therapy, aimed precisely at this link in pathogenesis.

Gaps in Classical AH Treatment

1. Symptomatic approach — drugs suppress manifestations but do not affect the cause.

2. Lifelong intake of antihypertensive drugs, the constant need to increase their dosages, side effects — kidneys, liver, and metabolism suffer from antihypertensive agents.

3. Resistance — in 20–30% of patients, BP remains high even on three or more drugs, and indicators of disability and mortality practically do not decrease.

Modern treatment strategies, based on lifelong antihypertensive therapy, are aimed only at BP control, not at eliminating the cause of the disease.

Correction of arterial pressure by the neuroreflex method involves searching for and diagnosing dysfunctional receptors that are the cause of increased BP: impaired baro-, chemo-, sympathico-, mechano-, nociceptors, etc., as well as their modalities. Then, simultaneous stimulation of the primary dysfunctional receptor (the cause of increased BP) and the compensatory receptor, which the nervous system immediately creates for compensation at the moment of exposure to a damaging factor to avoid disrupting its regulatory functions, is performed. Then, a tendon reflex is performed: knee, biceps, triceps, etc. The moment of exposure to the damaging factor on the body is reproduced in a mild form. After this, the CNS returns to optimal regulation of arterial pressure and other functions.

Body manipulations are akin to working with a computer. If erroneous data is entered into a computer, then with normal software, the computer produces incorrect information. The same happens with the CNS — when sensory systems malfunction, regulation is disrupted, and discomfort, pain, impaired movement patterns, increased BP, and other symptoms appear.

The method was developed by surgeon-orthopedist, neurologist, neurophysiologist, kinesiologist Jose Palomar (Mexico) [3]. He was the first in the world to identify the relationships between sensory perception and motor reactions, explained them, and proposed a method for treating various diseases (patent No. 2722402, 2019).

Key Advantages of P-DTR Correction of Arterial Pressure Over Traditional Treatment.

Acts on the cause, not the symptoms; restores normal sensory and proprioceptive afferentation — the main mechanism of BP regulation failure; corrects dysfunctions of baro-, chemo-, sympathico-, mechano-, nociceptors, etc., associated with BP regulation; safety and absence of side effects; does not require medication intake or invasive interventions; the effect after the course of therapy persists for a long time due to neuroplasticity; diagnosis of precise neurogenic disorders in

each patient and a personalized approach to treatment (rather than “template” drug prescription according to a scheme); can be used as a complementary method in combination with other methods; suitable for patients with metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and any other comorbid pathologies.

Thus, it is correct to assert that the method P-DTR can rightly be considered a promising hypothesis with a theoretical basis. Currently, its application is based on its positive five-year clinical testing, reliable results of efficacy and safety in treating limited groups of patients, in which statistically significant differences in all studied indicators were obtained when processing data before and after treatment using the Wilcoxon method.

However, the absence of randomized controlled trials (RCTs), meta-analyses, systematic reviews meeting the criteria of evidence-based medicine does not allow classifying P-DTR therapy as an intervention with proven efficacy, unlike many pharmacological drugs that have undergone a full cycle of clinical trials. There are no works on the application of the neuroreflex therapy method for AH in the available literature. The reason is that this method was proposed relatively recently. Currently, randomized clinical trials have only been initiated as part of a pilot project by the School P-DTR. P-DTR is a new method in the complex treatment of hypertension, associated with the restoration of neurophysiology.

Considering the complex multi-level and multifactorial pathogenesis of AH, one cannot fail to note the important role of neural mechanisms and, in particular, hyperactivation of the SNS is a key pathogenetic mechanism in the development and maintenance of arterial hypertension, especially in the early stages. It does not merely accompany AH but is its triggering and sustaining mechanism, the driving force integrating the influence of stress, metabolic disorders, risk factors, and kidney dysfunction.

A promising direction appears to be the use of techniques aimed at correcting sensory afferentation and sensorimotor integration with subsequent reflex reset of the CNS. P-DTR — therapy restores the possibility of optimal regulation of vascular tone. This opens up opportunities for developing targeted non-drug strategies capable of acting as a neurophysiological counterbalance to SNS hyperactivity. A comprehensive analysis of the neurogenic mechanism of arterial hypertension pathogenesis and determining its place and potential in the complex therapy of AH are key tasks addressed within this article.

Historical and Scientific Foundations of P-DTR — Therapy.

The initial increase in BP most often occurs as a result of exposure to a psychogenic factor on a healthy organism, with which depressor mechanisms can cope by activating baroreflex mechanisms. With a sharp rise in BP, baroreceptors of the aorta and carotid sinus are activated (a fast-acting compensation mechanism)

and send signals to the vasomotor center of the medulla oblongata, leading to a decrease in sympathetic tone and an increase in parasympathetic (vagal) tone, returning pressure to normal. But when depressor mechanisms are depleted, SNS tone becomes predominant.

The physiological foundation of the neurogenic factor in hypertension pathogenesis was laid in the 19th century.

Claude Bernard (French physiologist, 1813–1878) laid the foundations of the neurogenic theory of circulatory regulation, which remain relevant to this day [4]. His experiments first showed that damage to the floor of the fourth ventricle of the brain causes an increase in arterial pressure, which became direct proof of the CNS role in BP regulation. The existence of vasomotor nerves was established.

Walter Cannon (USA) in his book “The Wisdom of the Body” (1932) developed the concept of homeostasis and described in detail the role of the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) in the “fight or flight” response, which is directly related to a sharp rise in BP [5]. W. Cannon was one of the key researchers who radically changed the understanding of the functions of the sympathetic nervous system (SNS). The SNS works constantly, finely modulating organ function, regulating blood vessel diameter to maintain constant arterial pressure

Baroreceptors. Classical view: baroreceptors are “mechanosensitive” nerve endings in the arterial wall (in the carotid sinus and aortic arch) that stretch when pressure increases and send signals to the medulla oblongata. In hypertensive patients, baroreceptor sensitivity is reduced; they gradually reset to a higher pressure level. In hypertension, the arterial wall thickens and becomes rigid. Because of this, it stretches less when pressure rises, and baroreceptors simply do not receive an adequate mechanical stimulus to activate.

Sudakov K. V. [6] cites three researchers — Carl Ludwig, Henry Pickering Bowditch, and Corneille Heymans (Nobel Prize 1938), who discovered the afferent (sensory) and efferent links and the closing of the baroreflex arc. This approach fully corresponds to the theory of functional systems developed by Sudakov, as it requires considering holistic, closed regulatory circuits, not their individual parts.

Thus, by the beginning of the 20th century, it was firmly established that: The SNS regulates vascular tone; in the CNS (medulla oblongata) there are centers controlling arterial pressure; sympathetic nerves can quickly and powerfully increase BP.

Development of the Neurogenic Theory of Hypertension in the 20th Century. Contribution of G. F. Lang and A. L. Myasnikov

G. F. Lang was one of the founders of the neurogenic approach to hypertension. In his classic work “Hypertensive Disease,” he formulated the key idea [7]. Hypertensive disease is a disease of regulation, arising initially as a neurosis of the higher centers of nervous regulation of vascular tone (vasomotor centers), located

in the cerebral cortex, hypothalamus, and medulla oblongata. He linked this to prolonged psychoemotional tension, which was revolutionary for its time.

A. L. Myasnikov, being a student of Lang, developed and supplemented his theory, creating a more complex and detailed concept [8].

Both scientists viewed the sympathetic nervous system as the cornerstone in the pathogenesis of hypertensive disease. The role of the SNS: constant psychoemotional tension, stress, and conflicts (which they considered the main cause of AH) lead to overexcitation of cortical and subcortical centers. This excitation, in turn, is transmitted through the SNS to peripheral vessels, causing their persistent spasm and increased peripheral resistance. The works of these scientists laid the foundation for understanding hypertension as a neurohumoral disorder, which remains relevant in modern cardiology.

The historical aspect clearly demonstrates that the neurogenic concept was not refuted but was deepened and became an integral part of our understanding of arterial hypertension pathogenesis.

A cornerstone of modern neurophysiology is the concept that the sympathetic nervous system performs its functions not autonomously, but under the control of higher levels of the CNS. This ensures the integration of autonomic reactions into the organism's holistic behavioral and emotional activity. The sympathetic nervous system is not an autonomous but a strictly controlled system. Its activity is an accurate and dynamic reflection of the integrative activity of all higher parts of the CNS [9,10].

When factors that increase BP act on the body, the depressor system reduces it using baro- and chemoreceptors. If the stress is strong or chronic, the depressor mechanisms can become depleted and fail to cope with frequent BP increases.

Chronic emotional stress gradually disrupts the function and structure of the prefrontal cortex (PFC) of the brain. Sensory information from the sense organs enters the thalamus, the main subcortical sensory organ, which receives all sensory information (except olfactory). First, the thalamus directs information to the amygdala, as this is a fast, evolutionarily ancient pathway; its task is to provide an instant reaction to a potential threat, even without a full analysis of the situation. The amygdala instantly evaluates this signal exclusively as potentially dangerous and, without waiting for confirmation from the cortex, activates the hypothalamus and brainstem[11]. The body reflexively performs a protective action without conscious awareness of the situation. Under chronic stress, the PFC weakens, and the amygdala becomes hyperactive; through its connections with the hypothalamus, it further activates the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and the sympathetic nervous system, which intensifies hypertension and closes the vicious cycle.

Increased Sympathetic Tone: Direct measurements of neural activity (microneurography) unequivocally show that in patients with essential hypertension,

the tonic activity of sympathetic nerves going to muscles, kidneys, and blood vessels is chronically elevated. This is not just a theory but a measurable fact [12].

Mediated Impact: Stimulation of catecholamine (adrenaline, noradrenaline) release from the adrenal medulla enhances and prolongs these effects.

Role of the Kidneys: It has been discovered that increased sympathetic tone is also directed to the kidneys, constricting blood vessels and stimulating renin production, sodium and water retention, thereby increasing BP.

Humoral Systems Join: The renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), sodium and water retention, cardiac and vascular remodeling, and target organ damage. Now the changes become not just functional but morphological [13,14].

Thus, the SNS is the integral driver of hypertension pathogenesis. It is the initiator, a sustaining factor, and the connecting link. The SNS integrates the influence of numerous risk factors into a unified pathogenetic process.

Since the SNS is constantly involved in the leading trigger and sustaining pathogenetic mechanism of hypertension, it is logical to assume that there are methods for neurophysiological correction of these mechanisms, similar to how pharmacological agents influence individual links in the pathogenesis of hypertension. One such method proposed within alternative medicine is P-DTR.

The principles of treatment according to P-DTR — method are based on a strict scientific concept.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the role of the nervous system in regulating physiological processes was actively studied. I. M. Sechenov[15] laid the foundations of Russian physiology and scientific psychology. His main discovery was central inhibition, proving that the brain not only excites but also suppresses reflexes.

Academician I. P. Pavlov developed the theory of nervism, emphasizing the leading role of the CNS in controlling the work of internal organs [16]. I. P. Pavlov showed that the nervous system can form stable connections between stimulus and response. These studies laid the foundation for understanding the neurogenic nature of functional disorders, which later became a key element of the neuroreflex therapy method.

Sir Charles Sherrington (Nobel Prize 1932) laid the foundations of neurophysiology and introduced the concept of «integrative action of the nervous system.» His work on reciprocal innervation (coordinated tension of one muscle group and relaxation of antagonists) and on reflex arcs is a cornerstone of neurophysiology. Sherrington viewed the nervous system as an integrated whole [17]. He introduced and described in detail the term «proprioception» — the sense of the position and movement of one's own body in space, provided by receptors in muscles, tendons, and joints.

It was C. Sherrington who laid the neurophysiological foundation without which the existence of the neuroreflex therapy method would have been impossible. This method is the practical embodiment of the principles he discovered: the

integrative role of the nervous system and the critical importance of proprioceptive afferentation for controlling functions. Thus, Sherrington's work confirms the scientific validity and logical consistency of the theoretical base of the method P-DTR from the perspective of classical neurophysiology.

Correction of proprioception is the cornerstone of the entire methodology of P-DTR therapy. The name of the method (P-DTR) directly refers to it. The main idea is that the distortion of the proprioceptive signal from a specific receptor is the primary cause of imbalance, pain, increased BP, and other symptoms. All diagnosis and treatment using the neuroreflex therapy method are built on finding and "zeroing out" dysfunctional receptors and distorted signals.

Prof. N. A. Bernstein («On the Construction of Movements,» 1947; biomechanics and physiology of movements) showed that movement is not simply a command from the brain to the muscle but a complex process with feedback, where sensory afferentation (signals from the body to the brain) is critically important for movement correction. P-DTR — therapy is entirely a technique for working with this afferentation [18]. The method works not only with proprioceptors but with the entire sensory system.

The works of C. Sherrington, N. A. Bernstein, and other physiologists showed that proprioceptive afferentation (signals from muscles, tendons, organs, etc.) plays a key role in maintaining postural balance and movement coordination. This became the key foundation of P-DTR method — dysfunctions and chronic pain are considered as a consequence of distorted proprioceptive information, not pain in individual muscles, joints, etc.

Kendall H. O. The book «Muscles: Testing and Function» by H. O. Kendall became a cornerstone of modern physical rehabilitation, orthopedics, and occupational therapy [19]. Any dysfunctional signal affects the myotatic reflex of muscles, and consequently changes the muscular response during manual muscle testing (MMT). Feedback from the CNS can be obtained by determining the myotatic reflex of muscles. Unlike its role in correcting joint biomechanical disorders, MMT in the context of P-DTR — therapy is used for a fundamentally different purpose — to modulate the functional state of the central nervous system. P-DTR — The neuroreflex therapy method is a neurophysiological method for diagnosing and correcting nervous system dysfunctions. Its key idea: the cause of many pain syndromes and dysfunctions is not tissue damage but erroneous sensory (including proprioceptive — deep) afferentation, transmitting a false signal from dysfunctional receptors to the central nervous system.

The key role of neuroreflex mechanisms in the pathogenesis of arterial hypertension is the basis for correcting BP and other dysfunctions.

Correction of BP as a counterbalance to the neurogenic nature of hypertension development is based on identifying and diagnosing dysfunctional

receptors — impaired baro-, chemo-, sympatheto-, mechano-, nociceptors, etc., as well as their modalities. BP correction involves simultaneous stimulation of the primary and compensatory receptors followed by reproduction of a tendon reflex — knee, biceps, triceps. After this, dysfunctional sensory afferentation to the central nervous system ceases, and it begins to form optimal regulatory commands. Treatment takes 15–30 minutes per session, is effective, safe, painless, without the use of medications, invasive procedures, or equipment. A small sample showed a significant improvement in studied indicators after correction with reliability $p < 0.001$ according to the Wilcoxon test [20].

Conclusion.

The neurogenic mechanism of arterial hypertension has received a counterbalance in the form of a correction method — P-DTR. It is important to note that, to date, the scientific literature not only completely lacks information on large randomized studies and meta-analyses but also any publications dedicated to the application of — P-DTR for treating arterial hypertension. Thus, the present work is the first description of the method, demonstrating the potential of this approach.

The scientific and medical community should be acquainted with the new method in order not to miss potential benefits that may be discovered in the process of independent verification and replication of results; in the course of collective analysis, criticism, and improvement (other experts may see in the idea what the author did not see, propose improvements, or new research directions); in the process of open discussions and scientific debates (to subject it to rigorous testing and either confirm its value or reject it, saving time and resources); in the course of timely implementation into practice (if the idea is truly useful, then the sooner it becomes known, the faster it will begin to be applied to improve people's health and save lives).

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EXTRASYSTOLIC ARRHYTHMIA AS A PREDICTOR FOR THE ISCHEMIC STROKE: CLINICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

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Abstract. *Extrasystoles (ES) are the most common arrhythmias in the population. Aim. To establish the relationship between the stroke and ES, to explain the mechanisms in clinical and experimental research. Materials and methods. 634 patients (42–79 years): subgroup 1A (192) — with $ES \geq 700$ per 24 hours, before the peak of transmitral blood flow; 1B (442) — with $ES < 700$ per day, after the peak of transmitral blood flow in the cardiac cycle. Control (106) without AF, with $ES < 700$ per 24 hours. A prospective study was conducted for 1 year. The control end point is the development of ischemic stroke (IS) or transient ischemic attack (TIA). Results. Within 1 year, a significantly higher incidence of IS and TIA was registered in the main group, especially in subgroup 1A, compared to the control group. Conclusions. In ES is forming the “hydraulic shock” — the phenomenon of additional mechanical action on the arterial vessels walls, resulting from an increase in LSV and an increase in intravascular pressure during the passage of the IPES wave. ES is an additional risk factor for IS and TIA. The risk of these complications increases in case if the patient has ES of 700 or more per day, as well as in the presence of ES with ventricular systole before the peak of transmitral blood flow in the cardiac cycle, regardless of ectopic center localization (peak E on EchoCG).*

Keywords: *arrhythmias, extrasystole, stroke, intra-arterial hemodynamics*

Introduction. Extrasystoles (ES) are the most common arrhythmia within the world [1–3]. There are still debates if to treat asymptomatic ES or not [4]. Several

investigations reported about the increased risk of stroke mortality in patients with ES, especially associated with coronary heart disease [5]. In studies, the explanation of the increases risk of the stroke in ES is that this arrhythmia is the reason for the higher risk of atrial fibrillation (AF) that causes the stroke as the most frequent adverse event. The other explanations are the forming of atrial cardiomyopathy with the biochemical, functional and structural changes in atriums as predictor for AF with further stroke [6, 7]. Within predictors stroke, in ECG analysis, researches mention P wave terminal force, interatrial block (also advanced), abnormal P wave axis, PR prolongation and atrial premature complexes, but also meaning the higher risk of AF [9]. To reveal the non-diagnosed AF, it is recommended to do long-term Holter monitoring (3 days, 7 days) [9–11].

Within traditional risk factors for the stroke, in the list of arrhythmia, there is AF, and there is no ES. In our previous publications, we paid attention to the cases of cryptogenic stroke that were more frequent in patients with ES, without AF, and found the explanation for this from the point of view of intra-arterial hemodynamic changes [12, 13]. Moreover, we proposed the functional classification of ES based on the principles of the time of their appearance in cardiac cycle, independent from the ectopic center localization [14].

Aim. To establish the relationship between the stroke and ES, to explain the mechanisms in clinical and experimental research.

Materials and Methods. We performed a single-center prospective study with participation of 634 patients aged 42 to 79 years old. All patients had ES 700 and more per 24 hours, diagnosed during 24-hours Holter ECG. The control group were 106 patients with ES less than 700 per 24 hours. None of the patients included in the study, had AF. Depending on the ES characteristics, we divided patients of the main group into two subgroups. Subgroup 1A (192 people) consisted of patients with EC 700 or more per 24 hours, with the moment of occurrence of ventricular systole ES before the peak of transmitral blood flow in the cardiac cycle (peak E according to pulsed wave Doppler in transthoracic echocardiography (EchoCG) — “early” ES). Subgroup 1B (442 people) — patients with ES 700 or more per 24 hours, with the moment of occurrence of ventricular systole ES after the peak of transmitral blood flow in the cardiac cycle — “late” ES. We divided ES independent to the electric topic localization, depending to the moment of their appearance in biomechanical cardiac cycle — before or after the transmitral blood flow peak. Subgroup 1B was larger than subgroup 1A, because this variant of ES was more common. Including the patients to participate in the study, we tried to minimize the possible influence of traditional risk factors for the stroke. Thus, the exclusion criteria included: atrial fibrillation; resistant arterial hypertension; secondary arterial hypertension; intracardiac thrombosis; left ventricle or aorta aneurysms; heart failure NYHAI

or more; hemodynamically significant atheromas of any location; hematological diseases; prosthetic heart valves; myocardial infarction (MI) or stroke less than 1 year ago; cardiomyopathy; COPD of more than mild severity.

The present study conformed to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and was performed with the approval of the Ethics Committee of Samara State medical university № 239 dated 10.11.2021. Written informed consent was received from all study participants.

All patients underwent instrumental and laboratory methods: transthoracic or transesophageal EchoCG; 24-hours Holter ECG monitoring; stress echocardiography with bicycle; digital apexcardiography (ACG) and sphygmography (SG) of the common carotid artery, posterior tibial artery; Doppler ultrasound of the brachiocephalic arteries, abdominal aorta and its branches, arteries of the lower extremities; coronary angiography. In Doppler ultrasound, we detected the presence and severity of atherosclerotic lesions; in case of detection of atheromas, we used the international scales ECST, NASCET and St. Mary's Ratio to calculate the percentage of stenosis by diameter. When grading atherosclerotic plaques, we used the Gray-Weale-Nikolaides classification. During the EchoCG, we paid the special attention to the absence of intracardiac thrombi of any location, and in the case of ES, the moment of ventricular systole of ES in the cardiac cycle relative to the mitral valve peak E on EchoCG was determined when assessing transmitral blood flow. Laboratory research methods were also performed, which necessarily included the determination of hemostasis parameters and a lipid profile. All patients were on standard therapy recommended by the current ESC guidelines.

We performed prospective observation for 1 year from the onset of the study. Control endpoints are the development of ischemic stroke (IS) or transient ischemic attack (TIA).

The experimental part was performed with created by us original "Device for modeling of intra-arterial circulation" (patent for utility model RU202780U1 dated 03.05.2021). This device provided us with the opportunity to visualize the intra-arterial hemodynamics under various options (for example, with stenotic narrowing, with a regular heart rhythm, with ES). The main part is of a cone-shaped narrowed glass cylinder — a rotameter — a prototype of the arterial vessel. The cylinder is mounted on metal stands with stops to a horizontal surface. At the inlet end, there is a fitting with an inlet valve for the possibility of introducing indicators — coloring liquids (ink), thread or a piezo-crystalline pressure sensor into the tube. As the imitation of the blood, we used an aqueous glycerol solution inside the contour of the system. The imitation the blood flow in the regular heart rhythm, as well as in ES is possible due to the various modes of a water pump.

During statistical analysis, each parameter was assessed for normality of distribution. With a normal distribution, we used the methods of parametric statistics:

the characteristics of quantitative variables were made in the form of the mean value and standard deviation, and intergroup comparisons were carried out using one-way analysis of variance indicating the values of the F criterion, degrees of freedom (df) and statistical significance of the model (p). In case of violation of normality of distribution, quantitative indicators were characterized by medians and quartiles 1 and 3 (Q1 and Q3), and intergroup comparisons were carried out by the Kruskal-Wallis method indicating the value of the H statistic and the p value. Categorical variables were characterized by reporting frequencies and percentages. We considered differences between group parameters to be statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed using MedCalc® Statistical Software version 20.118 (MedCalc Software Ltd, Ostend, Belgium; <https://www.medcalc.org>; 2022), GraphPad Prism for Windows, version 10.1.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA, www.graphpad.com) and the free software environment R (<https://cran.rstudio.com/>).

Results and discussion. Initially in clinical, laboratory and instrumental data, the patients of the main subgroups and the control group were equal (Table 1).

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of the groups.

Parameter	Cath- gory	Group			Statistics
		1A N=192	1B N=442	Control N=106	
Age, y. o. Median, (Q1, Q3) ¹		64 (59; 69)	64 (58; 68)	62 (55; 67)	H=5.755, p=0.056
Gender, n (%) ²	w	94 (49.0)	216 (48.9)	52 (49.1)	$\chi^2 = 0.001$, df = 2, p = 0.999
	m	98 (51.0)	226 (51.1)	54 (50.9)	
Smoking, n (%) ²	Yes	39 (20.3)	97 (22.0)	22 (20.8)	$\chi^2 = 0.239$, df = 2, p = 0.887
Arterial hypertension, n (%) ²	1 grade	78 (40.6)	174 (39.4)	44 (41.5)	$\chi^2 = 1.358$, df = 4, p = 0.852
	2 grade	98 (51.0)	224 (50.7)	55 (51.9)	
	No	16 (8.3)	44 (10.0)	7 (6.6)	
Body mass index, Median, (Q1, Q3) ¹		27 (24.0; 31.0)	27 (23.0; 31.0)	27 (23.0; 30.0)	H=0.033, p=0.983
COPD, n (%) ²	Yes	36 (18.8)	88 (19.9)	17 (16.0)	$\chi^2 = 0.847$, df = 2, p = 0.655
Diabetes Mellitus 2 type, n (%) ²	Yes	20 (10.4)	48 (10.9)	18 (17.0)	$\chi^2 = 3.486$, df = 2, p = 0.175
NYHAI, n (%) ²	Yes	115 (59.9)	238 (53.9)	61 (57.6)	$\chi^2 = 2.116$, df = 2, p = 0.347
NYHAI, n (%) ²	Yes	77 (40.1)	204 (46.2)	45 (42.5)	$\chi^2 = 2.116$, df = 2, p = 0.348

Stable angina, n (%) ²	I class	95 (49.5)	220 (49.8)	54 (50.9)	$\chi^2 = 0.452, df = 4, p = 0.978$
	II class	65 (33.9)	154 (34.8)	34 (32.1)	
	No	32 (16.7)	68 (15.4)	18 (17.0)	
MI in anamnesis, n (%) ²	Yes	38 (19.8)	87 (19.7)	21 (19.8)	$\chi^2 = 0.676, df = 4, p = 0.954$
IS, TIA in anamnesis, n (%) ²	Yes	13 (6.8)	34 (7.7)	7 (6.6)	$\chi^2 = 0.256, df = 2, p = 0.880$
Distal arterial embolism in anamnesis, n (%) ²	Yes	1 (0.5)	3 (0.7)	1 (0.9)	$\chi^2 = 0.182, df = 2, p = 0.913$
Hypokinesia of the left ventricle, n (%)	Yes	48 (25.0)	131 (29.6)	20 (18.9)	$\chi^2 = 5.516, df = 2.000, p = 0.063$
Any stenosis in coronary angiography, n (%)	Yes	160 (83.3)	374 (84.6)	88 (83.0)	$\chi^2 = 0.263, df = 2.000, p = 0.877$
Hemodynamically insignificant carotid stenosis, n (%)	Yes	67 (34.9)	156 (35.3)	38 (35.9)	$\chi^2 = 0.027, df = 2.000, p = 0.986$
Plaque Type III, n (%)	Yes	31 (16.2)	69 (15.6)	16 (15.1)	$\chi^2 = 0.061, df = 2.000, p = 0.970$
Hemodynamically insignificant lower extremities stenosis, n (%)	Yes	21 (10.9)	53 (12.0)	13 (12.3)	$\chi^2 = 0.174, df = 2.000, p = 0.917$

¹ Kruskal-Wallis test;² χ^2 -Pearson test

However, in control endpoints analysis in 1 year in patients ES 700 or more per 24 hours, a statistically significantly higher incidence of IS or TIA was revealed, in comparison with the control group, especially the highest incidence had patients of subgroup 1A — with ES, with ES before transmitral blood flow peak E on EchoCG (Table 2).

Table 2. IS and TIA in 1 year within the groups.

Complication	Group			p, Fisher's exact test	
	1A N=192	1B N=442	Control N=106		
IS and TIA, n (%)	Yes	18 (9.4)	17 (3.9)	1 (0.9)	0.002
	No	174 (90.6)	425 (96.2)	105 (99.1)	

Thus, in patients with ES before the peak of transmitral blood flow peak in the cardiac cycle 700 or more per 24 hours OR = 7.923 (2.377, 26.406), z = 3.370, p < 0.001. At the same time, in patients with ES after the peak of transmitral blood flow peak in the cardiac cycle in an amount of 700 or more per 24 hours OR = 2.500 (0.748, 8.353), z = 1.489, p = 0.137. The presence of any ES 700 and more

per 24 hours was generally characterized by OR = 3.989 (1.231, 12.930), $z = 2.306$, $p = 0.021$. That is, for the development of IS or TIA, not only the number of ES more than 700 per 24 hours mattered, but also their quality, namely, in what phase of the cardiac cycle they occurred.

To explain the results we obtained, we analyzed the hemodynamic parameters characterizing each variant of ES in the subgroups and in the control group. The main parameters were: linear blood flow velocity and volumetric blood flow in the common carotid and posterior tibial arteries Doppler ultrasound imaging. For patients of subgroups 1A and 1B, we calculated these parameters for the regular, ES and first post-extrasystolic (1PES) cardiac cycle. The main hemodynamic parameters within the groups see in Table 3.

Table 3. Linear blood flow velocity, volumetric blood flow, in 1PES of patients of 1A and 1B subgroups and control group.

Parameter/ group	Artery	1A N=192	1B N=442	Control N=106	Statistics
Linear blood flow velocity, sm/sec, Median (Q1; Q3) ¹	Common carotid artery	108.0 (82.8; 126.0)	89.0 (75.0; 102.0)	61.0 (52.3; 74.8)	H=239.380, p<0.001
	Posterior tibial artery	63.0 (52.0; 70.3)	54.0 (46.0; 63.0)	39.5 (30.0; 48.8)	H=187.833, p<0.001
Volumetric blood flow, ml/min, Median (Q1; Q3) ¹	Common carotid artery	507.5 (489.0; 522.3)	420.0 (408.3; 432.0)	318.5 (306.3; 335.0)	H=566.521, p<0.001
	Posterior tibial artery	45.0 (38.0; 52.0)	37.0 (31.0; 42.0)	29.0 (24.0; 34.0)	H=239.191, p<0.001

Note. Each parameter differs pairwise between groups at $p < 0.001$ ¹ Kruskal-Wallis test

In 1PES, there is an increase in analyzed parameters of hemodynamics is observed, especially in ES with ventricular systole before the peak of transmitral blood flow E on EchoCG in the cardiac cycle. In other words, the moment of ventricular systole of the ES in the cardiac cycle plays a predetermining role for the parameters of hemodynamics, of the 1PES following this ES.

Increased hemodynamic and kinetic parameters of the 1PES wave are associated, in our opinion, by the appearance of the so-called “hydraulic shock” phenomenon. By this term, we mean an additional mechanical effect on the wall of arterial vessels that occurs as a result of an increase in linear blood flow velocity and an increase in intravascular pressure during the passage of the 1PES wave. Against the background of multifocal atherosclerosis, the repeated influence of “hydraulic shock” with frequent ES leads to chronic trauma to existing atheromas of the main arteries. As a result, this may pose a risk for the development of long-term

complications even in the presence of hemodynamically insignificant plaques. Thus, if they have signs of instability (uneven contour, heterogeneity with the inclusion of calcium, and others), then the repeated mechanical effect of the “hydraulic shock” phenomenon can become a kind of trigger mechanism for vascular complications, leading to the development of thrombosis on the plaque, tears, and also embolism of the part atheroma along the arterial vessel. This mechanism may become key in explaining the possible reasons for the development of some cryptogenic IS, when cardio embolic causes have been excluded.

The existence of the “hydraulic shock” phenomenon was demonstrated in experimental part of the trial using the “Device for modeling of intra-arterial circulation” (Figure 1).

Figure 1. “Device for modeling of intra-arterial circulation”, general view.

With the variable fluid speed, we simulated the blood flow inside the artery in regular heart rhythm and ES, which differed in the time of occurrence of ventricular systole of ES in the cardiac cycle. A piezo-crystal pressure sensor was installed inside the tube by inserting it from the side of the two-way fitting to control and determine pressure fluctuations inside the rotameter at the moment of passage of pulse waves. Data from the pressure sensor was transferred to an oscilloscope and stored on a computer. From the inlet end of the tube, an indicator — a silk thread — 25 mm long was introduced into the tube through the valve of a two-way fitting. As the experiment progressed, a dye (blue ink) was periodically introduced through the valve of the fitting to contrast the glycerol solution. The movement of the free end of the silk thread was monitored at the regular heart rhythm and in ES, which differed in the time of occurrence of ventricular systole of ES in the cardiac cycle. An increase in the mechanical effect of the pressure wave on the tube wall occurred when simulating the passage of the 1PES wave in all variants of ES, but was inversely proportional to the time of occurrence of ES in the cardiac cycle. Thus, when simulating “early” ES — with ventricular systole ES occurring before the peak of the TC, the intensity of the mechanical action of the pressure wave on the wall of the rotameter tube in 1PES was maximum (Table 4, Figure 2).

Table 4. Displacement of the indicator — silk thread — when simulating a regular pulse wave and 1PES.

Oscillation of an indicator — silk thread relative to a vertical plane, type of experiment	Number of experiments	Q1	Median	Q3	Mean	SD
Oscillation of thread, regular pulse wave, mm	40	3.75	5.00	6.25	4.93	1.54
Oscillation of thread, 1PES in “early” ES, mm	40	8.75	10.00	11.00	9.80	1.76
Oscillation of thread, 1PES in “late” ES, mm	40	6.75	7.00	9.00	7.55	1.63

Figure 2. Change in pressure inside the device rotameter when simulating various ES (%), oscilloscope data (N=40).

After that, we reproduced a marginal plaque, complicated with thrombus, with a 50% diameter stenosis. To do this, liquid plastic was attached to the wall of the rotameter, imitating the shape of an atherosclerotic plaque, narrowing the lumen of the vessel by 50%. After the plastic had dried, we glued it with red silicone (of indifferent density) as the imitation of a thrombus. Further, the circuit of the “Device for modeling of intra-arterial circulation” was filled with an aqueous solution of glycerol. Indicators — silk thread and dye — clerical ink — were alternately introduced into the rotameter tube. The purpose of this experiment was to study intra-arterial

hemodynamics in the presence of a hemodynamically insignificant atherosclerotic plaque when simulating ES. During the passage of the 1PES wave, the appearance of reflected, standing waves, turbulent fluid flow was recorded, and a rarefaction zone was observed following the plaque along the fluid flow. After several repeated “hydraulic shocks”, its mechanical action was enough to cause the detachment of a thrombus from the atheroma with further embolism (Figure 3).

Figure 3. “Device for modeling of intra-arterial circulation” in simulating a 50% marginal atheroma complicated by a thrombus. The moment of separation of the thrombus from the atheroma during the passage of the 1PES wave.

Conclusions.

1. In ES is forming the “hydraulic shock” — the phenomenon of additional mechanical action on the arterial vessels walls, resulting from an increase in LSV and an increase in intravascular pressure during the passage of the 1PES wave.

2. ES is an additional risk factor for IS and TIA. The risk of these complications increases in case if the patient has ES of 700 or more per day, as well as in the presence of ES with ventricular systole before the peak of transmitral blood flow in the cardiac cycle, regardless of ectopic center localization (peak E on EchoCG).

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ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VARIOUS METHODS OF PANCREATODUODENAL RESECTIONS

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Abstract. *A comparative analysis of the effectiveness of pancreatoduodenal resections utilizing VR technologies and ultrasound navigation was performed. The use of intraoperative ultrasound navigation and VR technologies enabled optimization of the surgical technique, resulting in a significant reduction in operative time and intraoperative blood loss. the rate of radical surgeries was significantly higher; a statistically significant reduction in operative time and intraoperative blood loss was achieved.*

Keywords: *pancreatic cancer; robotic surgery; effectiveness of surgical approaches, pancreatoduodenal resections.*

Relevance. Pancreatic adenocarcinoma is an extremely aggressive form of cancer with low survival rates [1]. Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma is globally recognized as the most challenging type of cancer, a malignant tumor projected to become the third leading cause of cancer mortality worldwide by 2026. This necessitates the refinement of surgical approaches in the treatment of pancreatic cancer [2–4].

Study objective: to analyze the effectiveness of pancreatoduodenal resections utilizing VR technologies and ultrasound navigation.

Materials and methods. The study included 157 patients aged 35 to 75 years who underwent inpatient treatment from 2015 to 2024. Patients were divided into two groups: the main group included 59 patients treated according to the developed protocol employing VR technologies and ultrasound navigation; The control group comprised 98 patients treated according to established protocols, primarily involving retrospective analysis of medical documentation.

The collected data were processed using classical variational statistical methods. The significance of differences between the compared groups was determined by the Student's t-test.

Results. In the control group, open pancreatoduodenal resections (PDR) predominated (51 cases), along with laparoscopic interventions (30 cases) and robotic surgeries (9 cases). In the main group, by contrast, there was a shift towards laparoscopic (31 cases) and robotic procedures (28 cases). Distal resection was performed exclusively in patients of the control group (8 cases).

Table 1 — Types of surgical interventions in the groups

Type of intervention	Control group (n=98)	Main group (n=59)	Total (n=157)
Open pancreatoduodenal resection (PDR)	51 (52.0%)	0 (0.0%)	51 (32.5%)
Laparoscopic pancreatoduodenal resection (PDR)	30 (30.6%)	31 (52.5%)	61 (38.9%)
Robotic PDR	9 (9.2%)	28 (47.5%)	37 (23.6%)
Distal PDR	8 (8.2%)	0 (0.0%)	8 (5.1%)

In the control group, surgeries were predominantly performed using the standard technique, while Ultrasound Navigation and VR technologies were extensively utilized in the main group.

Table 2 — Application of technologies in groups. All surgeries in the main group were performed using VR

Type of intervention	Technology	Control group	Main group
Distal PDR	Standard	8	0
Laparoscopic pancreatoduodenal resection (PDR)	Standard	19	0
	Ultrasound Navigation	11	31
Open pancreatoduodenal resection (PDR)	Standard	19	0
	with Ultrasound Navigation	32	0
Robotic PDR	Ultrasound Navigation	9	28

As shown in the table, all surgical interventions in the main group were performed using VR support and Ultrasound Navigation. In the control group, standard techniques predominated — both in distal and in laparoscopic and open pancreatoduodenectomy procedures. Nevertheless, Ultrasound Navigation was also used in the control group in 11 cases during laparoscopic access and 32 cases during open surgeries.

Incidence of achieving R0 resection

One of the key criteria for the radicality of surgical intervention in malignant pancreatic neoplasms is achieving R0 resection, i. e., complete tumor removal with

negative resection margins. This indicator largely determines the prognosis and long-term treatment outcomes.

In the conducted study, the frequency of achieving R0 resection differed significantly between the main and control groups. In the main group, where modern technologies (intraoperative Ultrasound Navigation, VR) were employed, the proportion of radical surgeries was markedly higher.

Table 3 — Data by oncological resection type

Indicator	Control group (n=98)	Main group (n=59)	Total (n=157)	p
R0 resection: Yes	55 (56.1%)	49 (83.1%)	104 (66.2%)	0.001
R0 resection: No	43 (43.9%)	10 (16.9%)	53 (33.8%)	.

The data obtained indicate that the use of navigation technologies and VR significantly increases the likelihood of performing a radical resection. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the groups ($p = 0.001$), which on one hand appears to confirm the effectiveness of integrating modern techniques into surgical practice. However, on the other hand, R0 resection was assessed solely by macroscopic examination. Considering the significant percentage of invasion of major vessels, in these cases the term R0 resection can be applied only tentatively.

Duration and blood loss

Analysis of intraoperative parameters demonstrated marked differences between the primary and control groups. Specifically, the key indicators reflecting the complexity and invasiveness of the procedure are surgical duration and blood loss volume.

Table 4 — Surgical duration and blood loss volume

Indicator	Control group (n=98)	Main group (n=59)	p
Surgical duration, min	433.6 ± 60.8 (median 434.5; 236–564)	354.3 ± 51.0 (median 349; 262–475)	<0.001
Blood loss, ml	935.8 ± 227.5 (median 963; 331–1436)	610.6 ± 179.7 (median 618; 286–1167)	<0.001

The obtained results demonstrate a statistically significant advantage of the primary group in both parameters ($p < 0.001$). It can be assumed that the application of intraoperative ultrasound navigation and VR technologies allowed optimization of the surgical technique, which manifested as a significant reduction in operation time and intraoperative blood loss.

In addition, an analysis of the length of hospital stay between groups was performed. Figure 3.2 shows the length of hospital stay in the main and control groups.

Figure 1 — Length of Hospital Stay in the Groups

The figure demonstrates that the median length of hospital stay in the main group was 14 days, compared to 17 days in the control group. Moreover, the range of values in the main group was narrower, indicating more homogeneous treatment outcomes and a decreased number of patients with prolonged postoperative hospitalization.

The obtained data may indicate that the adoption of modern technologies contributes to a significant reduction in hospitalization duration and provides more consistent postoperative results.

The analysis of treatment outcomes included an assessment of immediate postoperative results and long-term indicators. The average length of hospital stay in the main group was significantly lower than that in the control group, reflecting fewer complications and faster patient recovery. Reoperations were required significantly less frequently in patients in the main group. Furthermore, the pain level assessed by the visual analog scale (VAS) was lower, indicating a less traumatic character of interventions employing modern technologies (Table 5).

The rate of reoperations was lower in the main group (5.1% versus 14.3%, $p=0.048$), which may indicate a reduction in complications necessitating surgical correction. Additionally, patients in the main group reported lower pain intensity

on the VAS scale (4.3 ± 1.0 versus 6.1 ± 1.2 points, $p < 0.001$), indicating the effectiveness of the applied surgical techniques and perioperative analgesia.

Table 5 — Data on reoperations and VAS

Indicator	Control group (n=98)	Main group (n=59)	p
Length of hospital stay, days	18.2 ± 4.6	13.9 ± 3.8	<0.001
Reoperation, n (%)	14 (14.3%)	3 (5.1%)	0.048
Pain intensity (VAS, points)	6.1 ± 1.2	4.3 ± 1.0	<0.001

TConclusions. The application of intraoperative ultrasound navigation and VR technologies enabled optimization of the surgical technique, which was reflected in a statistically significant reduction in operative time and intraoperative blood loss. Concurrently, the rate of radical resections was significantly increased, accompanied by a statistically significant reduction in operative time and intraoperative blood loss.

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CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE SOFT TISSUES IN THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION AND NECK IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of cystic lesions of the maxillofacial and neck soft tissues in children as an independent group of pathological processes necessitating timely surgical intervention. The relevance of the study is determined by the high incidence of congenital and acquired neck cysts in childhood and the risk of complications arising from delayed diagnosis.*

The objective of the study is to evaluate the clinical and diagnostic characteristics of cystic lesions in the cervical region in children and to perform a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of conservative and surgical treatment approaches.

Materials and methods: a retrospective analysis of the medical records of patients admitted to the surgical department of Turkestan City Children's Hospital between 2020 and 2025 was conducted. Clinical, instrumental (ultrasound, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, contrast radiography), and morphological (fine-needle biopsy with histological examination) methods were employed.

Results: it was determined that cystic lesions at early stages often remain asymptomatic and are detected incidentally. With an increase in size, the risk of inflammation, purulent transformation, and fistula tract formation increases. Surgical excision of the lesion is recognized as the most effective treatment approach; in cases presenting with inflammatory changes, phased treatment is indicated.

Conclusions: timely diagnosis and appropriately selected surgical tactics provide a favorable prognosis and minimize the risk of recurrence.

Keywords: *cyst, cervical region, children, diagnosis, surgical treatment, fistula, embryogenesis.*

Introduction

Pathological processes in the child's body inevitably cause concern among parents. This is fully relevant to cystic, neoplastic, and tumor-like lesions of the maxillofacial region and neck, which often present with a paucisymptomatic course and are identified at advanced stages of development.

According to scientific literature, odontogenic cysts constitute 80–85% of all tumors and tumor-like lesions of the jaws, with approximately 95% of these being periapical (inflammatory) cysts. Jaw keratocysts account for 5.4 to 17.4% of all odontogenic cysts [1–5]. In children, developmental anomalies of the branchial apparatus represent 17–20% of all neck pathologies. Most commonly (in 90–95% of cases), anomalies of the second branchial cleft are encountered, with about 75% of these manifesting as cysts. According to the classification by G. V. Falileev (1978) and current classifications of soft tissue tumors, neoplasms of dysembryonal origin, including cysts, comprise up to 34.9%. At the same time, according to data from several authors, tumors of dysembryonal origin are relatively rare overall and constitute approximately 7%. Median neck cysts account for up to 70% of all congenital neoplasms in the neck region and about 12.7% of congenital soft tissue anomalies in the maxillofacial region. When collecting complaints and medical history, particular attention is paid to the duration of the lesion, its growth rate, the presence of neck trauma, and other clinically significant factors [6–9].

Features of coding a disease or condition (group of diseases or conditions) according to the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems

K04.8 Radicular cyst

K09 Cysts of the oral region, not classified elsewhere

K09.0 Cysts arising during tooth development

K09.2 Other cysts of the jaws

K09.8 Other specified cysts of the oral cavity, not classified elsewhere

K11.6 Mucocele of salivary gland

- Q18.0 Branchial cleft sinus, fistula, and cyst
- Q18.1 Preauricular sinus and cyst
- Q18.2 Other branchial cleft anomalies
- Q18.8 Other specified malformations of the face and neck
- D21.0 Benign neoplasms of connective and other soft tissues of the head, face, and neck
- L72.0 Epidermal cyst

Classification of disease or condition (groups of diseases or conditions)

Classification of jaw cysts

The most comprehensive classification is considered to be the clinicomorphological classification of tumors and tumor-like lesions of the jaws, developed by a working group comprising I. I. Ermolaev, V. V. Panikarovskiy, A. I. Paches, B. D. Kabakov, V. M. Bentsianova, and S. Ya. Balsevich (1975).

Jaw cysts are presented in section ‘B – Tumor-like lesions’ and are subdivided into:

I. Epithelial:

1. *Odontogenic cysts:* a) primordial cyst (primordial keratocyst); b) eruption cyst; c) paradental (periodontal) cyst; d) gingival cyst; e) dentigerous cyst; f) follicular cyst; g) root (radicular) cyst.

2. *Non-odontogenic cysts:* a) nasopalatine duct cyst (incisive canal cyst); b) deep maxillary cyst (fissural cyst); c) nasolabial cyst; d) cholesteatoma;

II. Non-epithelial cysts:

Bone cysts (aneurysmal, traumatic, hemorrhagic) A. K. Iordanishvili clinical classification of jaw cysts (2000):

Periapical cysts: – apical (periapical, radicular); – residual; – Pericoronal (follicular, eruption cysts) – retromolar (paradental cysts).

Primary cyst (keratocyst, primordial cyst).

Nasopalatine canal cyst (incisive foramen cyst).

Cholesteatomas of the jaws.

Traumatic (simple, hemorrhagic, or unicameral bone cysts).

Aneurysmal bone cyst.

Globulomaxillary cyst.

Nasolabial cyst (nasopalveolar, extraosseous cyst).

The development of the midline neck cyst begins during the 3rd to 4th week of gestation, when the embryo forms an evagination of the ventral pharyngeal wall – the thyroid gland primordium. Additionally, the thyroglossal duct forms in this area, connecting the thyroid tissue to the root of the tongue [10,11,12,13,14,15]. As the embryo grows, the duct elongates and becomes thinner, and its lumen gradually closes due to connective tissue proliferation.

Figure 1. Midline neck cyst in a child

In the development of the median neck cyst in children, all the above-mentioned processes become disrupted. The duct fails to obliterate; by the 18th to 20th week of intrauterine development it becomes epithelialized, transforming into a hollow tract that gives rise to a cystic cavity. The clinical significance of this condition in pediatric maxillofacial surgery is determined by the risk of its suppuration and the occurrence of other local complications [16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30].

Methods and materials: At the Department of Maxillofacial Surgery of the Turkestan City Children’s Hospital, 34 patients presenting with cystic lesions of 2 to 5 years’ duration were treated as inpatients during the period from 2020 to 2025.

Table 1. Distribution of patients by age and sex

Group	Number of patients	Sex		Age			
		Male	Female	2–7 years		7–14 years	14–18 years
Main group	34	15	19	11		15	9
TOTAL	34	15	19	11		15	9

Table 2. Distribution of pediatric patients by nosological entities

Median neck cyst	Median neck fistula	Cysts of the sub-mandibular salivary gland	Sublingual neck cyst
20	8	4	2
TOTAL: 34			

Cystic cavities of small and medium sizes are usually painless, do not cause difficulties with articulation, mastication, or the larynx, are asymptomatic in children, and are not detectable during clinical examination. The median neck cyst gradually increases in size and by preschool or early school age reaches 2–3 cm in diameter, occasionally attaining the size of a chicken egg. A midline cyst in children is a rounded swelling located in the upper half of the neck and is best detected when the head is tilted backward. Palpation of this area is painless.

The mass has an elastic consistency, is easily displaced laterally and upward, while its downward mobility is limited. The cavity is anatomically connected to the hyoid bone and moves synchronously with it during swallowing. As the midline cyst enlarges, it becomes visible and the child experiences a number of unpleasant symptoms, including difficulty bending the neck; an increase in temperature to 37–37.2 °C in cases of purulent complications; redness of the skin adjacent to the cystic structure; tenderness upon palpation of the lesion.

Clinical signs of a lateral cyst in children are similar to those of a median cyst but present more intensively. Signs indicating the development of a lateral neck cyst in a child typically appear following trauma or as a consequence of an infectious-inflammatory process. The symptomatology accompanying this form of neoplasm may include the following: the tumor enlarges excessively (reaching a diameter of up to 10 cm) and becomes visible to the naked eye; the adjacent lymph node enlarges; sharp pain occurs due to compression of the neurovascular bundle; the larynx is displaced to the opposite side of the neck; breathing becomes difficult;

After obtaining the medical history, including a parental interview, as well as conducting inspection and palpation of the child's neck, the physician will order a series of laboratory and instrumental examinations. They typically include:

- complete blood and urine analyses, ECG, chest radiography to exclude contraindications for surgical intervention;
- contrast-enhanced MRI of the neck when a lateral cyst is suspected, allowing precise determination of the lesion's location, size, and cyst cavity contents;
- fistulography (contrast study of the fistulous tract if present);
- cyst puncture when indicated for histological examination;
- ultrasound of the neck if the available data are insufficient.

Management of cystic lesions of the maxillofacial region and neck in children

Conservative management is not used; therefore, the only way to eliminate the cystic cavity is surgical treatment. The timing of surgical treatment is determined individually, considering the child's age, the size and growth rate of the lesion, and the presence of complications. Two approaches to surgical intervention exist, depending on the specific clinical situation:

- **Single-stage excision.** Single-stage excision of the cystic cavity with all its walls, along with resection of the hyoid bone, is performed to prevent disease recurrence. This surgical approach is recognized as the standard procedure for the planned excision of a median neck cyst.

- **Two-stage removal.** This technique was developed for the management of infected (suppurative) cavities.

During the first stage, puncture is performed to evacuate the contents and irrigate with antiseptics. Following a course of oral antibiotic therapy and resolution of local inflammatory signs, radical cyst excision is carried out. To increase treatment efficacy, modern surgery utilizes guided laser or argon plasma coagulation. Instrumental methods are employed to treat the surface of the hyoid bone to completely eliminate the epithelium of the remnants of the stylohyoid duct and prevent recurrence. During the operation, the muscular framework of the neck is restored in layers to ensure the physiological process of swallowing and other movements of the mandible.

Analysis and Results of the Study

The results of the study confirmed the effectiveness of surgical intervention in both one-stage and two-stage cyst removal procedures. The application of instrumental techniques for surface treatment of the hyoid bone demonstrated a significant reduction in the risk of recurrence, consistent with recent publications and corroborated by clinical practice.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of literature and clinical data, it can be concluded that cystic lesions of the maxillofacial region and neck in children may be detected across all age groups and occur in both boys and girls without a significant gender predilection. All patients presenting with such lesions require prompt and mandatory surgical treatment, as inadequate therapy may result in purulent-inflammatory complications, involvement of adjacent tissues, and the formation of fistulas and plegmons. Insufficient understanding of the clinical manifestations of cystic lesions leads to diagnostic and surgical management errors, underscoring the need for a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis and treatment of these patients. Timely diagnosis, understanding of the clinical presentation, and appropriate surgical management are key factors in the successful treatment of cystic lesions of the maxillofacial region and neck in children.

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PREVENTIVE CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF MILD CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS USING AUTOPLASMA

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All patients were examined at the Derzhavin Dental Department of Tomsk State University. The following were exclusion criteria:

Preventive conservative treatment of mild chronic generalized periodontitis using autologous plasma once every six months to prolong remission and reduce treatment time. All patients were examined at the G. R. Derzhavin Tomsk State University, Department of Dentistry, Tambov, Russia.

In accordance with the objectives of this research, clinical, clinical laboratory, laboratory, and statistical research methods were used.

Keywords: *clinical laboratory, laboratory and statistical methods for studying oral hygiene in periodontal diseases.*

The results are in Table 2. The criteria for exclusion of patients from the study were:

Criteria for exclusion of patients from the study	Pregnancy and lactation period.
Criteria for exclusion of patients from the study	Patients with a history of neoplasms.
Criteria for exclusion of patients from the study	Taking medications that affect the level of bone resorption and gum hypertrophy.
Criteria for exclusion of patients from the study	Presence of: diabetes mellitus type I and II, osteoporosis, allergic and infectious diseases.

The patient's examination began with anamnestic data collection, focusing on possible prerequisites for the development of this periodontal pathology.

Each patient underwent autologous plasma injections five times.

During the first visit, autologous plasma injections were performed in two segments of the upper jaw (1st and 2nd); during the second visit, 3 days later, in the lower jaw (3rd and 4th); the third visit after 1 week; the fourth visit after 1 month; and the fifth visit after 6 months.

Starting with the third visit, autologous plasma injections were performed in all four segments.

Insulin needles were used for autologous plasma injections into the mucosal fold. Volume and area of plasma injection: 0.1–0.2 ml to the papillae; 0.3–0.5 ml to the mucosal fold. Moreover, if therapeutic and preventive measures were carried out, the means and methods used were determined, as well as whether adequate oral hygiene was maintained.

To assess the severity of gingivitis and subsequently record the progression of the process, the papillary-marginal-alveolar index (PMA) was used.

Various modifications of this index have been proposed, but we used the PMA index as modified by Parma (1960).

Gum condition was assessed using the following codes and criteria:

- 0 – no inflammation,
- 1 – inflammation of the gingival papilla only (P),
- 2 – inflammation of the marginal gingiva (M),
- 3 – inflammation of the alveolar gingiva (A).

The PMA index was calculated using the formula:

The normal PMA index is 0. The higher the index value, the more severe the gingivitis. PMA index evaluation criteria:

- 0 – no gingivitis up to 30%
- mild gingivitis 30–60%
- moderate gingivitis 61% and above
- severe gingivitis.

Chronic periodontitis is known to activate the physiological processes of lipid peroxidation in the body, which is manifested by suppression of local immunity and contributes to the development of a long-term inflammatory process.

The results of the study were interpreted taking into account differential indicators. Microsoft Excel for Windows, v. 8.0, was used for statistical data processing and graphic production.

Using this package, we obtained pairwise correlation coefficients, linear regression coefficients, and single-factor linear regression equations.

These were used to calculate a model of expected periodontal health dynamics after our comprehensive treatment, six months later, based on data obtained before and immediately after the procedure.

Basic methods of variation statistics were used for statistical analysis and description of the obtained data.

Calculation of the applied indicators was performed using the formulas below:

Using Student's t-test, we determined the degree of significance within a statistical series (p) and when comparing two series (P), respectively. Data were considered significant at a p value (P) from < 0.05 to $<$ or > 0.001 .

We also used a questionnaire we developed that assessed the following parameters:

The experimental study was conducted at the Department of Dentistry at Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin in 2026.

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**INTEGRATION OF EDUCATION AND PRACTICE, CREATION
OF A UNIFIED COMMUNICATION ENVIRONMENT, EARLY
CAREER GUIDANCE FOR SCHOOLCHILDREN AS FACTORS IN
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TRAINING FOR HEALTHCARE:
THE EXPERIENCE OF TOMK**

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Abstract: *The paper examines ways to improve the quality of training for the healthcare system. It highlights the problem of a shortage of mid-level medical personnel in medical organizations at all levels, especially in rural areas. The importance of early pre-professional training for schoolchildren is indicated. The results of the college's project activities in creating a unified educational environment across organizations of different levels and profiles within the framework of regional experimental sites are presented. An example is provided of the early professional orientation program implemented by Tambov Regional Medical College in general education organizations, titled "Schoolchild as a Student" (medical class in a general education organization).*

Keywords: *Secondary Vocational Education (SVE), Human Resources Potential, Regional Educational Medical Cluster (REMC), Career Guidance, Medical Class.*

According to official estimates, there is a global shortage of 7.2 million healthcare workers to provide medical services, and by 2035, the demand for nurses is projected to reach 12.9 million [1]. The shortage of personnel in medical organizations is a global problem that is relevant to Russia and, in particular, to the Tambov region. It manifests as a shortage of doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and other specialists, which negatively impacts the quality of medical care for the population. As of today, the shortage of mid-level medical personnel in the Tambov region stands at 116 individuals.

Mid-level medical personnel constitute the most critical human resources asset and form the largest professional group. This group includes healthcare workers who make a significant contribution to providing quality medical services and help improve the health indicators of individuals, families, and communities through preventive and curative measures [2, p. 38]. Thus, an adequate number of personnel within the secondary vocational education (SVE) system is crucial for strengthening the healthcare system and improving the quality of medical care for the population. Obtaining an SVE degree enables young people from various socioeconomic backgrounds to acquire in-demand specialties and improve their living conditions. The Government of the Russian Federation has approved a set of measures to support and develop SVE institutions and has included these institutions in the priority national project “Healthcare,” as well as the federal projects “Medical Personnel” and “Professionalism” [3]. Consequently, modernization, as a key factor, has been combined with innovative activity.

As noted by A. Miroshnichenko, Director of the Educational and Methodological Center for Continuing Medical Education (VUNMTs) of the Russian Ministry of Health, in his congratulatory message on the occasion of SVE Day: “Secondary vocational medical education is currently undergoing a profound transformation. Approaches to assessing the roles of medical personnel are changing, new technologies for diagnosing and treating diseases are emerging, the relationships between healthcare workers and patients are being reconsidered, and working conditions and professional development opportunities are evolving. All of this necessitates new approaches to the training of future medical personnel at all levels” [4].

Eliminating the shortage of personnel in healthcare is a complex task that requires the combined efforts of the state, professional educational organizations, employers, and the public.

A comprehensive approach to solving the problem is necessary, taking into account the close connection with the needs of the modern regional economy for professional personnel within the SVE and higher education (HE) systems, mobilizing the educational environment, enhancing the prestige of the profession, and providing early career guidance for schoolchildren.

At the All-Russian Conference “Mid-level Specialists in Medicine and Pharmacy: Training, Accreditation, and Employment” (September 2024), the Minister

of Health of the Russian Federation, M. A. Murashko, outlined the main vectors for the development of the mid-level medical personnel training system until 2030 and emphasized the role of Regional Educational Medical Clusters (REMCs) [5].

REMCs bring together educational institutions, medical facilities, and scientific organizations, which facilitates the creation of a unified environment for training future medical specialists. This approach helps schoolchildren understand how theoretical knowledge is applied in practice. REMCs can develop programs that are tailored to the current needs of the regional healthcare system. This allows students to acquire knowledge that aligns with modern requirements and innovations in medicine. Regional medical clusters can contribute to early career guidance, helping schoolchildren make informed choices regarding profiles and directions for further education in medical institutions.

The college's experience lies in proposing new pedagogical approaches and implementing educational innovations, integrating education and practice based on the adoption of a partnership strategy, and organizing interaction between administrative structures and institutions of different levels and profiles.

The underlying idea for creating the project is rooted in the specific needs of the territory for medical personnel in healthcare. A coordinated project has been implemented, aimed at achieving a strategy for developing the human resources potential of mid-level medical workers, consolidating the efforts of general education, secondary vocational education, and employers.

Within the framework of the Regional Experimental Site (RES), a new model of vocational education, "School – College – Enterprise," has been introduced. Mechanisms for social partnership have been developed. Network interaction agreements have been concluded with general education organizations in the city of Tambov and the Tambov region regarding the creation of specialized classes at Municipal Educational Institutions "Secondary School No. 36," "Secondary School No. 22," "Secondary School No. 28" in Tambov, "Tsninskaya Secondary School No. 2" in the village of Stroitel, Tambov District, Uvarovshchinskaya Secondary School in Kirsanov District, and a secondary school in the city of Michurinsk. Four healthcare institutions in the region have been granted the status of RES. Participation in joint projects based on the RES has made it possible to create a unified educational and communication environment, thereby establishing conditions for implementing the strategy for developing the human resources potential of mid-level medical workers in the Tambov region.

Based on the results of a competition for original projects and initiatives aimed at the socio-economic development of villages, small towns, and large cities, college instructor M. G. Kalugina was awarded a 2nd-degree diploma (at the All-Russian competition "My Country – My Russia") for her project titled "Implementation of a Strategy for Developing the Human Resources Potential of Mid-level Medical

Workers through the Introduction of Social Partnership Mechanisms and New Forms of Training and Professional Development for Specialists.”

The college utilized the experience gained from participating in the international project ROSI (Russian-Canadian Nursing Initiative). As a result of this participation, the college was included in a catalog of best practice examples for organizing international cooperation.

Since September 1, 2023, on the premises of Municipal Budgetary Educational Institution “Satinskaya Secondary School” in the Samput district of the region, Tambov Regional Medical College has been implementing a program aimed at early career guidance for schoolchildren by creating a unified youth communication environment. This program helps students understand the opportunities and prospects in the field of medicine and make an informed career choice: the medical class in a general education organization called “Schoolchild as a Student.”

Career guidance for schoolchildren is a crucial stage in their lives. In rural areas, where access to specialized institutions is limited, medical classes can serve as an excellent solution.

The geography of the “Schoolchild as a Student” project is constantly expanding. As of September 1, 2024, two more schools from the region’s rural districts – Zherdevskaya Secondary School and Pervomayskaya Secondary School – have become participants in the project.

Based on the interim results of the project, there have been publications by students in scientific journals, for example: “The formation of a specialized medical class is dictated by a specific social demand: the need for earlier professional orientation of schoolchildren to ensure continuity of learning between medical classes in schools and institutions of the secondary vocational education system; addressing the personnel shortage in primary healthcare; and enhancing the role and activity of professional educational organizations in training motivated specialists for regional healthcare” [6, pp. 301–305].

From all the above, it can be concluded that professional medical educational organizations are not only bearers of experience relevant to the entire education system of Russia but are also focused on implementing a strategy for developing human resources for the region’s innovative economy and improving the quality of training for the healthcare system.

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OBESITY AS A FACTOR IN STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL REMODELING OF THE HEART: PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS AND EFFECTIVE CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. Obesity is an independent pathogenetic factor leading to structural and functional remodeling of the cardiovascular system. The scale of the problem is confirmed by WHO data: while in 2016, 1.9 billion people were overweight (650 million of whom were obese), by 2022 these figures had risen to 2.5 billion and 890 million, respectively. The aim of this study was to evaluate diagnostic criteria for structural and functional remodeling of the heart in obese patients. *Materials and Methods.* Electrocardiography (ECG) and transthoracic echocardiography (EchoCG) were used to assess changes. *Results.* Structural and functional cardiac abnormalities, such as extension of all cardiac chambers, eccentric left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy, and decreased systolic function, are caused by a complex set of pathophysiological mechanisms: chronic volume overload, metabolic disturbances (lipotoxicity, insulin resistance), endocrine activity of adipose tissue, and activation of neurohumoral systems. The combination of obesity with metabolic syndrome components (hypertension, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes) greatly increases the risk of heart failure, arrhythmias, and sudden cardiac death. Early diagnosis of structural myocardial changes in obese patients requires a comprehensive approach, including ECG and echocardiography, which will enable timely initiation of preventive and therapeutic measures to improve the prognosis.

Keywords: *obesity, cardiac remodeling, metabolic disturbances, insulin resistance.*

Introduction

In modern cardiology, obesity is considered not simply a risk factor, but an independent pathogenetic factor initiating a complex of structural and functional changes in the cardiovascular system. The scale of the problem is underscored by data from the World Health Organization. In 2016, 1.9 billion people were overweight; more than 650 million were obese. In 2022, 2.5 billion were overweight, 890 million were obese, and this figure continues to grow. Consequently, there has been growing interest in studying the mechanisms by which obesity affects the heart, particularly the phenomenon of structural and functional myocardial remodeling [1–3].

Cardiac remodeling in obesity is a complex dynamic process involving changes in the geometry of cardiac chambers, changes in wall thickness, transformation of the extracellular matrix, and impaired contractile function. Unlike classical models of remodeling (for example, in arterial hypertension or coronary heart disease), obesity triggers a unique cascade of pathophysiological reactions that combine hemodynamic, metabolic, and neurohumoral mechanisms.

Chronic volume overload leads to cavity dilation and compensatory left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy. Excess adipose tissue is transformed into an active endocrine organ, secreting adipokines (leptin, adiponectin), proinflammatory cytokines (interleukin 6, tumor necrosis factor α), and free fatty acids.

Metabolic disturbances associated with obesity exacerbate the pathological process. Lipotoxicity, caused by excessive free fatty acid influx into cardiomyocytes, disrupts mitochondrial β -oxidation, provokes the accumulation of toxic metabolites, and triggers apoptotic mechanisms. Insulin resistance develops concurrently, indirectly disrupting the electrical stability of the heart and impairing diastolic function. Activation of the sympathetic nervous system and the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system in obesity causes vasoconstriction and sodium and water retention. Hyperleptinemia, characteristic of obesity, further enhances sympathetic activity and promotes the progression of cardiomyocyte hypertrophy [4–6].

It is worth noting that obesity is often associated with other components of metabolic syndrome – arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, and type 2 diabetes. Their synergistic effects greatly increase the risk of developing heart failure, arrhythmias, and sudden cardiac death. However, early diagnosis of structural myocardial changes in obese patients remains challenging: clinical symptoms may be subtle in the early stages, and instrumental markers of remodeling require a comprehensive approach to interpretation.

The aim of this study is to evaluate diagnostic criteria for structural and functional cardiac remodeling in obese patients.

Materials and Methods

To assess structural and functional cardiac remodeling in obese patients, electrocardiography and transthoracic echocardiography were performed.

Results

Analysis of resting ECG parameters revealed a high frequency of atrial and ventricular ectopic activity, ECG signs of myocardial hypertrophy, and focal ECG changes (Table 1).

Table 1 – Resting ECG Parameters

Indicator	Patients, %
ECG without pathology	10
Supraventricular extrasystole, tachycardia	72
Ventricular extrasystole, tachycardia	48
Left ventricular myocardial hypertrophy	62
Focal changes	38

Analysis of echocardiographic results revealed pathognomonic structural and functional changes in the heart.

Table 2 – Echocardiographic Parameters

Indicator	Parameter, M ± m	Reference value
LAD, cm	5,7±0,08	2,3–4,0
RAD, cm	5,1±0,3	2,3–4,0
IVST, cm	1,32±0,14	0,7–1,1
LVPWT, cm	1,27±0,11	0,7–1,1
LVEDD, cm	5,84±0,62	4,0–5,5
LVESD, cm	4,46±0,65	2,5–3,8
LVEDVi	88,8±14,1	35–75
LVESVi	35,7±8,4	12–30
LVM, g	291,5±75,4	Male <225, female <170
LVMI	127,4±26,0	male <120, female <110
RWT	0,61±0,12	-
LVEF, %	41,5±7,3	>50

LAD – anterior-posterior diameter of the left atrium, RAD – Anteroposterior dimension of the right atrium, LA – left atrium, RA – right atrium, LV – left ventricle, IVST – interventricular septal thickness, LVPWT – left ventricular posterior wall thickness, LVESD – end-systolic diameter, LVEDD – end-diastolic diameter, LVESVi – end-systolic volume, LVEDVi – end-diastolic volume, LVM – left ventricular mass, LVMI – left ventricular mass index, RWT – relative wall thickness, LVEF – ejection fraction.

A marked increase in left atrial size may indicate prolonged volume overload and elevated left atrial pressure, which is often associated with left ventricular diastolic dysfunction. Right atrial dilation indicates increased pressure in the right chambers of the heart, possibly leading to pulmonary hypertension or right ventricular dysfunction. Thickening of the interventricular septum and posterior wall of the left ventricle indicates myocardial hypertrophy caused by chronic overload. Increases in the end-systolic and end-diastolic diameters, end-systolic volume, and end-diastolic volume of the left ventricle indicate left ventricular dilation, confirming chronic overload and reduced myocardial contractility. Increased myocardial mass and left ventricular myocardial mass index confirm hypertrophy, even after accounting for body surface area.

Thus, severe structural and functional abnormalities of the heart have been established, including dilation of all cardiac chambers, eccentric hypertrophy of the left ventricle, and decreased systolic function.

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THE POSSIBILITY OF USING SUBSTANCES WITH ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES IN PATIENTS WITH COMORBID PATHOLOGY

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Abstract. Rational nutritional correction in patients with obesity and cardiovascular disease is a pressing issue in modern dietetics. The use of dietary components with antihypoxic, antioxidant, and cytoprotective properties is considered a potential means of improving tissue nutrition and correcting hypoxia. The role of hypoxia in exacerbating metabolic disorders is discussed: the accumulation of intermediate breakdown products, the development of metabolic acidosis, the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and activation of the sympathoadrenal system, which contribute to inflammation, lipid degeneration, and mitochondrial dysfunction. Antioxidants and antihypoxants can reduce organ oxygen demand, improve oxygen utilization, and reduce ROS formation, thereby regulating the redox balance. The effects of active compounds from algae (omega-3, astaxanthin, carotenoids, polyphenols) and bioactive peptides on the endothelium, lipid metabolism, and blood pressure are considered potential elements in the comprehensive prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. The need for an individualized approach is emphasized: assessment of metabolic characteristics, recovery periods, and the clinical course, with appropriate dietary adjustments.

The article suggests that the inclusion of nutrients with antioxidant and antihypoxant activity may improve metabolic status, influence body composition, and possibly prolong life by reducing clinical symptoms.

Keywords: *obesity, antioxidants, antihypoxants, algae, cardiovascular pathology.*

Introduction

Dietary modification in patients with obesity and cardiovascular disease is a pressing issue in modern dietetics. Studying the clinical characteristics of dietary components with targeted properties is crucial for this group of patients.

A possible solution to the problem of chronic tissue hypoxia is the development and clinical evaluation of new substances with antihypoxant and cytoprotective properties.

It is worth noting that hypoxia leads to an excess accumulation of intermediate breakdown products (proteolysis, lipolysis, and glycolysis). Metabolic acidosis develops, aggravating the disease.

During hypoxia, blockade of the respiratory chain in mitochondria leads to excessive free radical formation; activation of the sympathoadrenal system is accompanied by increased formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Highly reactive radicals (nitric oxide, superoxide, peroxynitrite) are inflammatory mediators, negatively affecting proteins and nucleic acids. Lipid peroxidation is activated. Oxidative stress, in turn, is associated with the development and progression of obesity, as it can lead to chronic inflammation and metabolic dysfunction [1].

ROS are involved in the regulation of mitochondrial activity; they alter the concentration of molecules involved in inflammation, which is associated with a large number and size of adipocytes, promote adipogenesis and lipogenesis, stimulate the differentiation of preadipocytes and play an important role in the regulation of energy balance in hypothalamic neurons that control appetite [2].

Materials and Methods

Antihypoxants reduce the oxygen demand of organs and tissues, improve oxygen utilization, and increase resistance to hypoxia. Antioxidants block the formation of reactive oxygen species (free radical processes) and lipid peroxidation in cell membranes. Free radicals are converted into a stable molecular form that does not participate in the autooxidation process.

Antioxidants, given their effects (directly binding free radicals or stimulating the tissue antioxidant system), are considered potential nutrients for optimizing dietary therapy. They influence free-radical oxidation processes in various diseases by interacting with various reactive oxidants, reactive oxygen species, and other free radicals, leading to their partial or complete inactivation. Thus, antioxidants directly affect the pathogenic mechanism, preventing the balance from shifting toward active ROS production over their utilization.

The body's physiological antioxidant system (AOS) maintains oxidative-antioxidant balance in all organs and systems. It effectively corrects energy

metabolism by normalizing the functions of the mitochondrial respiratory chain, which carries out oxidative phosphorylation, and other metabolic pathways that supply energy substrates [3].

Dysfunction or insufficient activity of the antioxidant system leads to disorders at the cellular, tissue, and organ levels. Tissue-level dysfunction is one of the links in the pathogenesis of a wide range of pathologies (atherosclerotic and diabetic angiopathy, coronary heart disease, cancer, neurodegenerative and autoimmune processes, cataractogenesis, etc.).

Results

Studies have been published demonstrating the positive effects on the cardiovascular system of microalgae (such as chlorella and spirulina) and macroalgae (brown, red, and green algae), which contain a complex of unique biologically active compounds. Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids effectively reduce atherogenic lipids in the blood, normalize blood pressure, improve vascular endothelial function, and prevent blood clots, reducing the risk of atherosclerosis.

Astaxanthin, carotenoids, and polyphenols neutralize oxidative stress, a key factor in vascular damage and the development of atherosclerotic plaques, and possess anti-inflammatory properties, reducing inflammatory markers. Bioactive peptides block angiotensin-converting enzyme, which reduces high blood pressure. Algae polysaccharides influence lipid metabolism, helping to reduce “bad” cholesterol, making algae a promising complementary or alternative treatment for the comprehensive prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases [4]. The latest ESC guidelines emphasize the importance of phytosterol supplementation for patients with dyslipidemia. Daily intake of up to 2 g of phytosterols effectively reduces total and LDL cholesterol levels by competing with cholesterol for absorption in the gastrointestinal tract [5].

The diet of patients with obesity and cardiovascular disease should be based on their physiological needs for nutrients and energy, taking into account the individual characteristics of the disease’s pathogenesis and clinical course, the characteristics of the recovery period, and the nature of metabolic changes. The optimal approach is based on an assessment of individual metabolic parameters, followed by dietary adjustments congruent with these parameters.

There is reason to believe that including nutrients with antioxidant, antihypoxic, and cytoprotective properties in the diet may have a positive effect on the metabolic status of patients in this category. A shift in oxidative processes may also serve as an independent nutritional factor in improving body composition, achieving a reduction in clinical symptoms, and potentially impacting life expectancy.

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**STUDY OF INDICATORS OF KIDNEY DYSFUNCTION
IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE
IN UZBEK POPULATION**

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SUMMARY. *In patients with chronic heart failure, as the disease progresses, pronounced renal dysfunctions are observed, characterized by an increase in creatinine, a decrease in GFR, which correlated with the progression of the disease and a decrease in exercise tolerance.*

Key words: *chronic heart failure, renal dysfunction, glomerular filtration rate.*

According to the Framingham Heart Failure Study, the incidence of chronic heart failure (CHF) doubles every decade. CHF dramatically impairs the quality of life of patients and quadruples the risk of mortality; the annual mortality rate can reach 15–50%. The risk of sudden death in patients with CHF is five times higher than in individuals without heart failure [1, 2]. Currently, the problem of cardio-renal syndrome (CRS) in patients with chronic heart failure is widely discussed [3, 4]. The mutually negative influence of kidney and cardiac dysfunction has been proven, manifested in the progression of renal dysfunction with increasing CHF and the deterioration of cardiac function with the progression of renal failure [5, 6]. A number of studies have shown that even the earliest subclinical impairment of renal function is an independent risk factor for cardiovascular complications (CVC) and death, as well as recurrent complications in patients with cardiovascular disease. It has been shown that in CHF, the creatinine level, similar to the

left ventricular ejection fraction (EF), is an independent predictor of an unfavorable prognosis. It has been established that in patients with CHF, the presence of renal dysfunction is a predictor of an unfavorable clinical prognosis, even more significant than the severity of HF and the ejection fraction (EF) of the LV [7,8]. The prevalence of renal impairment in CHF, according to various studies, ranges from 25% to 60%. Similar to the LV ejection fraction, in CHF a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate (SFR) and the creatinine level are considered as independent signs of an unfavorable prognosis. With SFR <60 ml/min/1.73 m², the risk of mortality increases by 2.1 times, with reduced systolic function of the LV, the risk of death in patients with renal failure (RF) increases by 3.8 times, and with unchanged systolic function – by 2.9 times. Numerous epidemiological, prospective, and retrospective clinical studies have established a close association between the severity of renal dysfunction, assessed by the magnitude of the reduction in GFR/ plasma creatinine concentration, and the risk of all-cause mortality, as well as the occurrence of various cardiovascular events [9, 10, 11].

Study objective. To study renal dysfunction indicators in patients with CHF Uzbek population/

Material and methods. A total of 300 patients with CHF aged 40 to 65 years (mean age 60.1 ± 5.74 years) were examined. The clinical characteristics of the patients are presented in Table 1. There were 159 men (53%) and 141 women (47%). Patients were divided into groups based on their functional class (FC) of CHF according to the New York Heart Association (NYHA) classification, based on the 6-minute walk test and the Patient Clinical Assessment Scale (PCAS). Seventy-seven patients had FC I CHF, 129 had FC II, and 94 had FC III.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of patients

Indicators	n
Total patients	300
Men	159 (53%)
Women	141 (47%)
Average age of patients	60,1 ± 5,74 лет
CHF FC I	77 (25,7%)
Average age of patients with CHF FC I	60,2 ± 7,56 лет
CHF FC II	129 (43%)
Average age of patients with CHF FC II	64,0 ± 4,20 лет
CHF FC III	94 (31,3%)
Average age of patients with CHF FC III	61,7 ± 6,97 лет
Hypertension	148 (49,3%)
PICS	88 (29,3%)

A total of 88 patients (29.3%) had a history of myocardial infarction, and 148 patients (49.3%) had hypertension. The control group consisted of 50 healthy volunteers. Patients with diabetes mellitus were not included in the study. Creatinine (Cr) levels were determined in all patients. Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was calculated using the CKD-EPI formula. Patients were divided into 2 groups depending on the GFR indicator: Group 1 consisted of 154 patients with $GFR > 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² and Group 2 consisted of 146 patients with $GFR \leq 60$ ml/min/1.73 m². Statistical processing of the study results was performed on an IBM PC/AT personal computer using the ECXEL 7.0 spreadsheet package. Parameters were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (M \pm SD). Correlation analysis using the Pearson linear correlation coefficient or Spearman rank correlation coefficient was used to examine relationships between quantitative variables. Differences were considered significant at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Study results. A clinical study revealed that exercise tolerance, assessed by the exercise tolerance test, significantly decreased with disease progression. Analysis of the study results revealed that creatinine levels in patients with functional class I CHF were 84.6 ± 3.96 μ mol/L, while in patients with functional class III CHF, this level was 25.9% higher than in patients with functional class I CHF, reaching 114.3 ± 4.95 μ mol/L ($p < 0.01$). The initial parameters of GFR were 77.0 ± 3.42 ml/min/1.73 m² in patients with FC II CHF – 70.1 ± 2.05 ml/min/1.73 m² and 65.2 ± 2.82 ml/min/1.73 m² in patients with FC III CHF, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Creatinine and GFR values in patients with CHF FC I–III (M \pm SD)

Indicators	CHF FC I XCH Φ K I	CHF FC II XCH Φ K II	CHF FC III XCH Φ K III
Creatinine (μ mol/L)	84,6 \pm 3,96	93,8 \pm 2,81	114,3 \pm 4,95
GFR (CKD-EPI) (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	77,0 \pm 3,42	70,1 \pm 2,05	61,2 \pm 4,82

Moreover, $GFR_{CKD-EPI} \leq 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² was detected in 48.7% of patients with CHF and averaged 54.6 ± 5.3 ml/min/1.73 m² (Table 3). The creatinine level in patients with $GFR > 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² was 82.8 ± 1.80 μ mol/l, while in patients with $GFR \leq 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² – 119.5 ± 3.54 μ mol/l ($p < 0.001$). A study of exercise tolerance indices based on the results of the TSH depending on the functional state of the kidneys revealed that in patients with $GFR > 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² this index was 333.9 ± 11.12 m and in patients with $GFR \leq 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² 2287.4 ± 14.68 m ($p < 0.05$). The PCAS index in patients with CHF also characterized a more severe clinical course of the disease in patients with $GFR \leq 60$ ml/min/1.73 m² – 7.9 ± 0.33 points, compared to the group of patients with $GFR > 60$ ml/min/1.73 m², in whom this index was 6.0 ± 0.23 points ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Characteristics of patients with CHF depending on the functional state of the kidneys (M ± SD)

Indicators	Patients with GFR >60 ml/min/1.73m ² (n = 154)	Patients with GFR ≤60 ml/min/1.73m ² (n = 146)
Age (years)	59,7 ± 0,72	61,6 ± 0,86
CHF FC		
I	55 (35,7%)	20 (13,7%)
II	65 (42,2%)	65 (44,5%)
III	34 (22.1%)	61 (41,8%)
Creatinine (µmol/L)	82,8 ± 1,80	119,5 ± 3,54 (p<0,01)
Glomerular filtration rate (ml/min/1.73 m ²)	79,6 ± 1,42	54,6 ± 5,3 (p<0,05)
The 6-minute walk test (m)	333,9±11,12	287,4±14,68 (p<0,05)
The Patient Clinical Assessment Scale (PCAS) (points)	6,0±0,23	7,9±0,33 (p<0,05)
LVEF (%)	52,8±0,74	47,5±0,98 (p<0,05)

The study results showed that patients with CHF experience renal impairment as the disease progresses, characterized by a decrease in GFR. GFR showed a moderate direct correlation with the 6-minute walk test parameter ($r = 0.49$) and a strong EF ($r = 0.69$), and a strong negative correlation with the PCAS parameter ($r = -0.71$).

Conclusion. Thus, patients with CHF experience significant renal impairment as the disease progresses, characterized by increased creatinine levels and a decrease in GFR, which correlated with disease progression and decreased exercise tolerance.

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USE OF BACTERIOPHAGES IN FOOD PRODUCTION

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Bacteriophages are widely distributed in nature because they can inhabit any environment where favorable conditions for bacterial life exist. Therefore, the presence of these microorganisms is characteristic both in the external environment and within the bodies of animals and humans. They are most frequently isolated from wastewater, soil, and human or animal excretions.

Due to their pathogenic effect on bacteria, they have found application in various areas, ranging from medicine to food production. Currently, there is an increasing resistance of bacterial microorganisms to antibiotics. Bacteriophages are considered a promising area as an alternative solution for preventive, therapeutic, and diagnostic measures. Thus, bacteriophage-based agents are most often applied in medical and veterinary practice for the treatment of bacterial diseases. Their use is also widespread in laboratory research for the identification of bacterial species. The significance of bacteriophage preparations at food processing enterprises is also recognized, as they serve as agents for treating raw materials and food products, offering several advantages over traditional processing methods.

Bacteriophages are, by their nature, viruses of bacteria. Thus, to continue their life cycle, they require a host cell, in this case, a bacterial cell. During subsequent infection, reproduction occurs inside the cell, followed by its destruction (lysis) and the release of new progeny.

The bactericidal action of bacteriophages was first mentioned by Ernest Hankin in 1896, when he described the bactericidal properties of river waters in India against cholera vibrios [1, p. 4]. Experiments were conducted at the time that indicated the presence of microorganisms passing through bacterial filters. A similar phenomenon was later observed by other scientists, such as the Russian microbiologist N. F. Gamaleia and the English bacteriologist F. Twort. It was

only in 1917 that the Canadian scientist F. d'Erell, while conducting experiments related to dysentery, concluded that he was dealing with parasitic bacteria, which he named bacteriophages. Later, it was hypothesized that bacteriophages develop inside the bacterium itself, producing numerous progeny that then exit by lysing the bacterial cell wall. However, despite numerous studies, for a long time only the properties and methods of isolation were known. The structure began to be studied only with the advent of the first electron microscopes, when German microbiologist G. Ruska was able to obtain the first photographs of bacteriophages using one of these microscopes.

As one of the most widespread organisms in nature, bacteriophages are classified according to a variety of characteristics, distinguishing separate families. The largest groups are those subdivided based on the type of nucleic acid present in the microorganism: DNA-containing and RNA-containing. The majority of bacteriophages contain DNA.

Depending on their structure, bacteriophages are subdivided into six morphological types [1, p.10].

- First type: filamentous or rod-shaped (families Lipothrixviridae and Inoviridae)
- Second type: head only, without tails (families Plasmaviridae, Corticoviridae, Microviridae)
- Third type: head with small tail-like appendages (families Tectiviridae, Cystoviridae, Leviviridae)
- Fourth type: head and short tail (families Podoviridae, Fuselloviridae)
- Fifth type: head with long non-contractile tail and sheath (family Siphoviridae)
- Type six: head with a long tail and a contractile sheath (family Myoviridae)

Морфологические типы бактериофагов					
1	2	3	4	5	6
Нитевидные фаги	Фаги без отростка	Фаги с аналогом отростка	Фаги с коротким отростком	Фаги с длинным отростком и несокращающимся чехлом	Фаги с длинным отростком и сокращающимся чехлом

Figure 1 – division of bacteriophages based on morphological characteristics

The phage of type six is typical in structure and is the most frequently encountered bacteriophage. Therefore, it will be the focus of further consideration.

Conventionally, a bacteriophage can be divided into two parts: the head and the tail. These, in turn, consist of several components, each serving a specific function. The phage head includes the capsid and nucleic acid. The nucleic acid is the hereditary material that is transferred to the infected cell, while the capsid functions as a protein shell that contains the bacteriophage's DNA or RNA and protects it from external influences. The tail comprises components such as a contractile sheath, core, basal plate with spikes, and tail fibers on its surface. The contractile sheath has a protein composition and the capability to contract, which is crucial during the integration of the phage's genetic material into the bacterial genome. By contracting, the sheath assists the bacteriophage in penetrating the inner rod through the bacterial envelope, enabling it to inject its nucleic acid inside. The baseplate with spikes and the attached tail fibers, upon adsorbing to the surface of the bacterial cell, facilitate stronger attachment of the bacteriophage.

Figure 2 – structure of the bacteriophage

Bacteriophages are also classified based on their infection pathway, dividing them into two groups: virulent and temperate phages.

The life cycle of a virulent bacteriophage is referred to as lytic because, upon entering the cell, phages begin to reproduce inside it and are then released, causing lysis (destruction) of the bacterium. This process occurs in several stages. First, adsorption of the bacteriophage occurs – by attaching to the bacterial envelope with spikes and filaments, the bacteriophage adheres to its surface. Then injection into the bacterial cell occurs. By cleaving the cell wall with specialized enzymes, the bacteriophage gains unrestricted access to the cell membrane. The contractile sheath

contracts, allowing the internal phage tail tube to penetrate the membrane, after which the genetic material is injected into the bacterium. Subsequently, the biosynthesis of the injected components proceeds – the phage nucleic acid disrupts the bacterium’s own protein and nucleic acid synthesis. Instead of its own genome, the bacterial cell begins synthesizing viral proteins. Subsequently, the assembly of bacteriophage components begins within the cell cytoplasm, which are then assembled into complete particles. Only after the formation of fully mature and viable phages do they produce an enzyme that dissolves the bacterial envelope from within, thereby lysing it. As soon as the bacterial envelope ruptures, the bacteriophages escape.

Temperate phages differ from virulent phages in their life cycle – upon bacterial infection, lysis does not occur. The nucleic acid, initially integrated into the cell’s cytoplasm, subsequently incorporates into its genome and is transmitted hereditarily to other bacteria. Thus, it becomes a prophage, and the infected bacteria constitute a lysogenic culture, as this mode of existence of these organisms is called lysogeny. It is from this term that the life cycle of temperate phages derives its name – the lysogenic cycle. It is noted that in this case, no offspring phages appear – only the bacterium itself replicates with an altered genotype. However, under certain external factors such as exposure to ultraviolet radiation, peroxide compounds, and mitomycin C [1, p.23], the prophage is excised from the bacterial genome, thereby stimulating further formation and assembly of phage particles followed by destruction of the bacterial cell.

Figure 3 – routes of bacterial cell infection

However, not every bacteriophage can infect and lyse any bacterium. Each phage is capable of affecting only a specific type of bacteria. This leads to the most important characteristic of all bacteriophages – their specificity. According to their lytic capability, phages are classified into several groups: typical, monovalent, and polyvalent. Typical bacteriophages are those capable of affecting several different strains within a single species. Monovalent phages are those that interact exclusively with bacteria of a single species. Multivalent bacteriophages can infect groups of bacteria belonging to related species.

Furthermore, bacteriophages infect only prokaryotic organisms and do not affect eukaryotic cells, which distinguishes them from antibiotics, some of which may induce side effects with adverse consequences.

Another distinctive feature of bacteriophages is their resistance; unlike viruses that infect humans and animals, they are less susceptible to chemical and physical factors, which contributes to their increased longevity in the external environment. Phages retain their activity under conditions of low temperatures and across a broad pH range, indicating minimal influence of these factors. However, many bacteriophages cannot remain active at temperatures above 65–70 C°, and they are inactivated by boiling, ultraviolet radiation, or acidic conditions.

Based on these properties, bacteriophages have found practical applications in numerous fields.

The most extensive field of application of bacteriophages is medicine. Developed methods of prevention and treatment of bacterial infections based on phages are widely used and have been in practice for many decades. The developed drugs and methods for detection and identification are applied both in agriculture and veterinary medicine, as well as in laboratories. However, one of the priority areas for their application is the food industry. Although not all sectors within it require the implementation of this approach. Thus, in dairy production facilities producing fermented milk products or cheeses, the presence of bacteriophages is unacceptable. Since contamination of such enterprises with phages threatens the lysis of essential strains of lactic acid bacteria that ensure correct fermentation, this, in turn, leads to disruption of critical technological processes and the inability to realize product batches, followed by subsequent financial losses. The introduction of bacteriophage-based preparations should be considered in those sectors and production stages where they will not adversely affect operational processes.

One such example is the stage of raw material processing prior to its transfer to workshops where it is directly processed into finished products. It is important to promptly detect pathogenic microorganisms against which conventional cleaning methods may be ineffective (high temperatures, water, mechanical cleaning, etc.). Equally crucial is the timely elimination of these microorganisms before their colonies expand and pose a risk of contaminating consumers through the final

products. However, this requires having the tools and methods for the rapid detection of such pathogens. Based on these considerations, a phage preparation was developed that is capable of detecting *Bacillus mesentericus* bacteria in raw materials and finished plant-based products within 25 hours [2]. This is considerably faster than detecting the same bacteria using the traditional system, which takes 107 hours. This makes the developed method significantly more efficient and less costly compared to the previously used isolation and differentiation methodology.

In addition to enterprises engaged in the processing of plant raw materials, phage preparations can also be applied in meat processing plants and other enterprises involved in carcass processing. Before allowing animal carcasses to proceed to subsequent stages of production, they must also be examined for the presence of pathogenic microorganisms. Most often, raw materials entering such production are subjected to treatment with antibiotics, elevated temperatures, and water. However, when treated with phage-based preparations, it will be possible not only to identify pathogenic microorganisms but also to achieve their complete elimination. Thus, before sending carcasses to butchering, they can be sprayed with bacteriophage-based solutions against *E. coli*. At poultry farms and fish processing plants, it is possible to implement carcass treatment systems by immersing them in phage preparations: against *Campylobacter* in poultry and *Raoultella ornithinolytica* in fish.

In addition to bacteria multiplying within the product posing a risk of food poisoning for consumers, they also affect the shelf life of the product itself. Due to the rapid growth and development of colonies of undesirable microorganisms, the product can become unfit for consumption and must be disposed of in record short timeframes. This also leads to losses for companies. Thus, a biopreservative agent was developed, consisting of a cocktail of bacteriophages that actively interact with a range of pathogenic bacteria responsible for fish spoilage [3]. Moreover, it was found that soaking the samples in a solution of the prepared agent was more effective than its aerosol application on the surface. The method was tested under conveyor processing conditions, where it yielded positive results in the form of an extension of the product shelf life beyond the normal range of this parameter. Work was also carried out to study the safety and quality of sausages using bacteriophages against bacteria causing salmonellosis [4]. Two control batches of minced meat intended for sausage production were compared in terms of contamination levels. For this purpose, a phage-based agent was introduced into one batch, while the other batch was maintained with its original composition. Subsequently, after several hours of storage, the quantitative bacterial content of *Salmonella* was assessed. The experiment showed that the samples containing the phage preparation had 100–200 times fewer pathogenic microorganisms per 1 g of product compared to the control samples. At the same time, the organoleptic properties of the product

were not compromised. Thus, the effectiveness of bacteriophage application was confirmed not only during processing of raw materials but also finished products.

It is not only raw materials and products that can be treated. The technological line itself is also subject to treatment, including all its components: conveyor belts, cutting tools and tables, hooks, containers, and other equipment. Any surfaces that may become contaminated through contact not only with raw materials but also with personnel, who may unknowingly carry certain microorganisms, are subject to treatment.

In addition to treatment at various production stages, bacteriophages have found application in another field. In the field of biologically active additives production, a study was conducted testing a preparation based on a mixture of various bacteriophages.

The study developed a preparation based on seven polyvalent bacteriophages, which targeted a range of pathogens: *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. enteritidis*, *S. typhimurium*, *S. infantis*, *L. monocytogenes* [5]. An extensive trial of this mixture was conducted on laboratory animals, and only after obtaining positive safety results was it tested on a focus group. The experiment involved a group of individuals undergoing rehabilitation due to chronic diseases of the digestive system. The aim of the experiment was not only to develop a safe preparation but also to demonstrate the effectiveness of its application, which would support its characterization as a biologically active food supplement. Participants were randomly assigned to two control groups: the first underwent a rehabilitation course solely according to the established standard program, while the second received the standard program supplemented with the manufactured preparation. Upon completion of the rehabilitation course and, consequently, the conclusion of the experiment, the results were summarized. All changes in both test groups were documented, and the obtained results were compared. After completing the prescribed course, it was found that the group receiving the bacteriophage-based supplement had a significantly reduced number of pathogenic bacteria and accompanying microorganisms compared to those who underwent the standard course. Moreover, the number of individuals who have fully recovered within the rehabilitation program is substantially higher in the group that received the drug.

Thus, based on existing examples, it can be concluded that bacteriophages and phage-based preparations are beginning to be actively implemented in the food production process. The focus is primarily on developing solutions that extend the shelf life of finished products and eliminate pathogenic microorganisms in raw materials supplied to enterprises, thereby preventing their proliferation in the produced goods. Based on the knowledge and examples of application in medicine, a biologically active supplement has been developed that exerts a positive effect on human health. The main reason why food production enterprises have

not yet been able to widely adopt phage preparations is the difficulty of bacteriophage extraction. It was noted [2] that during the bacteriophage isolation stage for the developed agent, isolation was not possible from the majority of the listed samples. The complexity of manufacturing preparations also lies in contamination by inclusions that easily pass through bacterial filters along with the phages themselves. This is a serious issue, as such inclusions may consist of plasmids from lysed bacteria, as well as remnants of exotoxins and endotoxins that pose a risk to human health. To prevent this, emphasis should be placed not only on developing new phage agents but also on advancing purification technologies for the preparations being manufactured.

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BILATERAL ASYMMETRY OF THE FOREARM REGION: A GEOMETRIC MORPHOMETRIC STUDY IN YOUNG ADULTS

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Abstract. Introduction. *The study of the asymmetry of the human upper extremities remains an urgent problem of modern anthropology and biomechanics, as it reflects the interaction of the genetic features of the structure and functional specialization of the dominant arm. The forearm area is a key link in the kinematic chain of the upper limb, sensitive to the specifics of motor activity. Classical osteometric studies have shown pronounced directional asymmetry of the bones of the upper extremities in various human populations, however, a detailed analysis of the asymmetry of the contour of the forearm using geometric morphometry has been limited.* **Aim.** *Comprehensive assessment of the areas of the right and left forearms in right-handed young adults using geometric morphometry methods, determination of patterns of morphological intra-individual variability of this area among the study participants.* **Materials and methods.** *The study involved 32 young adults (18–20 years old, 23 young women and 9 young men), all participants were right-handed. The forearm was photographed in a frontal projection. Along the contour of the forearm, 40 evenly spaced half-marks (semilandmarks) were placed, which were transformed into marks (landmarks). Data processing was carried out in MorphoJ 1.07a using principal component analysis (PCA) and Procrustes ANOVA methods with an assessment of the effects of individual differences, asymmetry and their interaction, separately for the size (Centroid Size) and shape of the contour.* **Results and discussion.** *Procrustes ANOVA revealed a statistically significant intra-individual asymmetry of the average contour size ($F = 5.60$; $p = 0.0243$), however, the analysis of directional asymmetry vectors showed small differences ($F = 1.12$; $p = 0.2259$), which suggests a fluctuating*

nature of variability in the aspect of the pure shape of the forearm. The absence of statistically significant intra-individual differences in the shape of the forearm area between the right and left sides ($p = 0.2259$), while there is a statistically significant difference in the conditional “average” size (centroid size) between them ($p = 0.0243$), is an important result indicating that morphological asymmetry in the study group is realized mainly through proportional modification of the size of anatomical structures, with minimal local deformations, which preserves the overall pattern of absolute shape for the right and left sides. However, this does not mean that there is no asymmetry in the shape of the forearm. On the contrary, it is present, but without a certain directional vector, representing non-systemic fluctuations (a significant percentage of the residual variance $Ind*Side \approx 15.7\%$).

Conclusion. Morphological asymmetry of the forearm area in right-handed young adults is realized mainly through a proportional increase in size without obvious directional local deformations of the shape. The fluctuating nature of the shape asymmetry indicates random variations in development.

Keywords: forearm, bilateral asymmetry, geometric morphometry, MorphoJ, principal component analysis, Procrustes ANOVA.

Introduction. The study of human upper limb asymmetry remains a central topic in modern anthropology, biomechanics, and sports science, as it combines morphological, functional, and adaptive aspects of the musculoskeletal system’s response to unilateral loads. Bilateral asymmetry of long bones and soft tissues is considered a consequence of the interaction of genetically determined structural features and functional specialization of the upper limbs, particularly the dominant hand. Several studies have shown that the greatest values of directional asymmetry occur in the bones and segments of the upper limbs, while the lower limbs retain a greater degree of relative symmetry [1].

Classical osteometric studies have demonstrated that in various human populations, the longitudinal dimensions and diaphyseal geometry of the upper limb bones are characterized by pronounced directional asymmetry, predominantly with a right-sided displacement. An analysis of the long bones of the postcranial skeleton of early medieval and later populations revealed that the longitudinal diameters of the upper limb bones exhibit the greatest degree of asymmetry compared to those of the lower limb bones, which is interpreted as a result of specific motor activity and the distribution of mechanical loads. These data are consistent with observations across various ethno-territorial groups, where the humerus and forearm bones (radius and ulna) are often the most asymmetrical skeletal elements [2].

Of particular interest is the analysis of the bilateral asymmetry of the forearm region as a key link in the “shoulder girdle – shoulder – forearm – hand” kinematic chain, enabling complex pronation-supination movements and precise manipulation.

Modern three-dimensional studies of the radius and ulna have shown that, despite the absence of statistically significant differences in a number of integral parameters (length, volume), regional differences in the shape, curvature, and torsion of the diaphysis between the right and left forearms reach values of approximately 0.5 mm. This is important for both clinical surgical planning and the biomechanical interpretation of asymmetry. It is also emphasized that the dominant use of one hand throughout life potentially leads to asymmetric changes in the morphology of the forearm bones, even with general similarity in their sizes [3].

In athletic populations of young men and women who perform predominantly unilateral work with their upper limbs, asymmetry of the forearm and the entire shoulder complex is particularly pronounced. A study of morphological asymmetry in armwrestling athletes revealed that, in the baseline state, most of them exhibit pronounced asymmetry in the girth dimensions of the shoulder and forearm muscles, reflecting an imbalance in the development of the right and left upper limbs. Thus, prior to the initiation of the corrective program, the difference in shoulder circumference between the right and left arms reached 3–3.57%, and forearms, up to 1.4%, with statistically significant dominance of one side for a number of indicators. After the introduction of a specially developed training system aimed at equalizing the load, the magnitude of shoulder and forearm circumference asymmetry significantly decreased, which is interpreted as successful correction of the previously pronounced morphological asymmetry [4].

Similar results were obtained in studies of athletes specializing in sports with a pronounced hand dominance (tennis, martial arts, and applied sports). A study examining interlimb and trunk asymmetries in female table tennis players demonstrated that this category of athletes exhibits significant differences in the circumference of the upper and lower limbs, including the forearms, between the right and left sides, as well as asymmetry in postural parameters, which is considered a potential risk factor for overuse and injury. The authors emphasize that morphological asymmetry of the upper limbs is closely linked to functional lateralization and the specific motor demands of the sport. A study of upper limb asymmetries in student tennis players using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry demonstrated that the dominant upper limb of tennis players has significantly higher muscle mass, bone mineral content, bone density, and forearm circumference compared to both the non-dominant arm and a control group of runners. Moreover, the greatest asymmetry was observed in the distal forearm, reflecting local adaptations to long-term exposure to impact and rotational loads during racket use [5].

Asymmetry of the upper limbs in general, and the forearms in particular, is important not only for living populations and sports, but also for reconstructing motor activity in paleoanthropological series. It has been shown that directional asymmetry of long bones can develop as a result of functional adaptation to chronic mechanical

stress associated with economic lifestyles and the gender division of labor. Analysis of bilateral asymmetry in the long bones of the limbs of the early medieval population of North Ossetia revealed a number of reliably asymmetrical features, both with a pronounced directionality and with fluctuating asymmetry without a clear lateral predominance. This is interpreted as the result of the combined influence of environmental stress factors and the specific nature of motor activity. At the same time, extreme cases of pronounced asymmetry in one upper limb with relatively symmetrical development of other skeletal segments have been described. These cases are associated with long-term loss of function due to neurological damage (e.g., brachial plexus damage) and lead to profound morphological changes in the bones and muscle attachments. Such observations emphasize the importance of considering not only “normal” directional and fluctuating asymmetry, but also pathological conditions when interpreting morphological variability of the forearm [6].

Traditional methods of morphometric analysis based on measuring linear dimensions and angular characteristics have significant limitations when studying complex spatial transformations of shape. For example, with respect to the immediate values of the longitudinal parameters of upper limb segments, the intra-individual difference between the corresponding right and left segments is “lost” both during statistical processing of the obtained data and can be caused by errors in manual measurements performed directly by the operator [7]. In this context, the application of geometric morphometric methods opens up new possibilities for the quantitative analysis of holistic morphological structure, independent of the scale and position of the object [8,9]. The Procrustean superposition of landmarks allows for statistically reliable assessment of shape differences, independent of the size and position of objects, separating directional asymmetries caused by functional loads from fluctuating asymmetries reflecting individual stochastic variations. Integrated software packages, such as the TPS and MorphoJ suite, provide comprehensive analysis of morphometric data and two- and three-dimensional visualization of spatial patterns of variability, allowing researchers to identify hidden structural patterns that may be initially inaccessible to visual analysis. Thus, a comprehensive study of the morphological asymmetry of the upper limb segments using modern geometric and morphometric methods is a pressing scientific challenge, the solution of which can make a significant contribution both to the fundamental understanding of the principles of bilateral asymmetry in the context of the functional lateralization of the body, and to the development of applied aspects of medicine, sports anthropology and medical rehabilitation.

Aim. The aim of the study is to evaluate the region of the right and left forearm in right-handed young adults using geometric morphometric methods, to determine patterns of morphological intra-individual variability of the forearm area among study participants.

Materials and Methods. The study, which involved 32 young adults (average age 18–20 years), sought to minimize age-related morphological changes associated with involution while simultaneously completing the main growth processes. The age range adopted at the 1965 symposium of the USSR Academy of Pedagogical Sciences (adolescence for males is 17 to 20 years old, and for females, 16 to 20 years old). The study received approval from the local ethics committee of the Volgograd State Medical University of the Russian Ministry of Health (No. 2024/236 dated October 9, 2024). All participants provided informed voluntary consent to participate in the study. The gender composition of the group included 23 females (75%) and 9 males (25%). To exclude the motor dominance factor based on morphological characteristics, the study included only right-handed subjects, which was confirmed by the results of a standardized questionnaire of functional manual asymmetry [10]. The exclusion criteria included a history of traumatic injuries to the upper extremities, chronic musculoskeletal diseases, and congenital developmental anomalies. The study protocol consisted of photographing the forearm in a frontal projection with the upper extremities in a natural position along the body (in a normal anatomical position) with the most possible natural muscle relaxation. Given the complex nature of the forearm morphology, including the anterior and posterior muscle groups, and the predominance of the transverse dimension over the anteroposterior, the selected frontal projection will capture the most significant contour of the anatomical region. For each participant, separate photographs of the right and left forearms were taken sequentially under identical lighting conditions, shooting distance (1.5 m from the camera lens, however, a small difference in shooting distance was not of fundamental importance, since the Procrustean alignment used later leveled out this factor) and body orientation. The resulting photographs were subjected to standardization, which included conversion to a single spatial resolution (960x1280 pixels), which was a necessary condition for subsequent morphometric analysis. Each photograph also had to be assigned a unique name, which would allow each participant to be placed in a certain order and give the photograph a unique characteristic, for example, “dAf003” (d – right, “dexter”; A – forearm, “antebrachium”; f – female, “femina”; 003 – serial number). Next, the photographs (that were placed in a separate folder (right forearms in one folder, left forearms in another)) were been given the coordinates location in the computer’s memory by using tpsUtil32 and the “Build tps file from images” command. The tps-file generated in tpsUtil32 were then opened using tpsDig264. On each image, a line was drawn along the outer contour of the forearm region, along which the program was then instructed to place 40 semilandmarks at equal distances from each other (Fig. 1). A sufficient number of semilandmarks (40) was selected empirically.

Fig. 1. Semilandmarks applied along the contour of the right forearm area using the tpsDig264 program.

Next, to ensure proper operation in MorphoJ 1.07a, the semi-landmarks were converted in tpsDig264 into landmarks with the same coordinates. The coordinates of all landmarks for each specimen were then transferred to MorphoJ 1.07a as a single tps-file for subsequent data classification (i.e., assigning each specimen the “right” or “left” characteristic and a participant number), checking the data for normal distribution and the presence of outliers (the “Find Outliers” command), Procrustes fit (the “Procrustes fit” command), and statistical analysis (creation of a covariance matrix, principal component analysis (PCA), and Procrustes ANOVA). Principal component analysis (PCA) allowed for a quantitative assessment of the contribution of asymmetry to overall morphological variability. Before conducting PCA, the program generated a covariance matrix based on the data on the coordinates of the landmarks loaded into the program in the form of a tps-file (with already performed Procrustes alignment and classification of the data). The covariance matrix calculation was configured to group the data by the individual membership of each observation (the

“pooled within-group covariances: Individual” program command). This means that the program first automatically calculated the covariance matrix separately for each of the 32 participants, and then used the resulting 32 matrices to calculate the overall covariance matrix. The software allows for all these calculations to be performed in a single step. The next step was a generalized analysis of variance (Procrustes ANOVA). The critical significance level (p) for statistical testing hypotheses was set to 0.05. Conducting Procrustes ANOVA allows us to obtain the following (program-calculated) indicators in several areas: effects (i.e., the factor, the source of variation (Individual – for each individual, Side – among the right and left sides across the entire sample, Ind*Side – the interaction of the two previous effects)). The analysis is conducted separately for two independent aspects of the “pure” shape of the object: centroid size and shape. «Centroid size» is the size of the centroid, a scalar number representing the square root of the sum of the squared deviations of the coordinates of all landmarks from their mean value (the centroid). A centroid, in turn, is a point in space whose coordinates are equal to the arithmetic mean of the coordinates of all landmarks (can be compared to the “center of gravity” of a set of points). That is, instead of 40 marks (where each has two coordinates in two-dimensional space), for one object we obtain one, which collectively reflects these 40 and allows us to visualize the objects of study as individual points (centroids) arranged on the plane of centroid space. Thus, centroid size is a stored conventional value of the scale of each forearm, independent of units of measurement. «Shape» is the shape, configuration of the object, that is, how the contour is structured (in relation to this study), regardless of size. For «centroid size»: SS (Sum of Square – the sum of the squares of the deviations of the centroid size from the corresponding mean values for the effects under consideration; reflects how much variation is explained by a particular factor), MS (Mean Square – the average squared deviation of the centroid size, per one degree of freedom for the effect under consideration, essentially this is SS divided by «df»), df (degrees of freedom, i.e., independent parameters in the calculation), F (F-statistics, i.e., an indicator showing how much the variation caused by the effect is greater than random variation (error)), p (p -value, i.e., this is the probability of obtaining such F if there is no effect of the factor). For «shape», the interpretation of the meaning of the indicators will be somewhat different: SS is the sum of the squares of the Procrustes distances (Procrustes distance) between the realization of the shape of each forearm and the corresponding model shape (the average shape for a specific person or the average shape for a given side), determined by each effect (Individual, Side, Ind*Side), MS is the average square of the Procrustes distances per degree of freedom for the effect under consideration (reflects how much, on average, for all coordinates and for all observations, the shape deviates from the model shape associated with a particular effect).

Results and its discussion. The first principal component of 32 (PC1 – Principal Component 1) explains 65.748% of the variance. The eigenvalue of PC1 was 0.00045792, significantly exceeding the values of the subsequent components. The second principal component (PC2), with an eigenvalue of 0.00007967, explained an additional 11.440% of the variance, and the third component (PC3), with an eigenvalue of 0.00003972, explained 5.703%. The cumulative share of variance explained by the first three principal components reaches 82.891% (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Distribution of variance in the aspect of principal component analysis (PCA).

The analysis itself does not provide a clear indication of the specific aspect expressed by each principal component. However, visualization of the vector changes in the first principal component (PC1) space for each landmark against the background of the transformation grid (Fig. 3) reveals that the greatest vector shifts are observed for landmarks related to the medial and lateral surfaces of the forearm.

The construction of confidence ellipses in the space of which the “average” shape of the right and left forearms will be found with 95% probability shows a significant overlap between them, which indicates that in the shape space the right and left forearms are similar to each other (Fig. 4).

The Procrustes ANOVA results (Table 1) are presented for two independent aspects of the object’s “pure” shape: «centroid size» and «shape». We will examine the data sequentially.

Fig. 3. Visualization of displacement of landmark vectors on a transformation grid in the space of the first principal component (PC1).

Fig. 4. Confidence ellipses for mean values (separate ellipses for the right and left sides of all observations, each ellipse includes an area in which the mean value of each of the “right-left” groups can be found with 95 % probability).

Table 1. “Procrustes ANOVA results”

Centroid size:					
Effect	SS	MS	df	F	p
Individual	495919,489144	15997,402876	31	19,38	<0,0001
Side	4626,655516	4626,655516	1	5,60	0,0243
Ind * Side	25591,083765	825,518831	31	-	-
Shape:					
Effect	SS	MS	df	F	p
Individual	0,11457987	0,0000486332	2356	5,33	<0,0001
Side	0,00077731	0,0000102278	76	1,12	0,2259
Ind * Side	0,02150959	0,0000091297	2356	-	-

In the “Individual” row (for centroid size), $F = 19.38$, $p < 0.0001$, meaning that the relative sizes of the forearms differ significantly between the study participants, which is quite logical given the interindividual differences. In the “Side” row (for centroid size), $F = 5.60$, $p = 0.0243$ ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant difference between the relative sizes (centroid size) of the right and left forearms in each individual. The “Ind*Side” row reflects the extent to which this right-left difference varies between individuals, meaning that this variation is not explained by either Individual or Side, representing random influences, or “noise.” Therefore, calculating the F-statistic and p for “Ind*Side” makes no mathematical sense. However, it is possible to interpret the contribution of Ind*Side through the percentage of variance: that is, the quotient of $SS_{Ind*Side}$ and the sum ($SS_{Individual} + SS_{Side} + SS_{Ind*Side}$) = $25591.083765 / (495919.489144 + 4626.655516 + 25591.083765) = 0.0486 \approx 4.9\%$. That is, this is a variation in forearms size that is specific to each person and to each side, which cannot be described as a simple sum of intra-individual differences and the “right-left” difference. Now let’s move on to the shape aspect. In the “Individual” row (for shape), the parameters $F=5.33$, $p<0.0001$ are interpreted as a reliable presence of interindividual difference in shape between the right and left forearms, which is also quite logical and expected. In the “Side” row, the parameters $F = 1.12$, $p = 0.2259$ indicate the absence of a significant difference between the right and left forearms in the sample as a whole in terms of shape (i.e., after artificially “removing” size), which is confirmed by the obtained data from the conducted PCA. The calculated proportion of variance “Ind*Side” is $\approx 15.7\%$.

The absence of statistically significant intra-individual differences in forearm shape between the right and left sides ($p = 0.2259$), despite the presence of a statistically significant difference in the conditional “mean” size (centroid size) between them ($p = 0.0243$), represents an important result, indicating that morphological

asymmetry in the study group is realized primarily through proportional modification of the size of anatomical structures, with minimal local deformations, preserving the overall pattern of absolute shape for both the right and left sides. However, this does not mean that forearm shape asymmetry is absent. On the contrary, it is present, but without any directional vector, representing non-systemic fluctuations (significant percentage of residual variance $\text{Ind*Side} \approx 15.7\%$).

However, several limitations of the study should be noted. The use of two-dimensional images in the frontal projection allows for the contour of the forearm to be captured, but does not depict the full three-dimensional configuration of the musculoskeletal structures. To obtain more complete information about the spatial organization of asymmetry, it is advisable to use three-dimensional morphometry methods based on 3D scanning, or computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging with 3D reconstruction, but these methods are more complex in their implementation.

Conclusions. The study results revealed a specific pattern of forearm asymmetry in right-handed adolescents: a systematic and statistically significant asymmetry in the conventional “mean” contour size ($p = 0.0243$) in the absence of significant shape asymmetry ($p = 0.2259$). These data suggest that morphological asymmetry is realized through proportional “scaling” of one side relative to the other, without directed local deformations or “reworking” of the overall shape pattern, consistent with the concept of geometrically similar (isometric) growth.

The primary source of morphological variation in forearm contour (65.748% of the variance) is concentrated in overall size. The fluctuating nature of shape asymmetry, manifested as small random differences varying in directions without a systematic pattern, indicates random variations in morphogenesis rather than directed adaptive effects. The obtained data may be useful in clinical practice when planning surgical interventions on the upper limb, where a detailed understanding of the variability of forearm morphology is required. Furthermore, the results have implications for biomechanical studies and the analysis of functional asymmetry of the upper limbs in various motor contexts. In paleoanthropology, the proposed methodology for separating the size and shape components of asymmetry can be applied to the analysis of morphological variability of bone structures in historical populations.

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USE OF AQUATIC LACTOBACILLI IN FOOD BIOTECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *This paper presents an analysis of scientific studies dedicated to the investigation of the biological properties of bacteria of the genus Lactobacillus and the potential for their practical application. Particular emphasis is placed on the prospects of utilizing lactobacilli and their metabolites in the development of probiotic formulations, functional foods, and biological agents for the prevention of microbiota disturbances. Their metabolic activity and the role of adhesive structures in the interaction of bacteria with host organism cells are analyzed. The potential of employing lactobacilli in the creation of probiotic formulations and biological agents is demonstrated.*

Keywords: *Lactobacilli, Lactobacillus, probiotics, lactobacilli metabolites, antagonistic activity, microbiota, bacterial adhesion, probiotic formulations, biotechnology.*

In recent times, researchers in the fields of microbiology, biotechnology, and medicine have shown considerable interest in the study of bacteria of the genus Lactobacillus. Lactobacilli are a key component of the microbiota and play a significant role in maintaining the microbiological balance of the organism. Lactobacilli are gram-positive anaerobic bacteria that produce lactic acid and are consequently classified as lactic acid bacteria. They are widely applied in the food, pharmaceutical, and biotechnological industries. These microorganisms are found in aquatic environments, in vegetables and other food products, in the intestines of humans and animals, and, naturally, in dairy products. Thanks to their ability to synthesize organic acids and other biologically active compounds,

lactobacilli demonstrate characteristic antagonistic activity against pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora.

Lactobacilli of aquatic origin attract particular attention. They constitute a diverse group of lactic acid microorganisms inhabiting marine and freshwater environments, surfaces of aquatic plants, bottom sediments, the intestines of fish, and other organisms. The primary distinction is their higher adaptability, as they develop under more unstable conditions. For instance, they display high tolerance to salinity, since seawater contains a higher salt concentration compared to food matrices or intestinal environments. Furthermore, nutrients in aquatic environments are less stable than in other media.

Current research is aimed at investigating the biological properties of lactobacilli, their metabolic activity, adhesive characteristics, and their application in practical research. The primary directions in the utilization of lactobacilli include the development of probiotic formulations, biologically active supplements, and functional food products. These microorganisms can be applied in various fields of modern biotechnology. The broad spectrum of biological activity enables us to explore and develop various new technologies and methods for producing pharmaceuticals and food products, thereby posing a new pertinent challenge for contemporary science.

In his abstract, V. Yu. Krumlikov The study and development of technology for producing a symbiotic starter culture based on lactobacilli isolated from traditional fermented dairy products is addressed in the development of symbiotic starter culture technology [1]. The challenges associated with the production and consumption of dairy products are increasingly influenced by global trends in the food market. Among health food products, fermented dairy products such as Ayran, Kumis, Kurunga, and Chegen hold a distinguished place. These products serve as sources of diverse strains of lactic acid bacteria. The author notes that the microflora of these products includes various species of *Lactobacillus*, *Lactococcus*, and *Streptococcus*, which exhibit antagonistic activity against pathogenic microorganisms. The obtained symbiotic bacterial consortia are capable of synthesizing proteinaceous metabolites, including bacteriocins, which exhibit antimicrobial activity. Based on the conducted studies, a technology has been developed for obtaining a symbiotic starter culture for the production of functional fermented dairy beverages.

These beverages are characterized by high digestibility, exert beneficial effects on the gastrointestinal tract, and possess bactericidal and tonic properties. However, industrial production is complicated by the insufficiently studied starter microflora of these products.

Therefore, it is important to develop scientifically grounded approaches for creating combined starter cultures with high biological activity. To achieve this, it is necessary to study the physiological-biochemical and industrially valuable properties

of lactic acid bacteria isolated from national fermented dairy products. This will enable improvement in quality and expansion of the assortment of dairy products.

A comprehensive set of microbiological, biochemical, and technological studies was conducted, aimed at creating an effective symbiotic starter culture. Main studies conducted:

1) Identification of microorganisms. Species identification of bacteria was performed to determine the morphological, physiological, and biochemical characteristics of the isolated strains.

2) Microbiological analysis of fermented milk products. The natural microflora composition of traditional products (Ayran, Kumis, Kurunga, Chegen) was determined, and promising strains were isolated.

3) Investigation of antagonistic activity. Assessment of the ability of isolated bacteria to inhibit the growth of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms. Evaluation of the probiotic and protective potential of cultures.

4) Assessment of technological properties. Analysis of acid-producing activity, fermentation rate, and culture stability. Selection of strains suitable for the production of starter cultures.

5) Formation of symbiotic consortia. Combination of multiple lactic acid bacteria strains. Creation of an effective symbiotic starter culture.

6) Development of technology for the production of starter cultures. Optimization of cultivation conditions and production of bacterial compositions. Development of technology for the production of functional fermented milk products.

The conducted studies allowed for the isolation of promising strains of lactic acid bacteria from traditional fermented milk products and the investigation of their biological and technological properties.

Thus, it can be concluded that, based on the obtained data, a symbiotic starter culture based on lactobacilli, exhibiting antimicrobial activity and suitable for the production of functional fermented milk products, was developed. I consider the use of this starter culture to be a promising and functional approach. The application of such starter cultures not only improves the technological properties of the product but also increases its biological value. Within symbiotic cultures, lactobacilli can synthesize bacteriocins, biologically active substances, and organic acids. Consequently, they inhibit the development of pathogenic microflora, and fermented milk products acquire probiotic and antimicrobial properties, which positively influence the human organism's condition and contribute to the maintenance of the microbiota.

In the study by Chistokhina L. P. The work 'Immunobiological characterization of the preparation Microstim based on metabolites of lactobacteria' addresses the pressing issue of developing a new preparation for normalizing the human microecological and immune status [2]. To achieve the established goal, Larisa Pavlovna encountered several tasks:

1) To develop a method for isolating low-molecular-weight metabolites of lactobacteria and to create the preparation Microstim based on them.

2) Assess the safety of the drug Microstim: evaluate its acute and chronic toxicity as well as allergenicity.

3) Examine the bacteriotropic activity of Microstim – specifically its probiotic and antibacterial properties.

4) Evaluate the immunomodulatory effect of the drug in both in vivo and in vitro experiments.

Contemporary human living conditions involve exposure to adverse factors; therefore, it is necessary to mitigate their effects. It is crucial to develop pharmaceuticals aimed at maintaining and restoring microbiocenoses – in particular, next-generation probiotics based on biologically active metabolites of bacteria from the normal human microflora. Currently, on the Russian market, only the preparation ‘Hilak Forte’ is utilized among similar products. Therefore, the development of a new product based on the metabolic activity of lactobacilli, including assessment of its bacteriostatic and immunotropic properties, is pertinent. Indeed, dysbiosis and intestinal infections impair immune status; consequently, the inclusion of immunocorrective agents in therapy is recommended.

In the course of the study, investigations were carried out: the immunobiological properties of the product were examined; The influence of lactobacilli metabolites on the immune system has been studied; The antimicrobial activity and safety of the preparation have been investigated [2].

The author investigates the effect of biologically active substances produced by lactobacilli on the host immune system. It has been established that lactobacilli metabolites exhibit pronounced antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activity, contribute to the stimulation of the host’s defense mechanisms, and enhance resistance to pathogenic microorganisms.

Based on the analysis of the abstract and the experiments conducted, it can be concluded that Lactobacilli metabolites may be utilized for the creation of biological products possessing immunomodulatory and protective properties. The use of these metabolites is considered a promising foundation for the development of biological products. Their application facilitates the activation of the body’s defense mechanisms, the maintenance of the physiological balance of the microbiota, and enhances resistance to pathogenic microorganisms. Consequently, the use of biological preparations based on lactobacilli metabolites can be regarded as an effective strategy for enhancing immune defense and preventing infectious diseases.

In the abstract by I. V. Anjukhina, ‘Materials for the characterization of lectin-binding adhesin in the surface structures of lactobacilli’ discusses the relevance of the issue concerning the development of probiotic preparation production [3]. At present, dysbiotic conditions are widespread across all age groups, which

underscores the necessity for active development of drugs and products with probiotic properties. Dysbiosis is widespread across all age groups, necessitating the development of probiotic preparations. Normal microflora provides colonization resistance and supports metabolism.

Lactobacilli are a natural component of the biological niches of humans. Their beneficial effects on the body are mediated by two mechanisms: the formation of a protective barrier, whereby lactobacilli adhere to intestinal epithelial cells and inhibit the penetration of pathogenic microflora. Reproduction in the terminal niche: during the growth of probiotic cultures, bacteriocins, metalloproteinases, and adhesins accumulate, inhibiting pathogens. An optimal probiotic can be developed based on a combination of strains featuring shedding adhesins and lectin-like structures associated with the bacterial cell wall. Microencapsulation of adhesins will allow the production of a preparation that protects target cells from pathogenic flora. Prior to conducting the study, the objectives were established as follows: to test *Lactobacillus* strains for the presence of loosely bound adhesins capable of being released into the cultivation medium, to isolate these adhesins, and to evaluate the feasibility of their practical application. The subject of the study comprises the surface structures of bacteria of the genus *Lactobacillus* containing adhesive components.

During the study, the surface structures of lactobacilli and their biochemical properties were investigated. The capacity of cell surface components to bind lectins was investigated. An analysis was conducted on the adhesive properties of the bacteria and their capacity to interact with epithelial cells. The role of surface protein structures in the attachment processes of microorganisms to host organism cells was also examined.

The study established that specific adhesive molecules capable of binding lectins are present in the surface structures of lactobacilli. These components are involved in the process of bacterial adhesion to epithelial cells and ensure their attachment to the mucous membranes. The author notes that these structures play an essential role in establishing stable interactions between microorganisms and host cells.

Thus, based on the analysis of the conducted studies and the materials presented in the work, it can be concluded that lectin-binding adhesins are important components of the lactobacilli cell surface and play a key role in the processes of adhesion and colonization of mucous membranes, facilitating the interaction of bacteria with host cells. Due to these properties, they facilitate the stable colonization of mucous membranes and the formation of a stable microbiota. These properties make lactobacilli promising candidates for the development of functional biopreparations and probiotic agents capable of maintaining the physiological balance of the microflora and exerting a positive influence on the organism's condition.

In her abstract, Irina Valentinovna Fadeeva, titled 'Development of a Complex Probiotic Preparation Based on Lactobacilli,' isolated and characterized strains of

lactobacilli possessing probiotic properties [4]. The relevance of the issue is due to contemporary factors such as unbalanced nutrition, vitamin and mineral deficiencies, and environmental pollution. These factors cause disturbances in the natural human microbial communities, making research on the development of preparations to restore the microecological balance highly important. Domestic practice includes many years of applying biological preparations based on lactobacilli. A promising direction is the development of complex probiotics based on compatible strains from different species. The study involves the following strains:

- 1) *Lactobacillus plantarum* 8P-A3;
- 2) *L. fermentum* 90T-C4;
- 3) *L. acidophilus* K3Sh24;
- 4) *L. acidophilus* YOash;
- 5) *L. acidophilus* NKi.

Thus, the development and production of pharmacopoeial probiotic formulations based on viable lactobacilli is underway. This approach will allow for an expanded spectrum of biological activity of the preparations.

The aim of the study is to investigate and implement production strains of lactobacilli for the construction of a complex probiotic formulation. The author also sets the following objectives:

- 1) To study the biological and technological properties of industrial strains of lactobacilli.
- 2) To design a bacterial composition for the complex formulation.
- 3) To develop a method for producing the preparation and techniques for monitoring its activity.
- 4) To investigate the *in vitro* biological activity of the preparation in comparison with analogous products.
- 5) To study methods for stabilizing bacterial cultures for various pharmaceutical forms.

Research conducted during the study led to subsequent findings. Morphological, physiological, and biochemical characteristics of microorganisms were investigated, as well as their ability to suppress the growth of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microflora. An evaluation of the antagonistic activity of lactobacilli, their resistance to various environmental conditions, and their capacity to maintain viability within the probiotic formulation was carried out. Based on the obtained data, a comprehensive probiotic formulation was developed.

Consequently, Irina Valentinovna established that certain strains of lactobacilli exhibit antagonistic activity against pathogenic microorganisms and are capable of stabilizing the microbiota. The selected cultures are characterized by high biological activity and can be effectively utilized as part of probiotic formulations.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of lactobacilli in probiotic preparations represents a promising direction in modern microbiology and biotechnology.

Lactobacilli exhibit pronounced antagonistic properties against pathogenic microorganisms and are capable of maintaining microbiota stability. Consequently, the development of complex probiotic formulations based on these microorganisms may facilitate the prevention of disruptions in microbiological balance and enhance the body's protective functions.

In the study by Sorokina Yu.V. entitled "Development of Technology and Standardization of Medicinal Forms of a Preparation Based on Metabolites of Lactobacilli," the objective was to develop technology and evaluate the quality of soft pharmaceutical forms of a probiotic preparation based on metabolites of the Lactobacillus strain producer L.plantarum 8P-A3.

The development of probiotics is a highly demanded and promising field [5]. They normalize the symbiotic relationships between the human body and its microbiocenosis, replenish the deficit of metabolites, and create favorable conditions for the growth of the native microflora, while causing virtually no side effects. In the Russian Federation, experimental metabolite probiotics are being developed, among which 'Microstip' exhibits probiotic, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory effects. It demonstrates probiotic, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory activities and is recommended for the prevention and treatment of intestinal infections and dysbiosis. Nonetheless, the development of a broad spectrum of dosage forms remains a current task.

This study examined biologically active metabolites produced by lactobacilli: their physicochemical and biological properties were analyzed, and their effects on microorganisms were assessed. Furthermore, a technology for producing a preparation based on these Lactobacilli metabolites has been developed, and various pharmaceutical formulations have been created. The final stage involved standardizing the preparation – key indicators of its quality, stability, and safety were defined.

The study established that Lactobacilli metabolites exhibit pronounced biological activity. They also demonstrate the ability to suppress the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. The developed technology enables the production of stable pharmaceutical preparations containing active components of metabolic origin.

Based on the analysis of the presented data, it can be concluded that Lactobacilli metabolites possess significant biological potential and can serve as an effective basis for the development of medicinal products. These biologically active substances enable the creation of agents that not only suppress the growth of pathogenic microflora but also contribute to maintaining microbial balance in the body.

I believe that the development of technologies for the production and standardization of pharmaceutical forms based on Lactobacilli metabolites is an extremely promising direction for modern biotechnology and pharmacology. Its advancement can:

1) to expand the range of tools for correcting dysbiosis and preventing infectious diseases;

2) to propose safer alternatives to certain antibacterial agents through a mild regulatory effect on the microbiota;

3) to open new opportunities for the treatment of conditions associated with microbiota imbalance, including in gastroenterology, gynecology, and immunology.

Thus, the targeted study and practical application of lactobacilli metabolites can make a substantial contribution to the advancement of personalized and preventive medicine.

The analysis of the presented scientific studies demonstrates that Lactobacilli possess a wide spectrum of properties that protect the host organism from pathogenic microorganisms. The primary focus in the authors' works is the investigation of physiological, biochemical, and adhesive characteristics. Particular emphasis is also placed on the development of technologies and their practical applications.

Consequently, it is evident that Lactobacilli are capable of synthesizing diverse metabolites exhibiting immunomodulatory and antimicrobial properties. They contribute to the formation of a stable microbiota, as lactobacilli exhibit a pronounced ability for adhesion and colonization of mucosal surfaces.

The application of lactobacilli and their metabolic products represents a promising approach for the development of probiotic formulations, functional foods, and biological means for the prevention of microbiota disturbances. Further investigations in this field may facilitate the development of novel effective biotechnological solutions.

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P-DTR NEUROREFLEX THERAPY METHOD: THEORETICAL BASIS AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION

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Abstract. *This article presents for the first time a new therapeutic method – neuroreflex correction of body dysfunctions, which can be used in the complex therapy and rehabilitation of various pathologies. The method P-DTR is effective, safe, non-invasive, requires no medications or equipment, and takes about 30 minutes of a doctor’s appointment. A randomized clinical trial has been initiated to scientifically substantiate its application.*

Keywords. *Neuroreflex therapy. P-DTR*

Introduction

Medical progress is associated with the emergence of new, more effective methods of diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation. Alongside significant advances in pharmacotherapy and surgery, increasing attention is being drawn to prevention and non-drug therapies.

This work presents the P-DTR (Proprioceptive Deep Tendon Reflex) method, developed by orthopedic surgeon Jose Palomar (Mexico) and protected by Patent No. 2722402 of the Russian Federation (published May 29, 2020). This method allows for the elimination of functional disorders in the body, as well as significant improvement in the condition and quality of life of patients with morphological disorders [1].

The method P-DTR is of great interest for practice because it possesses characteristics not found in any other method. It is safe, effective, painless, non-invasive, drug-free, takes 15 to 30 minutes of a doctor’s appointment, is strictly individualized, and requires no specialized equipment. The P-DTR method is a neuroreflex approach based on the correction of proprioceptive distortions and sensorimotor integration to restore optimal central nervous system function and eliminate

dysfunctions in the body. The P-DTR therapy method is a modern manual method of neurofunctional correction that works with dysfunctional receptors and afferent pathways to restore the normal regulatory function of the central nervous system (CNS) and eliminate symptoms.

The P-DTR method was created based on sciences such as neurology, topical neurology, neurophysiology, all neurosciences, traumatology and orthopedics, body biomechanics, anatomy, applied kinesiology, and others.

Historical and Scientific Preconditions for the Creation of the P-DTR Method: Key Principles and Mechanisms of Action

In 1896, the English neurophysiologist Charles Scott Sherrington [2] discovered the fundamental mechanism of movement coordination known as reciprocal innervation of muscles. Sherrington's discovery laid the foundation for understanding neural control of movement and remains key in modern neurophysiology.

In 1946, M. R. Mogendovich discovered that electrical stimulation of internal organs in dogs causes changes in the tone of specific skeletal agonist muscles, recorded by EMG [3]. This phenomenon formed the basis of visceromotor reflexes, explaining the connection between internal organ dysfunction and musculoskeletal disorders.

Dr. Palomar discovered and theoretically substantiated the relationship between sensory perception and motor responses. He conducted a vast number of tests aimed at discovering which receptor stimuli could elicit a CNS response. Thus, he developed a system of receptor stimuli and counter-stimuli and proposed it for practical application.

The P-DTR method relies on manual techniques and neurophysiological principles, including the modulation of afferent sensory input, central integration of signals, and their influence on the efferent response of the nervous system.

In a healthy body, the brain, in response to correct input from receptors, regulates the work of all systems, muscles, and organs accurately and precisely. Body manipulations are akin to working with a computer. In a computer with functional software, distorted input signals, when processed normally by the processor, lead to incorrect output data. The same happens with the human body: if the information sent by the receptors is incorrect due to impaired receptor function or their signal, the brain's response will be distorted. This will lead to all kinds of dysfunctions, such as pain, limited range of motion, impaired function of internal organs, and any other disorders or symptoms related to improper functioning.

P-DTR interacts with various types of nociceptors and pathways involved in pain signal transmission, reducing the hyperactivity of nociceptive systems. The method affects various levels of the CNS.

Optimizing the processing of sensory signals leads to more efficient functioning of the nervous system, improving both motor functions and general regulatory processes – from the molecular level and autonomic control to the cognitive sphere.

P-DTR is a method positioned by its developer and practicing specialists as an approach to correcting neurological dysfunctions. Its operating principle is based on the idea of correcting proprioceptive afferentation to optimize CNS function. Definitive conclusions about its effectiveness can only be drawn after conducting large-scale randomized controlled trials, which have only recently begun at the P-DTR School. There are no independent studies or meta-analyses on the use of the method, and there are no publications of its use in the available literature. The method should be considered an experimental technique of alternative medicine.

Proprioception and Sensorimotor Integration.

The nervous system is unique in the immense complexity of the thinking and regulatory processes it carries out. Every minute, it receives and integrates millions of bits of information from different sensory organs, forming adequate responses of the body [4]. The basic functional unit of the central nervous system (CNS) is the neuron. The CNS contains over 100 billion neurons. The coordinated interaction of neurons ensures precise regulation of physiological processes, allowing the body to adapt to changing conditions and achieve optimal functional outcomes.

The P-DTR method relies on the work of a vast number of receptors of various modalities (muscle spindles, Golgi tendon organs, Pacinian corpuscles, Ruffini endings, joint receptors, etc.), which transmit information about body position and the state of internal organs to the CNS.

The body receives information about the external environment primarily through the sense organs equipped with receptors: ears (hearing), eyes (vision), nose (smell), tongue (taste), skin and mucous membranes (tactile and pain sensations). Receptors transform the energy of a stimulus into nerve impulses, which are transmitted from the receptors along nerve fibers to different levels of the nervous system. Receptors provide the brain with the information necessary for the optimal, pain-free functioning of the body. Distortion of information in the receptor–conducting tract–brain chain leads to impaired biomechanics and imbalance in the work of muscles and internal organs.

The P-DTR method has the ability to work with receptors, conducting tracts, and brain nuclei directly through stimuli of these structures, as well as with emotions, meridians, and sympathetic and parasympathetic responses of the nervous system. Consequently, the method allows for the correction of functional impairments of virtually all brain structures.

Reflexes: Classification and Mechanisms of Functioning.

It is known that reflexes are unconditional, conditional, and defensive; the latter are the subject of the neuroreflex therapy method's work. If a defensive reflex arises, its trace in the CNS remains for an indefinite long time.

The body compensates for the influence of the defensive reflex at the expense of the resources of other organs and systems. [13]. The nervous system tries to

neutralize the influence of a pathological focus by creating compensatory mechanisms. If one compensation is insufficient, it creates the next cascade of compensations – a fractal – so that the body can continue to perform its functions.

The P-DTR therapy is a type of alternative medicine within which P-DTR specialists identify primary and compensatory dysfunctions. The approach is based on the hypothesis that such dysfunctions, even long-standing ones, can be corrected by acting on dysfunctional receptors to restore the optimal control functions of the central nervous system [5].

Diagnosis and Correction of Dysfunctions Using P-DTR Method.

Clinical and manual methods, instrumental research methods, neurophysiological methods, functional diagnostics, assessment of pain syndrome and functional limitations are used.

Dysfunctional Receptors.

A dysfunctional receptor, unlike normally functioning receptors, has too high or too low bioelectrical activity, is energy-inefficient, and causes a systematic load on the CNS, constantly needing compensation for its dysfunction. The central nervous system compensates for the demand at the expense of other functional systems, leading to their overload and destabilization. This, in turn, causes disturbances in body biomechanics, limited mobility, pain syndrome, dysfunctions of internal organs, chronic fatigue, etc. [5].

Diagnosis of Dysfunctions.

Any dysfunctional signal affects the myotatic reflex of muscles, and consequently changes the muscle response during manual muscle testing. An incorrect signal generated by any type of receptor can cause hypotonia or hypertonia of a single muscle, as well as global hypo- or hypertonicity. By determining the myotatic reflex of muscles, we obtain feedback from the CNS. In their work, the specialist uses various algorithms and tools of the neuroreflex therapy method.

P-DTR Tools:

1. Tools that reduce the signal from the dysfunction: anti-stimulus, opposite stimulus, the “Golden Rule,” etc.

2. Tools that enhance the signal from the dysfunction: stimulus, double stimulus, universal therapeutic localization, double therapeutic localization (kinesiology terms), etc.

P-DTR Algorithms:

1. Algorithm of working through an associated muscle
2. Algorithm of working through an indicator muscle
3. Algorithm of working through patient complaints [52].

Algorithm and Protocols for Correction Using P-DTR Therapy Method.

The algorithm for correcting dysfunctions using the P-DTR method is very complex and consists of a huge number of elements; its analogy is a neural network].

These elements include checking postural reflexes, myotatic reflexes in standing, sitting, lying positions, modalities and stimuli, of which dozens are used, etc. The study of these elements allows for the diagnosis of dysfunctional receptors needing correction. First, it is necessary to find the zone of primary damage and the modality of the dysfunctional receptor, then determine the location and modality of the compensatory receptor.

The specialist always has a personalized approach to each patient because each patient has a unique set of dysfunctions. There are several starting points for building the treatment algorithm. When the choice is settled on the problem the specialist begins work with, a sequence of algorithm stages is built. At any moment, this personalized algorithm can change the planned sequence due to the dynamics of the patient's symptoms. There is always the possibility of using several actions at each stage. Thus, the algorithm for diagnosing and correcting dysfunctions using the P-DTR method begins with choosing an entry point and then develops according to the specifics of the patient's pathology. Since the specialist knows all the elements that make up the general algorithm, for a specific patient they select the shortest, personalized, and most effective algorithm for diagnosis and correction.

Protocols for Correcting Dysfunctions.

Based on the elements of the general algorithm, the specialist forms an individual correction protocol for each patient. The protocol takes into account all the features of the patient's symptoms and their neurological status.

Technology for Correcting Body Dysfunctions Using the P-DTR Method.

It is necessary to eliminate the pathological conditioned reflex by simultaneously stimulating these two identified dysfunctional receptor zones, followed by the rapid reproduction of one normal tendon reflex – knee, biceps, triceps, etc. [5]. After normalizing the receptor function, the CNS eliminates the entire pathological pattern and returns to normal functioning.

The treatment technology is associated with reproducing the mechanism of injury in a mild form. At the moment of the damaging factor's action and the occurrence of the primary receptor dysfunction, a compensatory receptor and a rigid link with it arise immediately. Therefore, simultaneous impact on both zones – priority and compensatory – imitates the situation of dysfunction occurrence but in a mild form, and the dysfunction disappears permanently. Recovery occurs along the same neurochemical pathway as during the action of the damaging factor because the nervous system chooses an already known and, therefore, less energy-intensive mechanism [6].

In most cases, the correction result can be seen and felt immediately: pain symptoms significantly decrease or disappear, range of motion increases, associated muscles acquire normal tone, withdrawal (inhibition) patterns disappear, internal organ function is restored, and blood pressure normalizes.

The method fully corrects functional deviations of the nervous system and internal organs. In cases of deep morphological disorders and serious consequences of injuries, it can only improve the patients' condition to varying degrees, which also changes their quality of life – pain disappears, motor activity increases, internal organ functions improve, and the resources of the nervous system and the body as a whole are enhanced.

Neuroreflex therapy is compatible with any treatment and rehabilitation methods and integrates perfectly into them. It is used as an additional manual intervention within the framework of complex therapy for correcting bodily dysfunctions.

Materials and methods

The effectiveness of the P-DTR method was assessed using treatment in a group of 65 patients.

The age of the subjects ranged from 13 to 52 years. In addition to the usual examination, symptoms graded on a scale from 0 to 10 were studied in both groups: pain in the area of the patient's complaint using the VAS scale (0 – no pain, 1 – discomfort, 2 – mild pain, 10 – unbearable pain, not amenable to drug therapy), muscle strength using dynamometry, joint mobility using goniometry, innervation using neurological methods, and emotional state using the HADS questionnaire. Indicators were studied before treatment, immediately after treatment, and subsequently in dynamics after 1–2–3–4 weeks, as well as in the long term.

A comparison of the state of the subjects and the five studied symptoms before and after correction using the P-DTR method was conducted. The control group consisted of outpatients with injuries, dorsopathies, and joint pathology receiving standard treatment from a traumatologist and neurologist, including drug therapy, exercise therapy, massage, physiotherapy, and other conservative methods.

In patients were observed pains in the back, neck, interscapular area were observed, as well as complaints of increased fatigue and limited joint mobility. Mild disturbances in tactile sensitivity, numbness, and paresthesia were noted. In such patients, the key trigger mechanism was often chronic stress or an emotionally significant event that occurred alongside an injury or intervention (e.g., appendectomy). In the absence of adequate physical activity, the disturbances became fixed and manifested as pronounced asymmetry of paired muscles, stooping, and pelvic and cranial misalignments. Thus, regardless of the level of physical activity, the decisive role in symptom development was played by the overlay of chronic stress on unrecovered primary disturbances, which ultimately formed stable patterns of dysfunction.

Results.

In the vast majority of subjects ($\approx 95\%$), symptoms were relieved immediately after the procedure; in the remaining 5%, regression of symptoms was observed within the next 2–5 days. Side effects were absent in all cases. Long-term

observation (up to 6 months) confirmed the stability of the results: no recurrences of the corrected symptoms were recorded.

A statistical analysis of the results of symptom correction using P-DTR method was performed using the Wilcoxon statistical test. Two independent samples were compared – before and after treatment, according to five digital indicators: local pain, local strength, local mobility, innervation and emotional background.

Comparison of symptoms before and after correction showed a substantial improvement in indicators in both groups, with p-value being much less than 0.0001.

It can be concluded that the dysfunction correction method led to a significant improvement in symptoms across all investigated parameters.

After the correction of dysfunctions using method P-DTR, a significant improvement in subjective state, emotional sphere, and all studied indicators without exception was observed. The pain syndrome decreased most substantially and indicators of muscle strength and joint mobility increased. The emotional background improved, and innervation disturbances resolved.

Other treatment methods – therapeutic exercises, massage, kinesiotherapy, osteopathic treatment, manual and physiotherapy – require a lot of time and do not always eliminate the troubling symptoms. These methods are usually prescribed in courses of 10 or more procedures. Furthermore, treatment with these methods is often directed at the zone of the pain syndrome – the compensatory dysfunction – therefore, in these cases, there is either no effect or it is short-lived. The advantage of the P-DTR method lies in the fact that the impact is made on the root cause of the disorders, so the healing can be complete [5].

Discussion

P-DTR is an alternative method of manual therapy that is positioned as a way to correct pain syndromes and dysfunctions through work with the nervous system.

The absence of randomized controlled trials, meta-analyses, systematic reviews meeting the criteria of evidence-based medicine does not allow classifying neuroreflex therapy as an intervention with proven efficacy. There are no works on the application of the neuroreflex therapy method in the available literature. The reason is that this method was proposed relatively recently. Currently, randomized clinical trials have only been initiated as part of a pilot project.

The Place of the P-DTR Method in Modern Medicine. Modern medicine is experiencing a period of integration, where alongside highly specialized, reductionist approaches, a holistic paradigm is gaining strength, viewing the organism as a complex, self-regulating system where physical, neurological, psycho-emotional, and environmental aspects are closely interconnected [69, 88]. The neuroreflex therapy method, in its philosophy and methodology, organically belongs to holistic medicine. This thesis is confirmed by an analysis of its fundamental principles: the priority of working with the central nervous system rather than peripheral symptoms;

understanding the organism as a unified sensorimotor network adapted to the external environment; emphasis on individual adaptive response rather than nosological classification of diseases; and a personalized treatment approach.

Conclusion.

The main task of the article is to transfer the method from the category of “ideas” to the category of “scientifically testable hypotheses.” The article is not an end product but a starting point. Publishing ideas is possible and necessary. But the path from an idea to a recognized method lies only through a long and rigorous process of scientific verification.

Familiarization with a new method is necessary so as not to miss potential benefits that may be discovered during the process of independent verification and replication of results; other experts may see in the idea something the author did not see, propose improvements, or new directions for research; verification can either confirm the value of the method or reject it, saving time and resources; if the idea is truly useful, then the sooner it becomes known, the faster it will begin to be applied to improve people’s health and save lives.

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CHEMIGATION BY MULTI-SUPPORT SPRINKLERS

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Abstract. *The use of multi-support sprinklers to combine various irrigation operations makes it possible to optimize the irrigation process. Chemigation with irrigation is the application of agrochemicals to the soil or plants using an irrigation system and by introducing a chemical into irrigation water. The obvious advantage is cost reduction. The required number and range of technical means is reduced, labor costs and the total cost of work are reduced, soil compaction caused by the movement of machines and aggregates is minimized. The article presents a technological scheme for the introduction of agrochemicals with irrigation water. A schematic diagram of the chemicalization point (block) and its device are given. The device of a water-air sprayer is proposed, its operation is modeled. The main design parameters of the spray torch of the water-air mixture are presented.*

Keywords: *Sprinkler, irrigation, chemicalization, agrochemical, sprayer.*

Introduction. The use of multi-support sprinklers to combine various irrigation operations makes it possible to optimize the irrigation process.

Irrigation chemigation is the application of agrochemicals to the soil or plants using an irrigation system and by introducing a chemical into irrigation water.

The obvious advantage is cost reduction. The required number and range of technical means is reduced, labor costs and the total cost of work are reduced, soil compaction caused by the movement of machines and aggregates is minimized. Insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, nematocides and other preparations are used for chemigation.

Fertigation is currently widely known and there are few practical recommendations and studies on spraying, pollination, application of insecticides, fungicides, chemical fragrances and other preparations using wide-range sprinkler equipment.

The effectiveness of chemigation is determined by the type of drugs used and their physical properties, the type and humidity of the soil, the type of crop, the time of application of drugs to the irrigation stream, the irrigation technology used and the perfection of the automated system of dosing and monitoring solutions.

A new approach and research are required to combine irrigation with the application of fertilizers (mineral and organic), trace elements, chemical ameliorants, growth stimulants and pesticides, while ensuring maximum environmental safety. The works of many scientists are devoted to research [1–12].

It is known that irrigation technology can be used to apply various chemical agents, including pesticides, defoliant, structure-forming agents and growth stimulants that meet the requirement of solubility in water [4, 11].

Sprinklers ensure high spraying efficiency due to the large gripping width and uniform distribution of substances.

Relevant is:

- Creation of units that combine technological operations of irrigation, fertilization, chemical meliorants and pesticides based on wide-range sprinklers.
- Improvement of technologies and technological methods of work.
- Development of sprinklers and sprayers for different operating conditions, technological operations of irrigation and application of various agrochemicals.

Materials and methods

When designing and selecting equipment for a chemicalization point (block), first of all, the aggregate state of agrochemicals and their type (chemicals, fertilizers, pesticides, growth agents, etc.) should be taken into account. When assigning parameters, it is necessary to take into account the consumption and capacity of the irrigation system, the type of sprinkler equipment used and the required concentrations of agrochemical solutions.

The chemicalization unit can be universal and designed for different agrochemicals. The aggregate state determines the application technology, the method of transportation, and the choice of dispensers that supply chemicals to the water stream. The schematic diagram of the chemicalization point (block) is shown in Figure 1.

Results and its discussion

Currently, fine spraying, aerosol sprinkling, pollination and spraying with water-air jets using wide-range sprinkler equipment equipped with special sprayers and compressor units are relevant.

A circular multi-purpose sprinkler includes a sprinkler, a compressor, a container with chemicals, and drain tubes on which sprayers are mounted.

The sprinkler (Figure 2) is a tubular body in the lower part of which a thread is made, onto which a sleeve is screwed, in the lower part of which a replaceable nozzle with a calibrated hole is installed. An air supply fitting is also installed in the sleeve. The replacement nozzle is selected with the required opening, depending on the required flow rate.

An aqueous solution from the machine's pipeline and air from the compressor are fed into the sleeve through a fitting fixed in the sleeve, forming a water-air chemical mixture at the outlet. Watering with an aqueous fertilizer solution can

be carried out without air supply. When air is supplied, it is used as a water–air chemical mixture, i. e. watering, spraying or spraying. Let's simulate the operation of the nebulizer.

The characteristics of the jet are shown in Figure 3. The longitudinal velocity varies from u_0 in the core to zero at the outer boundary.

The velocity in different sections can be found by the Schlichting formula:

$$u = u_m(1 - \bar{y}^{1.5})^2, \quad (1)$$

Here $\bar{y} = \frac{y}{b}$ – dimensionless distance from the axis;

b – half the width of the jet or the radius.

$$b = c'x. \quad (2)$$

where c' – experimental coefficient, Figure 3.

Fig. 1. – Diagram of the chemicalization point: 1 – chemical reagent supply pipeline; 2 – distribution pipelines; 3 – valves; 4 – pump; 5 – reagent mixing tank; 6 – solution supply pump; 7 – pressure pipeline; 8–12 – storage tanks for reagents, pesticides, chemicals, fertilizers; 13 – dissolution tank; 14 – level sensor; 15 – barbellator; 16 – valves; 17- solution pumping pipeline; 18 – sludge removal pipeline; 19 – gate valve; 20 – pump for supplying water and solutions; 21 – sludge removal pump; 22 – sludge discharge pipeline.

Fig. 2. Water-air sprinkler

Fig. 3. Design diagram of jet characteristics (rotated)

Mass fraction of water in the jet:

$$w_M = \frac{\rho_W}{\rho_A}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ_A – air density; ρ_W – the density of the sprayed water.
The maximum mass fraction of water is on the jet axis.

Fig. 4. Profiles of the longitudinal velocity of the jet for different sections of the jet section

For practical purposes, the geometry of the spray torch is important. The width of the spray torch depends on the pressure, the angle of the spray and the height of the installation of the water-air sprinkler relative to the surface (Fig. 5).

The uniformity and quality of crop treatment or watering depends on the accuracy of determining the distance between water and air sprinklers and the height of their installation on surface irrigation devices.

Considering the spray torch, it is necessary to single out the geometric diameter of the torch and the effective one, where coating with drops of solution will be sufficient to effectively perform the technological process of watering or spraying.

The values of the geometric parameters of the spray torch are shown in Table 1. Experimental studies are needed to determine the effective diameter of the jet.

Fig. 5. Geometry of the spray torch

Table 1. Geometric parameters of the spray torch (rounded to an integer value)

Torch angle	The width of the jet at the installation height of the water-air sprinkler in cm											
	10	15	20	25	30	40	50	60	70	80	100	120
20°	3	5	7	9	11	14	18	21	25	28	35	42
30°	5,0	8,0	11	13	16	21	27	32	38	43	54	64
45°	8,0	12	17	21	25	33	41	50	58	66	83	99
60°	12	17	23	29	35	46	58	69	81	92	115	138
90°	20	30	40	50	60	80	100	120	140	160	200	240
120°	35	52	69	87	105	139	173	208	242	277	346	416
140°	55	83	110	137	165	220	275	330	385	440	550	660

Conclusions. Retrofitting of wide-range sprinkler equipment with compressor units and water-air sprinklers ensures effective application of fertilizers, trace elements, biologics, herbicides and other chemicals in spraying and pollination modes.

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**INTELLIGENT MULTI-MODULE AGRICULTURAL LAND
MANAGEMENT SYSTEM BASED ON THE INTEGRATION
OF REMOTE SENSING DATA, GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION
SYSTEMS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS**

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of the development and testing of an intelligent multi-module agricultural land management system that integrates remote sensing data, GIS modeling, and artificial intelligence algorithms. The relevance of this work stems from the need to shift from reactive agricultural resource management to proactive forecasting under conditions of climate change and resource constraints.*

Keywords: *agricultural lands, GIS modeling, remote sensing, artificial intelligence algorithms, precision farming.*

The current stage of agricultural sector development is characterized by the need to resolve a fundamental contradiction between production intensification and the preservation of soil fertility. Traditional land-use planning methods based on averaged indicators demonstrate insufficient efficiency under conditions of the

increasing dynamics of agroclimatic processes. Accordingly, there is a growing demand for systems capable not only of assessing the current state of agrolandscapes but also of predicting their changes [1–4].

Analysis of global scientific and technological trends shows that the key direction in the development of smart agriculture is the creation of digital intelligent systems integrating GIS modeling, remote sensing (RS) data, and machine learning algorithms [4–8]. Unlike existing developments focused on solving individual tasks (crop monitoring or weather forecasting), the proposed approach aims to create a unified modular architecture covering the full management cycle – from data collection to the generation of prescription maps. System development was carried out along four modular directions: predictive analytics, GIS modeling and analysis, remote crop assessment, and information support for precision farming technologies (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Architecture of the intelligent agricultural land management, planning, and use system

For the predictive analytics module, data from the long-term multifactorial field experiment of Siberian Research Institute of Agriculture and Agricultural Chemicalization SFSCA RAS (Elite experimental station, Novosibirsk Region), established in 1981, were used. Modeling of nitrate nitrogen and available phosphorus content was performed using multinomial logistic regression (MLR) and artificial neural networks (ANN) in SPSS v.26. Yield forecasting was carried out using an adaptive neuro–fuzzy inference system (ANFIS). ANN models demonstrated

substantially higher predictive accuracy for nutrient content compared to regression methods. The overall percentage of correctly classified observations for nitrate nitrogen was 90% (9% higher than MLR), and for available phosphorus – 85% (vs. 63.1% for MLR). Forecasting of productive moisture reserves with an accuracy of 80.6% was achievable only with neural network methods, as MLR did not yield adequate results.

The results demonstrate that neural network approaches provide a qualitatively different level of generalization over agrochemical data – one that is unattainable through linear regression methods. The high proportion of correctly classified observations across all three target indicators confirms the practical suitability of the developed models for supporting agrochemical monitoring within long-term field experiments. Integration of the predictive analytics module with the GIS modeling and remote crop assessment modules enables the formation of a unified information environment in which predicted values of nutrient elements and productive moisture are applied directly in the generation of differential fertilizer application prescription maps.

The GIS modeling and analysis module employed object-based image analysis (OBIA). In this methodology, images are first segmented into objects – groups of pixels representing land parcels – which are subsequently classified into target categories using machine learning algorithms. Sentinel-2 satellite data (10 m resolution) for 2023–2025 and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) were used for mapping. Classification was performed using SVM, MLP, and RF algorithms using Python. A confusion matrix was used to assess classification accuracy.

For the remote crop assessment module, weed and disease classifiers were developed based on the ResNet-34, –50, and –101 architectures, achieving spatial object recognition accuracy of up to 95% [9]. Yield detection was implemented using YOLO models (accuracy exceeding 85%).

A method of differential nitrogen fertilizer application based on prescription maps generated by the Random Forest algorithm from agrochemical and spectral reflectance data was implemented. Production trials demonstrated that differential fertilizer application reduced the coefficient of variation to 10.6%, compared to 23.2% under conventional application. Fertilizer savings and unit cost reductions amounted to 15%.

Thus, the modular architecture of the system covers the complete operational cycle – from geospatial data collection and analysis to the generation of prescription maps. Experimental validation confirmed the high effectiveness of the proposed methods: ANN and ANFIS models achieved predictive accuracy of up to 90% for nutrient content and crop yield; ResNet- and YOLO-based classifiers reached object and weed recognition accuracy of up to 92.3% [10]; and prescription maps generated by the Random Forest algorithm not only improved yield uniformity (reducing

the coefficient of variation from 23.2% to 10.6%) but also reduced fertilizer costs by 15%. These results confirm the practical applicability of the developed system for precision farming and its contribution to sustainable agricultural land management under conditions of climate change and resource constraints.

The current trend in AI is related to the development of explainable models (Explainable AI, XAI), including SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) methods, LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), feature importance analysis, neural network activation visualization, partial dependencies, and interpretable models (decision trees, linear models with regularization). Integration of extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) with Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) enabled creating an interpretable model for spring wheat yield prediction with high accuracy ($R^2 = 0.95$) [10]. SHAP analysis revealed the most significant features determining yield in the forest-steppe of Altai Ob region. Explainable artificial intelligence models [10] represent a significant breakthrough, opening prospects for deeper understanding of agroecological processes and mechanisms for the formation of productivity of agrophytocenoses. The ability to interpret model predictions and understand the underlying factors driving agricultural outcomes is crucial for enabling evidence-based decision-making.

Implementation of these digital technologies in crop production systems possesses enormous potential for solving critical problems in agricultural science and creating sophisticated management systems for modern agriculture. The practical implementation of the developed digital technologies significantly improves the efficiency of agricultural production planning, optimizes the use of natural and chemical-technogenic resources, and reduces production risks in uncertain and variable climates. The research results are particularly important for ensuring food and environmental sustainability in agriculture.

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STUDY OF THE FILTRATION PROPERTIES OF ACIDIC COMPOSITION IN CARBONATE RESERVOIRS FOR THE SELECTION OF AN INJECTION MODE

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Abstract. *The present work presents the results of filtration tests aimed at optimizing the filtration process of acidic composition (CS) in carbonate reservoirs. Within the conducted studies, the following procedures were carried out: measurement of the pressure drop at the ends of core samples, calculation of core permeability values before and after exposure to the acid composition, determination of the time required for the formation of an acid “wormhole” and breakthrough through the core. For each investigated core sample, four values of injected pore volumes were recorded before the breakthrough; each test series was conducted at a different specified injection rate of the CS. An interpretation of the obtained filtration study results was performed, and model constants for the acid composition (CS) were calculated for each sample: permeability increase coefficient, injection rate, and volume of injected CS prior to the breakthrough of the core by the acid “wormhole.”*

Keywords: *filtration studies, acidic composition (CS), optimal filtration mode, permeability, breakthrough time, pore volumes, wormhole*

Introduction

Acid treatment of the near-wellbore zone of the formation is one of the most common technologies for enhancing oil recovery in carbonate reservoirs [1]. Hydrochloric acid, when reacting with calcite and dolomite, causes rock dissolution and the formation of highly conductive dissolution channels of complex geometry – wormholes. The formation of such channels, penetrating to depths of up to several meters from the wellbore, results in a significant reduction of the skin factor and an improvement in the hydrodynamic connectivity between the well and the reservoir [2]. Carbonate rocks contain approximately 60% of the world's

oil and gas reserves; therefore, improving acid stimulation methods for these rocks is of substantial practical importance.

The acid treatment modeling process is comprehensive and includes the following stages: physicochemical studies of acid compositions, reservoir fluids, and the rocks of the target formation; physical modeling of acid treatment on core samples; calculation of the optimal design of salt-acid treatment (SAT); production forecasting and evaluation of inflow intensification efficiency based on mathematical modeling [3–9].

The design of matrix acidizing is defined by three main factors: the acid surface reaction rate, the diffusion coefficient within the pore space, and the acid injection (filtration) rate into the formation [10, 13, 14]. The final factor largely determines the nature of the dissolution process: varying the velocity can result in different types of rock dissolution structures. At low velocities, all the acid reacts near the pore throat, causing compact dissolution (damage limited to the near-wellbore zone); at higher velocities, wide conical wormholes are formed; at an optimal velocity – narrow, long wormholes with minimal branching (dominant channels); Further increase in injection rate leads to the formation of multiple branches off the main channel, and at extremely high rates, the acid uniformly distributes throughout the pore structure without forming a distinct channel [11]. There is a critical injection rate below which only surface dissolution occurs, and an optimal range of rates at which dominant wormholes develop.

The concept of optimal acid treatment injection rate was introduced based on filtration experiments on the core: the optimal rate is defined as the acid injection velocity at which wormhole breakthrough through the sample is achieved with the minimal volume of reagent injected [12]. The optimization criterion is quantitatively expressed by the pore volume to breakthrough (PVbt) parameter – the number of pore volumes of acid injected until wormhole breakthrough occurs. Graphically, treatment efficiency is represented by the relationship between PVbt and the injection rate: the curve has a minimum corresponding to the optimal mode, indicating the lowest acid consumption required to achieve the specified penetration depth. At the optimal flow rate through the sample, a peak increase in permeability is observed. For example, during experiments with a 15 % HCl solution, the ratio of final to initial permeability reached 11.2 at this optimal flow rate, which also coincided with the minimum acid volume observed at the breakthrough stage.

Achieving wormhole breakthrough means creating a continuous drainage channel capable of efficiently draining the formation. Further acid injection (exceeding the optimal volume) results in excessive reagent consumption without a proportional increase in the zone of impact. If the injection rate is selected below optimal, a significantly larger volume of acid is required to advance deeper:

a substantial portion of the solution is neutralized near the inlet, forming a dissolution cone, and the wormhole fails to deepen to the required extent. Thus, the proper selection of the acid filtration mode (injection rate and volume) directly affects the efficiency of the near-wellbore zone treatment.

Experimental study

To select the optimal CS filtration mode, filtration tests are required. The experiments were conducted using the SMP-FES2A filtration apparatus. The design and instrumentation of the apparatus enable measurement of the pressure drop across the core ends, which was used to calculate permeability values before and after CS exposure, as well as to monitor injection under constant flow rate and volume, from which the acid wormhole breakthrough time in the core was determined.

Core samples from Fields 1 and 2 consist of 80% calcite and about 20% dolomite, whereas for Field 3 the calcite/dolomite ratio is approximately 50/50. The acid composition (CS) is an 8% HCl solution containing a corrosion inhibitor, an iron stabilizer, a demulsifier, and a surfactant.

The experimental filtration testing program was conducted in the following sequence:

1. Loading the core sample into the core holder of the filtration apparatus, followed by the establishment of reservoir thermobaric conditions and holding the core sample under these conditions.
2. Oil injection through the sample in the forward direction to determine the oil phase permeability at residual (bound) water saturation (without aging). Table 1 presents the properties of reservoir oil models used in the experiments. Reservoir oil models were prepared from degassed oils, with viscosity and density adjusted to match the properties of reservoir oil by adding a solvent. Aviation kerosene was used as the solvent.

Table 1 – Properties of Model Reservoir Oils

Field	Experimental Temperature Range, °C	Model Oil Viscosity Range, mPa·s	Model Oil Density Range, kg/m ³
Field 1	21.8–40.0	50.7–22.7	896–886
Field 2	21.6–40.0	51.0–22.6	896–885
Field 3	23.3–40.0	46.4–22.7	903–893

3. Oil displacement by water in the forward direction within a single core sample (12 pore volumes) with continuous monitoring of pressure and volumes of displaced fluids, followed by high-rate water filtration until stabilization – at least four pore volumes – and subsequent measurement of model porous medium permeability to water upon stabilization of filtration parameters (K1). A saline solution of distilled water with a density of 1.14 g/cm³ was used as the formation water model.

4. Injection of the acidic CS composition at various filtration rates for rocks from the same collection until breakthrough occurring in the reverse direction (from the wellbore to the formation). The following parameters were determined: the volume of acid injected until core breakthrough (wormhole formation) and the maximum pressure gradient (Figure 1).

5. Displacement of the CS from the pore space by water in the forward direction until stabilization of the pressure drop (at least four pore volumes), with determination of the porous medium model permeability to water (K_2).

6. Calculation of the permeability change factor to water before and after CS injection and determination of the volume of injected CS prior to breakthrough (determined by the decrease in pressure drop).

Figure 1 – Dynamics of the pressure gradient variation during CS injection

Following the completion of the experiment, core samples were extracted, and their mass measured after acid exposure to calculate the ratio of dissolved core mass to the initial core mass. To select the optimal filtration mode of the acidic composition (CS) for the selected fields, three sets of four core samples each were prepared. Samples were cut from full-size cores, subjected to extraction, and characterized by filtration and capacity properties.

Figure 2 presents experimental data reflecting the volume of acid injected (V_{por}) before wormhole breakthrough at various injection rates for cores from the studied fields.

As shown in Figures 2 (a-c), the optimal injection rate before breakthrough under the conditions of Reservoir 1 is $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$, for Reservoir 2– $0.1 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$, and for Reservoir 3– $0.15 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$.

Table 2 presents the permeability increase factors after core exposure to acid and the relative masses of dissolved material (core) under the effect of CS.

Figure 2 – Graph of filtration test results CS under conditions of Field 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c)

Table 2 – Selection of the optimal volume of CS

Field	Experiment	CS rate, cm ³ /min	Da	Permeability, *10 ⁻³ μm ²				Permeability increase factor, rel. units	Ratio of the mass of core dissolved under CS exposure to the initial core mass, %
				by gas	by oil	by water before CS	by water after CS		
1	1	0.1	0.0006	37.78	14.09	3.643	7.72	2.119	0.0578
	2	0.05	0.0012	37.27	9.34	2.74	792.73	289.31	0.0716
	3	0.025	0.0024	35.86	18.6	3.31	52.58	15.88	0.1602
	4	0.01	0.006	32.3	19.39	2.56	4.9	1.91	0.5308
2	1	0.1	0.0006	92.63	33.16	15.6	80.58	5.16	0.2739
	2	0.05	0.0012	91.64	33.16	13.29	1063.06	79.98	0.7279
	3	0.025	0.0024	79.8	47.42	13.39	18.64	1.39	1.2071
	4	0.35	0.0002	71.17	44.42	12.53	1670.77	133.34	0.6326
3	1	0.1	0.0006	66.69	61.17	11.43	2492.43	218.06	0.3202
	2	0.05	0.0012	61.28	43.93	11.81	1245.59	105.46	0.3889
	3	0.3	0.0002	50	28.89	6.69	2826.46	422.01	0.113
	4	0.15	0.0004	50.02	30.27	11.54	2401.5	208.1	0.2552

For the interpretation of the nature of the acid-rock interaction, the concept of the Damköhler number ($Da = (k \cdot a_0 \cdot L) / (D \cdot \phi)$) [15] was introduced. It was shown that at low acid injection rates, the Damköhler number is less than 1, indicating diffusion limitation and the formation of a compact dissolution zone. It should be taken into account that the studies were conducted under laboratory conditions, and thus at low injection rates. With increased injection rates, Da values greater than 1 may be reached, indicating the predominance of reaction-controlled processes and promoting the formation of dominant wormholes. Optimal efficiency is achieved at $Da \approx 1-10$, which corresponds to the transitional zone characterized by maximum effectiveness of the impact.

Conclusions:

1. The lowest permeability increase factor occurs at a relatively high degree of rock dissolution, corresponding to low injection velocities. This is explained by the fact that a slow injection velocity causes significant rock dissolution at the inlet (for the given CS) end of the sample, potentially impeding the formation of an effective wormhole.

2. Rapid injection of acidic compositions (CS) effectively increases permeability but simultaneously reduces the extent of core dissolution due to insufficient acid-rock reaction time. Furthermore, this method increases acid consumption, which may adversely impact profitability. If deep penetration of the CS into the formation is required, it is more appropriate to use retarded acid compositions

instead of rapid injection. These compositions provide uniform and complete dissolution of the formation rock, resulting in a more effective treatment.

3. For Reservoir 1, where the calcite content is 80% and dolomite is 20%, pronounced localized dissolution is observed. For Reservoir 3, with a calcite/dolomite ratio of 50/50, uniform dissolution is observed, which is attributed to differences in the reactivity of the rocks.

4. Maximum efficiency of the acid treatment is achieved at optimal CS injection rates, at which a stable wormhole is formed without excessive rock dissolution, and with the minimum volume of CS consumed compared to other injection rates.

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HYBRID COOLING SYSTEM CONCEPT OF SPARK-IGNITION TWO-STROKE ENGINE FOR UAV

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The process of improving two-stroke UAV engines is considered. The cooling system and methods of effective heat removal are analyzed in detail.

Traditionally, two-stroke engines have used air cooling, which subsequently dissipates excess heat into the environment through the airflow. Such internal combustion engines are relatively simple, lightweight, and cheap.

More powerful car engines have a more complex cooling system. Liquid cooling is used here with the use of a heatsink. This makes it possible to significantly increase the area of excess heat dissipation into the environment. This medium is the airflow. To increase the airflow, a special fan is turned on.

Aircraft engines face a technical contradiction: a powerful engine is needed, but the use of water cooling significantly increases the weight of the aircraft. Some foreign firms, such as Germany's Hirth, offer liquid-cooled engines for medium power. But such engines were not widespread.

The authors offer a combination of air and liquid cooling. The main heat dissipation is carried out by a blown air stream. In the event that the engine temperature rises above the critical value, rapid heat removal is carried out by liquid cooling through water evaporation.

Vaporization requires a lot of heat, which is discharged into the surrounding trail with the steam generated. The use of the endothermic phenomenon in vaporization formed the basis of the proposed type of cooling of the UAV engine. During the transition from one state of aggregation, the temperature of the substance

(during the transition of water into steam) practically does not change. This allows you to stabilize the temperature regime of the engine.

Keywords: *UAV, heat dissipation, liquid cooling, two-stroke engine, endothermic phenomenon*

Introduction

During the period of rapid increase in demand for unmanned aerial vehicles (hereinafter referred to as UAVs), there was a need for the selection and creation of a specialized engine.

The UAV market has been replenished with a number of worthy power plants. The leading players in this field are manufacturers from Germany, Austria, Italy, Russia and China [1, 2].

Depending on the size, purpose and requirements for UAVs, different types of engines are used, such as piston, rotary piston, turboshaft, turbojet, internal combustion engines, electric motors, etc. [3].

Foreign design developments for UAV motors include a voluminous list of technical solutions from small electric motors to powerful turbojet and turboprop engines.

A similar task was faced by the domestic engine industry, taking into account the specifics of the application. Among the known types of engines, spark-ignition internal combustion engines turned out to be optimal due to their higher power-to-weight ratio and simplicity of design. Although it is necessary to improve their cooling system, which is an important task.

In the article [4], he recommends using two-stroke engines with spark-ignition for UAVs, noting their simplicity, manufacturability, cheapness and high energy efficiency.

Sources [5, 6] indicate the advantage of two-stroke engines over four-stroke engines in terms of specific power – it is about 50–70% higher. It was this advantage that became the decisive factor in choosing the type of engine for the UAV.

Two-stroke engines are most often cooled by air or liquid cooling. Air cooling is based on the natural circulation of air passing through the fins on the cylinder. This method of cooling does not require additional components such as pumps and radiators, but is less effective at high ambient temperatures, as air is less thermally conductive than liquid.

Liquid cooling is more efficient at dissipating heat due to the circulation of coolant through a jacket around the cylinder, although it requires a more complex and expensive system that includes a pump, radiator, hoses, and the coolant itself.

For aircraft where weight indicators are critical, liquid cooling is not widely used. Air cooling is used in most of the invented UAVs with an internal combustion engine, including to control the temperature of electrochemical reactions of fuel cells of electric motors [7–13]. The disadvantage of some fuel cell air cooling systems is

the need to use a large number of components, which not only complicates assembly and maintenance, but also increases the weight of the device, material costs.

Liquid cooling leads to the complication and increase in the cost of the engine, which, ultimately, leads to a deterioration in the technical characteristics of the UAV [14, 15].

In this paper, the authors offer a compromise solution to minimize the discrepancy between the effective cooling of the engine and its technical and economic indicators.

Methods

The main challenge was the need to provide effective cooling with the compact size and limited weight of the device. A two-stroke UAV engine, like any heat engine, in addition to mechanical energy, generates a lot of heat, which is fraught with engine failures. Usually, this type of engine is cooled by an air flow that blows around the engine while driving. The volume of heat dissipation mass is unlimited, it is important that there is a good transition of excess heat into the surrounding air. However, for this purpose, the contact surface of the engine and the air surrounding the aircraft is structurally increased. Usually, a special ribbing of the cylinder surface and cylinder head is made. The shape of the fins should allow easy passage of airflow with minimal resistance and rapid air replacement. Additionally, guides can be made to increase the air flow. This somewhat complicates the design and increases the cost of the engine, increasing the weight of the UAV. But so far, this is the most common way for UAVs.

With intensive operating modes, characteristic of many types of UAVs, traditional methods of air cooling are not effective enough.

Liquid cooling is more common in road transport, where weight increase is not as important as in UAVs. In a car engine, a water jacket is structurally made, which is another sealed shell on the engine. Coolant is forcibly circulated through this shell, which then gives off excess heat to the surrounding atmosphere through the radiator. As long as the engine is not overheated, a small circle works and the heat transfer is small. When the engine overheats, a special valve begins to open – a thermostat [16]. The liquid begins to flow into the circuit of the large circle, which includes the heat exchanger – the radiator. Excess heat is released into the surrounding air, the jet of which penetrates the heat exchanger. If this is not enough, a fan is turned on at a certain temperature, which increases the airflow [17].

When the UAV starts, the engine temperature is equal to the ambient temperature (from minus 50–60 °C in winter to plus 50 °C in summer). The largest temperature difference occurs when the engine is running [18, 19].

Therefore, we have proposed a double, hybrid, cooling system: both air and liquid. The main heat dissipation from the UAV engine remains behind the air

flow, but when approaching dangerously high temperatures, liquid, namely water cooling, should be connected [20–22].

Water is one of the most heat-intensive substances in nature: at 18 °C, the specific heat capacity is 4.19 kJ/(kg · K) [23]. This means that to heat 1 kg of water from 18 °C to 100 °C, 343.58 kJ will be required.

But in order to turn 1 kg of water in a liquid state at 100 °C into steam at the same temperature, it is necessary to spend another 2,260 kJ of energy for vaporization [23]. Thus, vaporization requires 6.5 times more energy (at the same temperature).

The UAV hybrid engine cooling system we offer works as follows. The bulk of the excess heat is removed from the UAV engine through the passing airflow. However, under circumstances when the engine begins to overheat and the temperature approaches critical values, water cooling begins to work, effectively removing excess heat by transferring water to another state of aggregation – gaseous.

The diagram of the water-cooling system of a two-stroke internal combustion engine for UAVs is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Diagram of the water-cooling system

Structurally, the practical implementation of water cooling of the solution proposed by us can be carried out by the following device.

Initially, the water is in a vessel connected by a tube to the dispenser. When the critical value of the engine cylinder temperature is reached, the temperature sensor is activated, which sends a signal to the metering unit to open the drop.

The dispenser releases a portion of water at a certain interval so that the temperature of the entire cylinder has time to equalize and the cylinder does not “lead” from a large temperature difference. Usually, permanent deformations occur in the material with a large temperature difference between individual parts of the part in a short period of time (welding, quenching in water). This is possible only with temperature deformations that go beyond the elasticity of the material.

Since the direction of water from the dispenser goes to a certain point, for a more uniform cooling of the cylinder, it would be necessary to place several nozzles evenly around the circumference in the annular chamber. This complicates the design, worsening other parameters (weight, cost, reliability, maintainability). For example, single and multi-electrode spark plugs. The latter are more expensive and less common.

Boiling water cools the engine, the temperature drops to normal operating values, and the dispenser closes. The degree of heat dissipation will be determined by the amount of water evaporated. When the temperature drops and when the engine starts, the water-cooling system will not work.

Maintenance of water cooling consists in periodic cleaning of the inner surface of the evaporation chamber from scale and other foreign deposits so that there is a good thermal conductivity from the surface to the cylinder body. Therefore, the shape of the vapor chamber should be simple and easy to clean.

It is recommended that it be closed from the outside air by a threaded plug with a drain valve to release steam into the environment. To reduce the likelihood of scaling, distilled water is preferred.

After the UAV returns to the base, it is refueled with fuel, oil and water. In this case, distilled water becomes a consumable that needs to be replenished as needed (similar to fuels and lubricants).

Figure 2 describes the design of the vapor chamber.

There is an evaporation chamber in the engine housing *I*. The inner surface of the evaporation chamber should be located in such a way as to remove excess heat from the combustion chamber with the shortest possible time [24]. An important condition is that the water is sprayed not into the air, but on the surface of the engine. The dispenser is necessary to supply water in certain portions, the amount of which will be determined by the degree of cooling of the engine. The signal to turn on the hydro-injector-dosing unit is given from the control circuit.

Figure 2.– Evaporation chamber design: 1 – inner surface of the evaporation chamber; 2 – hydro-injector-dozer; 3 – drain valve

The drain valve 3 is necessary to remove the vapor generated by evaporation (with which the excess heat from the engine must also escape). The drain valve must be set so that the pressure remains in the evaporation chamber. The boiling point in the evaporation chamber will depend on the setting of the drain valve 3.

For the convenience of cleaning the inner surface of the evaporator, a large-diameter threaded cap is provided, which houses a hydro-injector-dosing device for supplying water to the evaporation chamber and a drainage valve for removing steam into the atmosphere.

The control scheme has certain settings that should take into account the following: When water evaporates from the inner surface of the chamber, sometime must pass for the excess heat to pass from the combustion chamber to the evaporation chamber. It is important here that there is good thermal conductivity of the engine cylinder material, and the evaporation chamber is in the immediate vicinity of the combustion chamber, for example, from the opposite direction to the air flow. Therefore, it is necessary to provide a time delay for the signal that triggers the next nozzle opening to avoid excessive water inflow.

Figure 3 shows an example of a cyclogram according to which the proposed liquid cooling of the UAV engine operates. It is important that water cooling is turned on only when the maximum temperature of the engine is reached. Air cooling accompanies the operation of the UAV engine and operates in parallel and continuously.

Figure 3.– An example of a cyclogram of the operation of the liquid cooling of the UAV engine

As you can see from Figure 3, water cooling only works when the engine is out of the normal temperature range. Water cooling is characterized by the rapid extraction of excess heat through evaporation, which returns the temperature to normal operating levels.

If we compare the proposed cooling system with the traditional liquid cooling system typical for cars, then the traditional one has an increased weight due to the presence of a cooling jacket (double wall). In such a cooling system there are additional elements: a cooling radiator filled with a certain amount of coolant, a fan, etc. In the proposed case, the design of water cooling is much simpler and has lower metric parameters.

Results

In order to increase the reliability of the engine for the UAV, a hybrid cooling system was proposed. The main flow of excess heat is traditionally removed by the air flow. In the event of an increase in engine temperature and exceeding the operating range, water cooling begins to work, increasing heat transfer to the environment and returning the engine temperature to the operating range.

This will extend the life of the UAV engine, improve reliability, expand the scope of the engine in various types of UAVs, including vehicles with a long flight time and intense load.

Further research is aimed at improving the engine temperature control system, exhaust and inertial charging systems for two-stroke spark-ignition internal combustion engines.

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ACTIVATED HARDWARE TROJAN DETECTION IN AES-256 COMMUNICATIONS EQUIPMENT

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Abstract. *Today's market requirements increasingly demand the minimization of time expenditures, including those related to the design of digital devices. This approach compels designers of digital devices to increasingly utilize custom third-party digital blocks that implement portions of the functionality of the final device, for example, encrypting output data. Given the high integration of IoT components with numerous civilian and military services, the importance of safeguarding information against compromise becomes ever more critical. This work presents the results of applying a trained neural network to detect anomalies in the output traffic of an AES-256 encryption module based on analyzing received and transmitted data without the use of a golden reference.*

Keywords: *digital electronics, hardware security, hardware Trojans, cryptography, AES, machine learning, neural networks, functional testing.*

Introduction

The large number of specialized personnel and resources engaged in addressing operational tasks for governmental and major commercial organizations necessitates expanding the range of technical solutions in the field of secure communication systems, capable of rapidly receiving, processing, and transmitting large volumes of data. Such continuous competition compels developers to utilize custom IP blocks or third-party manufacturing capabilities. This practice considerably increases the risks of embedding hardware Trojans with malicious functionalities, potentially leading to data leakage or failure of the digital device.

At present, the primary challenge in detecting hardware Trojans within microchips is the increased number of components in modern designs. Consequently, classical verification approaches for finished products—such as layer-by-layer examination of the topology of a randomly selected microchip from a batch, side-channel analysis, or conventional functional-logical testing—do not provide the necessary accuracy to reliably identify hidden functionalities.

To address the stated problem, machine learning methods are actively employed today to analyze the large volumes of data obtained through the classical methods mentioned. A key innovation in these methodologies is that some enable the detection of Trojans at the design stage without a golden model, as demonstrated in [1], where, by analyzing the gate-level design, a trained model identified anomalous patterns within graph structures and detected the hardware Trojan with considerable accuracy.

This approach also facilitates efficient analysis of finished products through side-channel analysis, as illustrated in [2], where a trained model accurately detected an embedded hardware Trojan by analyzing the electromagnetic spectrum of the chip using a “golden sample” reference.

The aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness limit of the applied machine learning method for identifying hardware Trojans in a digital cryptographic encryption device. For this purpose, an AES-256 encryption module was developed within the Xilinx Vivado 2024.2 software suite, embedded with hardware Trojans featuring various activation mechanisms, each implementing encryption replacement, encryption key leakage, or transmission of an unencrypted payload [3]. Using the Python programming language and the PyTorch software platform, the neural network from [3] was enhanced; by analyzing data from peripheral interfaces and applying an image classification approach, it is designed to detect anomalous behavior in the traffic of encrypted payloads.

Methodology

The AES-256 encryption module was chosen as the device under investigation, into which hardware Trojans with multiple activation mechanisms from [3] were embedded, with the aim of modifying functionality that leads to leakage of confidential information or the encryption key. The test environment depicted in Figure 1 is employed to coordinate the sending and receiving of packets, encryption processes, and the encryption key, as well as to transmit corresponding values of the trained model during device operation simulation. The neural network analyzes traffic patterns and classifies them as either normal or anomalous when deviations from the predicted result occur. This procedure is implemented to simulate device operation under the conditions envisaged for the application of the described methodology.

Hardware Trojans employ three activation mechanisms: a synchronous counter driven by the device’s primary clock signal, a combinational counter clocked by an XOR logic gate, and a finite state machine (FSM) that requires receiving the values ‘15’, ‘1F’, and ‘AF’ in the most significant bits of the encrypted packet for activation. Each Trojan, upon activation, performs the operation of substituting the encryption key with identical bits, sending an unencrypted packet, or transmitting the encryption key [3]. In this study, the hardware Trojan was modified by

substituting the encryption key with identical characters to both verify the overall viability of the applied methodology and to identify the robustness threshold of the employed model.

Fig. 1. Testbench diagram [3]

The trainable model is a fully connected (Multilayer Perceptron, MLP) neural network with five layers, designed to process fixed-length input vectors. The model classifies traffic into one of 13 classes, among which 10 correspond to different variations of key substitution. Model training consists of minimizing the cross-entropy loss function using the AdamW optimizer and the StepLR learning rate scheduler. The loss function formula, in the implementation under consideration, is as follows:

$$L(x, y) = -\log \left(\frac{e^{f_{\theta}(x)[y]}}{\sum_{C=0}^{12} e^{f_{\theta}(x)[C]}} \right), \tag{1}$$

where x – input vector, y – class label, C – number of classes, $f_{\theta}(x)$ – output of the model for the input vector x with parameters θ , and θ represents the set of all weights and biases of the trainable model [4].

The model was trained using more than 11 million values across 50 epochs. To validate the trained neural network, a new dataset was generated using Python and the cryptography 47.0.0 library with a generation seed different from that used in training; this dataset consists of one million input packets and one thousand encryption keys per each thousand packets. This dataset was employed to produce encryption results for both pure AES-256 and AES-256 containing embedded Trojans.

This straightforward model enables a rapid evaluation of the applied methodology’s effectiveness and guides the direction of further research. The author established a threshold of at least 90% accuracy under normal cryptographic module operation and at least 96% for detecting a Trojan exhibiting a high-density leakage of confidential information as the criterion for the applicability of the trained neural network, taking into account the complexity inherent in predicting the bitwise output of AES-256 encryption.

Results

Following the initial training of the model, an error matrix—depicted in Figure 2—was generated using Python and the matplotlib library, with the training outcomes summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Trained model’s confusion matrix

Table 1. Model’s training report

Malware type	Precision	Recall	F1-score
1	2	3	4
Normal	0.63	0.61	0.62
Key leak	1.00	0.38	0.55
Plaintext leak	1.00	1.00	1.00
Key substitution (average)	0.95	1.00	0.97

Table 2 presents the results of applying the trained neural network for analyzing the traffic of the cryptographic device. For scenarios involving key substitution by identical bits or digits, the output is the average value derived from the sum of results of the specific key substitution cases. In the case of a clean design, the average value across all instances within the specified category is presented: the total value for the class corresponding to key substitution with identical digits is 25.43%.

Table 2. Trained model’s test results

Project under test	Normal, %	Key leak, %	Key substitution (all bits 0/1) (avg.), %	Key substitution (same digit) (avg.), %	Plaintext leak, %
1	2	3	4	5	5
No trojan	62.73	0.07	10.70	2.94	0.07
Trojan-synchronous counter (key substitution to all bits 0/1) (average)	0.17	0.00	99.78	0.01	0.00
Trojan-synchronous counter (key substitution to same digit) (average)	0.21	0.00	0.02	99.72	0.00
Trojan-synchronous counter (plaintext leak)	0.10	0.00	0.02	0.01	99.83
Trojan-synchronous counter (key leak)	61.61	1.82	10.52	2.89	0.07
Trojan-asynchronous counter (key substitution to all bits 0/1) (average)	8.69	0.01	87.61	0.41	0.01
Trojan-asynchronous counter (key substitution to same digit) (average)	17.20	0.02	2.96	73.28	0.02
Trojan-asynchronous counter (plaintext leak)	17.14	0.02	2.95	0.82	72.56

Project under test	Normal, %	Key leak, %	Key substitution (all bits 0/1) (avg.), %	Key substitution (same digit) (avg.), %	Plaintext leak, %
1	2	3	4	5	5
Trojan-asynchronous counter (key leak)	61.91	1.34	10.57	2.90	0.07
Trojan-FSM, (key substitution to all bits 0/1) (average)	0.08	0.00	99.91	0.00	0.00
Trojan-FSM (key substitution to same digit) (average)	0.12	0.00	0.01	99.85	0.00
Trojan-FSM (plaintext leak)	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	99.98
Trojan-FSM (key leak)	61.61	1.82	10.52	2.89	0.07

Discussion

As shown in the error matrix in Figure 1, the current fully connected neural network model, when the classifier is expanded, cannot reliably classify the normal operation of AES-256 as demonstrated in [3]: the model erroneously classifies 20% of the data stream as a key substitution involving simple digits, and 10% as a key substitution with identical bits. Furthermore, in the case of key leakage, up to 34% of the data was incorrectly classified by the model during training as representing the normal operation of the device.

Upon evaluation of the trained model on new datasets, it was observed that the model's ability to recognize the normal data stream during clean AES-256 operation had significantly deteriorated compared to the results in [3]: 98.06% of normal traffic correctly identified before class expansion, versus 62.73% afterward. In other cases, despite the model's low recall for the class type involving key bit substitution, it did not underperform in detecting key leakage incidents during testing when compared to [3]. This is due to the fact that key leakage events, as defined by the hardware Trojan's operational algorithm, inherently have a low frequency for covert operation: approximately 20 thousand key leakage events per 1 million encryption transmissions. This implementation enables a more comprehensive evaluation of the neural network's capability to detect functional and logical anomalies in a complex device such as AES-256. However, despite the analysis result being close to the actual leakage volume (approximately 2%), the combined trigger values for events belonging to classes of encryption key substitution to identical bits or digits are significantly higher than the events of the key leakage class, which are obscured by model noise: key substitution accounts for more than 38% across all variants of hardware Trojan activation mechanisms.

Based on the presented analysis, the authors conclude that further increasing the complexity of the classifier for training the model with a fully connected neural network architecture is not justified. According to open-source research, promising approaches involve employing Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) [5] for analyzing large datasets aimed at detecting hardware Trojans, where the authors present a comparison of three graph neural networks with varying numbers of layers. The results of this study suggest that this model enables improved performance with fewer layers by reducing overfitting losses.

Conclusion

1. Based on the research findings, it can be noted that the methodology employing a neural network-based classifier enables the detection of cases where the key is substituted by identical digits in the AES 256 cryptographic encryption device with an activated hardware Trojan. In all such substitution cases, the classifier detected traffic changes with a probability of at least 96%, which corresponds to the threshold defined by the author. Despite the expansion of the classifier, the detection results for other types of anomalous functional and logical behavior did not deteriorate compared to those reported in [3].

2. The obtained data indicate the promising potential of the proposed machine learning approach for analyzing cryptographic device traffic; however, the model architecture requires modification due to significant noise encountered when expanding the classifier, which impedes the detection of normal device operation.

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INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF 2023–2025 AND THEIR IMPACT ON MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract. *The article examines innovative technologies introduced between 2023 and 2025 and their impact on modern society. Special attention is paid to wearable devices, artificial intelligence, neural interfaces, and generative AI. These technologies significantly expand human capabilities and transform everyday interaction with digital systems.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, artificial intelligence, wearable devices, robotics, neural interfaces, generative AI.*

Introduction

In recent years, technological development has accelerated significantly, leading to the emergence of innovative devices and systems that are changing everyday life. Modern technologies are becoming more integrated into human activity, improving productivity, communication, and mobility.

This article presents some of the most remarkable technologies developed between 2023 and 2025, focusing on their features, applications, and future potential.

1. MO/GO Wearable Technology

One of the most fascinating modern innovations is the MO/GO wearable device¹, which combines clothing and robotic technology.

From an external perspective, MO/GO looks like a combination of high-performance outdoor pants and a robotic exoskeleton. It features a durable and form-fitting design with a carbon-fiber-like frame integrated along the outer side of each leg.

¹Arc'teryx, Skip. MO/GO Wearable Technology. 2024.

Functionally, the system is powered by motors located at the knees. Sensors detect the user's movement and intentions, such as climbing or descending. The device provides additional power when moving upward and reduces impact when moving downward.

The primary purpose of MO/GO is to improve mobility. It is especially useful for people with muscle weakness, joint problems, or age-related decline. At the same time, it can also be used in everyday activities and outdoor environments.

2. Astribot S1 Robot

Another important technological development is the Astribot S1 robot¹, created by a company focused on embodied artificial intelligence.

The robot has a modern and user-friendly design. It features a humanoid upper body mounted on a wheeled base, which allows smooth movement. One of its key characteristics is a pair of highly flexible robotic arms capable of performing precise tasks.

The system is based on advanced artificial intelligence, which allows the robot to process information, learn from its environment, and perform complex actions. It can acquire new skills after observing tasks only a few times.

The main purpose of the Astribot S1 is to assist humans in various environments, including homes, offices, and industrial settings. It combines intelligent decision-making with physical interaction.

3. Huawei MateBook Fold

Another innovative device is the Huawei MateBook Fold², which represents a new generation of portable computers.

This device combines the functionality of a laptop and a tablet. When folded, it looks like a compact tablet, while in an open position it can function as a full laptop. The flexible screen allows multiple usage modes.

The internal components are distributed in a way that maintains a thin and lightweight design. The device also supports a detachable keyboard, which increases its usability.

The main purpose of this device is to provide an all-in-one solution for work and creativity, eliminating the need for multiple devices.

4. Meta Ray-Ban Display

Meta Ray-Ban Display³ represents a new step in wearable digital devices.

These smart glasses include a built-in display that allows users to access information directly in front of their eyes. The display is integrated into the lens and does not fully block the user's vision, allowing interaction with the real world.

¹ Astribot. Astribot S1: AI Robotic System. 2023

² Huawei. MateBook Fold Ultimate Design: Product Overview. 2024

³ Meta. Ray-Ban Smart Glasses: Technical Specifications. 2024

The device supports various features such as taking photos and videos, displaying notifications, and using messaging applications. It can be controlled using voice commands.

The glasses are also equipped with a high-quality camera and microphone system, providing good image and audio recording capabilities.

However, there are still some limitations. Battery life remains relatively short, and some features, such as advanced AI integration and higher video quality, could be improved in future versions.

5. Neuralink

Neuralink¹ is one of the most advanced developments in the field of brain–computer interfaces.

This technology allows direct communication between the human brain and digital devices through a small implanted chip. The chip reads neural signals and converts them into commands.

The system uses extremely thin wires inserted into specific areas of the brain. A special surgical robot performs this procedure with high precision.

Initial experiments have already demonstrated promising results. For example, patients were able to control a computer cursor and even play games using only their thoughts.

This technology has great potential, especially for people with severe medical conditions, as it may restore their ability to communicate and interact with the world.

6. Generative AI and Deepfake Technology

One of the fastest-growing areas of technology is generative artificial intelligence².

Generative AI systems can create new content, including images, text, video, and audio, based on learned data patterns. One of the most well-known examples is deepfake technology.

Deepfakes³ allow the creation of highly realistic but artificial media, such as replacing faces in videos or imitating voices.

This technology is widely used in entertainment, film production, and video games, where it helps create realistic characters and visual effects.

At the same time, it presents certain risks. Deepfakes can be used to spread misinformation or manipulate public opinion. Therefore, it is important to develop tools to detect such content and ensure ethical use of this technology.

¹ Neuralink. Brain–Computer Interface Technology Overview. 2023

² Goodfellow I., Bengio Y., Courville A. Deep Learning.– MIT Press, 2016

³ Kietzmann J. H., Lee L. W., McCarthy I. P., Kietzmann T. C. Deepfakes: Trick or treat? // Business Horizons. 2020. Vol. 63(2). pp. 135–146

Conclusion

The technologies developed between 2023 and 2025 demonstrate rapid progress in digital innovation. They significantly improve human capabilities, enhance everyday life, and transform interaction with digital systems.

At the same time, these technologies raise important ethical and technical challenges. Their future development will depend on responsible implementation and proper regulation.

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STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF BUTT JOINTS OF AL-CA-ZN-MG ALLOY BILLETS IN CAST AND WROUGHT STATES PRODUCED BY FRICTION STIR WELDING

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Abstract. *The influence of heat input on the microstructure, microhardness profile, and mechanical properties of butt joints of hot-rolled plates made of Al-5Zn-1.3Mg-1Ca (wt.%) alloy produced by friction stir welding (FSW) at two values of the heat input coefficient, $K = 9.41$ ($T = 408\text{--}415$ °C) and $K = 6.95$ ($T = 355\text{--}370$ °C), was investigated. The absence of a characteristic microhardness “trough” in the heat-affected zone (HAZ) was established – a behavior fundamentally different from that of heat-treatable 6xxx and 7xxx series alloys. The mechanism underlying this effect is shown to be the thermal stability of the (Al) + Al₄Ca eutectic at welding cycle temperatures. Reducing the heat input narrows the HAZ from 3–5 mm to 2–3 mm and increases the bending angle from 45° to 54°, with an insignificant change in strength (325 vs. 330 MPa). The obtained results indicate that Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system alloys are fundamentally insensitive to thermal softening during FSW.*

Keywords: *friction stir welding, aluminum-calcium alloys, heat-affected zone, microhardness, heat input, thermal stability, eutectic.*

1. Introduction

Friction stir welding (FSW) is a solid-state joining process in which heat is generated by friction between the rotating tool and the workpiece, and the joint is formed at temperatures below the solidus [1]. The absence of melting fundamentally eliminates defects inherent in arc and laser welding methods, such as porosity, hot cracking, and microstructural coarsening in the heat-affected zone (HAZ).

For aluminum alloys of the 6xxx and 7xxx series, which are strengthened by precipitates of metastable phases (Mg₂Si and MgZn₂, respectively), the thermal

cycle of FSW inevitably causes dissolution or coarsening of the strengthening particles in the HAZ. This manifests as a characteristic microhardness trough and a reduction in joint strength relative to the base metal [2]. To eliminate this effect, post-weld heat treatment is typically required.

Eutectic alloys of the Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system represent a fundamentally different class of aluminum materials: their strength characteristics are determined by the thermally stable (Al) + Al₄Ca eutectic, rather than by metastable precipitates [3, 4]. The Al₄Ca phase dissolves a significant amount of zinc and retains its morphology and dispersity over a wide temperature range up to ~300 °C [3]. From a physical metallurgy perspective, if the temperatures of the FSW thermal cycle do not reach the solidus, HAZ softening should be absent. However, this hypothesis has not been verified in the open literature for alloys of the Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system.

The present work is devoted to a systematic study of the influence of heat input on the HAZ and microhardness profile of butt FSW joints of hot-rolled Al-5Zn-1.3Mg-1Ca alloy billets, as well as to establishing the mechanism of structural stability of the HAZ.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Base Material

Hot-rolled plates with a thickness of 5 mm made of an experimental Al-5Zn-1.3Mg-1Ca (wt.%) alloy were investigated. Rolling was carried out at 450 °C with a reduction of 10% per pass on a DUO 260 rolling mill without prior homogenization annealing; the total degree of deformation was 75%. The mechanical properties of the initial billets were as follows: $\sigma_B = 330\text{--}335$ MPa, $\sigma_{0.2} = 275\text{--}285$ MPa, $\delta = 4.3\text{--}4.85\%$.

2.2. Welding Procedure

Welding was performed on a laboratory setup. The ends and the areas at a distance of 15 mm from the joint were cleaned with a wire brush; the edges were milled to $Ra \leq 16.5$ μm . The tool was made of R18 steel: the shoulder had a diameter of 22 mm, and the pin was a truncated cone ($\varnothing 5$ mm at the base, $\varnothing 3$ mm at the tip) with a threaded surface. The rotational speed of the tool was fixed at $n = 800$ rpm. The welding speed was varied: $v = 85$ mm/min (Mode 1) and $v = 115$ mm/min (Mode 2). The tilt angle of the tool axis was 2.5° , and the downforce was 8.4–9.2 kN. The heat input coefficient was calculated as $K = n/v$.

2.3. Research Methods

The temperature in the stir zone was recorded using chromel-alumel thermocouples. Static tensile and bending tests were carried out in accordance with GOST 6996. Microhardness was measured across the transverse cross-section of the weld at intervals of 0.5 mm. Microstructural analysis was performed by optical microscopy on etched metallographic specimens.

3. Results

3.1. Influence of heat input on mechanical properties

The characteristics of the welding modes and the results of mechanical testing of the joints are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Mechanical properties of welded joints of hot-rolled billets of the Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system alloy produced by FSW under different modes

FSW mode	Heat input coefficient K	Peak temperature in the stir zone T , °C	Ultimate tensile strength of the welded joint σ_B , MPa	Ultimate tensile strength of the weld metal, MP	Bending angle α , deg
1 ($v=85$ mm/min)	9,41	408–415	325	347	45
2 ($v=115$ mm/min)	6,95	355–370	330	350	54

A decrease in the heat input coefficient from $K = 9.41$ to $K = 6.95$, achieved by increasing the welding speed, is accompanied by a reduction in the peak temperature in the stir zone by 40–50 °C. The increase in strength under these conditions is insignificant: σ_B increases by 5 MPa. Ductility, in contrast, increases markedly: the bending angle rises from 45° to 54°, i.e., by 20% relative to Mode 1.

3.2. Microhardness profile and HAZ width

The microhardness profile across the transverse crosssection of the joints for both modes does not exhibit the characteristic trough in the HAZ. In the weld nugget, the hardness is slightly higher than that of the base metal. Moving away from the weld center toward the base metal, the hardness decreases monotonically without falling below the initial level.

The HAZ width for Mode 1 ($K = 9.41$) was 3–5 mm; for Mode 2 ($K = 6.95$), it narrowed to 2–3 mm. Thus, reducing the heat input allows a narrower thermally affected zone to be obtained while maintaining a high level of strength properties.

4. Discussion

4.1. Mechanism of the absence of softening in the HAZ

The absence of a hardness trough in the HAZ is interpreted within the framework of the eutectic strengthening mechanism. In 6xxx and 7xxx series alloys, the thermal cycle of FSW leads to dissolution or coarsening of metastable precipitates ($MgZn_2$, Mg_2Si) in the HAZ, reducing the hardness by 20–40% relative to the base metal [2]. In the Al–Ca–Zn–Mg alloy, the strengthening phase is the stable (Al) + Al_4Ca eutectic [3, 4]. Since the FSW thermal cycle does not reach the solidus temperature of the alloy, coarsening or dissolution of the eutectic particles does not occur, and HAZ softening is physically precluded.

The slight increase in hardness directly in the weld nugget relative to the base metal is attributed to dynamic recrystallization and grain refinement induced by severe plastic deformation in the stir zone – a wellknown effect in FSW of aluminum alloys [1].

4.2. Influence of heat input on HAZ width and ductility

The low sensitivity of the strength characteristics to changes in heat input (an increase in σ_B of only 5 MPa with a 26% decrease in K) is a distinctive feature of this class of alloys and reflects the thermal stability of the primary strengthening constituent. In contrast, ductility, characterized by the bending angle, responds noticeably to reduced heat input: an increase from 45° to 54°. This effect is associated with the narrowing of the HAZ (from 3–5 mm to 2–3 mm) and, consequently, with a reduction in the extent of the transition zone with a gradient in structure and properties – a source of stress concentration during bending.

The obtained results indicate the preference for regimes with reduced heat input (increased welding speed) when processing Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system alloys by FSW: a narrower HAZ and higher ductility are achieved without compromising strength.

5. Conclusion

1. At the two investigated heat input levels ($K = 9.41$ and $K = 6.95$), the microhardness profile across the crosssection of the FSW joints of the hotrolled Al-5Zn-1.3Mg-1Ca alloy does not exhibit the characteristic trough in the HAZ. This result fundamentally distinguishes the alloy class under consideration from heattreatable materials of the 6xxx and 7xxx series.

2. The mechanism underlying the absence of softening is the thermal stability of the (Al) + Al₄Ca eutectic: at the temperatures of the FSW welding cycle (355–415 °C), coarsening and dissolution of the eutectic particles do not occur.

3. Reducing the heat input (increasing the welding speed from 85 to 115 mm/min) narrows the HAZ from 3–5 mm to 2–3 mm and increases the bending angle from 45° to 54°. Strength changes insignificantly: 325 vs. 330 MPa.

4. For alloys of the Al–Ca–Zn–Mg system, FSW regimes with reduced heat input are recommended: they ensure maximum joint ductility while maintaining strength characteristics.

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CURRENT METHODS FOR CONSTRUCTING UNDERGROUND PARKING IN INTEGRATION WITH THE RECONSTRUCTION AND RENOVATION OF OPEN PUBLIC SPACES IN THE CITY OF SAMARA

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Abstract. *This article addresses the relevance of reconstructing and renovating open public spaces in the city of Samara, focusing on enhancing their functionality and integrating them into the urban fabric without compromising the quality of the urban environment. It is indicated that the functional and physical obsolescence of such areas, including their planning solutions, is a consequence of a pervasive deficit of parking spaces. Public spaces must be adapted to contemporary requirements through the implementation of underground parking beneath them. It should constitute a unified system. The principal public spaces of the city of Samara have been identified. A systematization of the methods for their development has been carried out.*

Keywords: *reconstruction, renovation, public center, public space, underground parking, system of centers, underground infrastructure.*

Samara possesses a substantial number of open public spaces that define the city's urban form. Among them are major parks: Suburban Park, one of the oldest and most frequented recreational facilities in the city; Gagarin Park, featuring well-developed infrastructure; Shchors Park; Druzhba Park; Pobeda Park; Youth Park; Mira Park; and the Science and Culture Park 'Soyuz,' formed by the union of the Square of Revolutionary Fighters and the Garden of Balance near the branch of the Tretyakov Gallery. Additionally, there are the Voronezh Lakes and the 50th Anniversary of October Park.

The squares of Samara hold a significant position within the urban center system. The majority of squares targeted for renovation are situated in the 'old' city, and their reconstruction necessitates the formulation of urban planning regulations for the historic settlement, a status designated to a portion of pre-revolutionary Samara. Consider other spaces such as Agricultural Square, Memory Square,

Nikitinskaya and Krymskaya Squares, and Heroes of the 21st Army Square adjacent to the Fountain of the 40 Years of Victory, where one of the entrances to the metro station is located.

Alabinskaya, Basov Square, Krasnov Square, Michurin Square, Sanfirova Square, despite their relatively small size, play a significant role in the daily lives of urban residents. Apple Square, 'Shanghai' Square, and Bulgarian Square function as transitional spaces leading to larger public areas or hubs of urban activity. Fadeev Square is a relatively large, well-developed public space located in the Oktyabrsky district of Samara. Other public spaces include the boulevard along Chernorechenskaya Street, Komsomolsky Boulevard, "Stuttgart" Alley, Memory Alley, Labor Glory Alley, as well as Sofiyskaya and Orlovskaya embankments, form significant pedestrian links between various parts of the city. These areas also perform a transit function and, upon comprehensive landscaping, have the potential to develop into high-quality recreational zones.

Additionally, open public spaces encompass the territories of various public facilities, such as surface parking areas at Shopping Center «Cosmoport», «Mega-City», «Okhotny Ryad», «InCube», and the zone along the Vysotsky Sports Palace. It is important to note that some of the facilities have already undergone reconstruction in recent years. For example, certain sections of the embankments, the boulevard along Chernopechenskaya Street, as well as several squares and urban green spaces in the central part of the city have received or will soon receive new landscaping. However, these works were often isolated in nature and did not address systemic problems related to spatial organization, particularly those concerning parking infrastructure.

Currently, the condition of many of the aforementioned public spaces is characterized by a number of common issues. The primary issue is the deficit of organized parking spaces, which results in disordered parking on adjacent streets and surrounding areas. This consequently diminishes both the quality and accessibility of the public open spaces themselves. Additional factors constraining the development of these territories include outdated infrastructure and obsolete urban amenities.

To determine the areas requiring renovation through the implementation of underground parking, a comprehensive analysis employing multiple criteria was conducted:

- Firstly, the urban planning significance of the facility, its location, and its role within the nodal center system of Samara's planning structure were considered.
- Secondly, the transport situation, the adequacy of the street and road network, traffic intensity, and the extent of the parking deficit were analyzed.
- Thirdly, the development potential of the studied territories and the technical feasibility of implementing underground structures were evaluated, where the

presence of Metro lines and underground pedestrian crossings would considerably facilitate the construction of underground parking facilities.

An analysis of the distribution of publicly significant facilities across the city has shown that the highest concentration of open public spaces requiring reconstruction or renovation is located in the Oktyabrsky district of Samara. This district, being one of the most densely populated and actively developing areas, exhibits a clear imbalance between the demand for parking spaces and their actual availability. Furthermore, it is precisely within this district that numerous key nodal centers of urban significance are situated – including cultural institutions, business centers, commercial-office clusters, sports facilities, and shopping and entertainment centers.

Based on the analysis results, a list of priority objects was formed where the construction of underground parking can provide the greatest effect in terms of improving the human environment of public spaces. Among the parks are Suburban Park, Gagarin Park, Shchors Park, the Science and Culture Park “Soyuz,” as well as the Voronezh Lakes. These objects experience high parking demand and possess sufficient area to accommodate underground structures without compromising the above-ground recreational function.

Among the squares, Agricultural Square and Heroes of the 21st Army Square are of the greatest interest. These spaces are currently utilized inefficiently. Fadeev Square, Basov Square, Apple Square, Krasnov Square, and Shanghai Square have been identified as sites capable of serving as examples of integrated renovation of public spaces. The close proximity of Fadeev and Basov Squares necessitates a specialized approach to the design of underground structures, potentially involving their integration into a unified system. Surface parking areas at Shopping Center «Cosmoport», «Mega-City», «Okhotny Ryad», and «InCube», Shopping Center «Rus», as well as the vicinity of the Vysotsky Sports Palace and near the ZIM business center also require comprehensive renovation.

Sofiyskaya and Orlovskaya embankments, Komsomol Boulevard, and Memory Alley, as linear components of the system of centers within Samara’s spatial planning framework, are proposed to be analyzed collectively with their adjoining territories. All listed entities represent various types of open public spaces, each requiring distinct approaches to their reconstruction and renovation. A shared trajectory for their future transformation is the implementation of a comprehensive system of underground parking facilities beneath all types of these spaces, accompanied by infrastructure corresponding to contemporary standards.

The development of underground parking spaces within the established urban planning framework of Samara necessitates a differentiated approach that accounts for the specific layout and development characteristics of each particular public space experiencing a shortage of parking for vehicles [1, 2]. The analysis

of the identified territories, alongside advanced international and domestic experience, enabled the systematization of key methods for constructing underground parking in Samara, each characterized by specific implementation features and fields of application.

The first method involves the construction of underground parking beneath existing parks, squares, and public gardens [3, 5]. This approach allows for the preservation of valuable green spaces

while simultaneously resolving the issue of parking deficits in these areas. From a technical perspective

This entails the utilization of a parking construction technology whereby the load-bearing slab structures simultaneously function as the foundation for the restored landscape. This method of underground parking construction and the technology for preserving green plantations during construction have been successfully implemented in Paris, Munich, Hamburg, Moscow, and numerous other cities worldwide (Fig. 1, Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Michel-Garage – Parking beneath the urban park in Hamburg [7]. Fig. 2. Entrance to the underground parking beneath Zaryadye Park in Moscow [8].

The second method involves the construction of entrances and exits for underground parking directly from the streets, following the Parisian model [3, 5]. This method proves particularly effective for linear open public spaces. This approach has been successfully implemented in the French capital, Paris, where entrances and exits of underground parking are harmoniously integrated into the urban landscape without compromising its visual integrity (Fig. 3, Fig. 4). In the Samara context, this solution is ideally suited for Komsomolsky Boulevard in the Zagorodny Park district, where the sufficiently wide pedestrian zone allows for the placement of access points without disrupting traffic flows. A similar approach can be applied to the Sofiyskaya and Orlovskaya embankments, where the installation of multiple access points at regular intervals along the embankment will create a convenient access system without overloading individual sections of urban traffic.

Fig. 3, Fig. 4. Entrance and exit to the underground parking in Paris [3].

An important advantage of this method is its relative simplicity in implementation and economic efficiency, as it does not require complex engineering solutions for organizing access. However, meticulous design of entrances and exits is necessary to minimize their visual impact on the surrounding environment and to ensure pedestrian safety.

The third method involves the integration of parking facilities with existing underground infrastructure, particularly applicable to areas adjacent to metro stations [3, 5]. The example of the Heroes of the 21st Army square, located near the metro station, illustrates a unique opportunity to develop parking either above or at the same level as the metro tunnels, with the establishment of a direct connection between them. This solution will not only enhance user convenience but also establish a significant transport interchange hub, fostering the development of a ‘park-and-ride’ system in which drivers leave their vehicles in specially designated parking areas and utilize public transport to reach their final destination. In the vicinity of the Science and Culture Park

Fig. 5. Underground facility complex at Karlsplatz, Munich [3].

Fig. 6. Contemporary view of Karlsplatz Square [9].

The ‘Soyuz’ near the branch of the Tretyakov Gallery can effectively utilize existing underground pedestrian crossings through their integration with underground parking. This will establish convenient pedestrian connections between cultural venues and parking facilities, thereby improving accessibility (Fig. 5, Fig. 6).

The fourth method presupposes the construction of underground parking facilities near central-forming buildings and structures, including shopping and entertainment complexes [5]. These objects, being major centers of attraction, generate significant parking loads on the surrounding urban environment. In Samara, these are the surface parking areas adjacent to the shopping centers «Kosmoport,» «Mega City,» «Okhotny Ryad,» «Rus on the Volga,» «InCube,» and others. A distinctive feature in the design of parking at shopping centers should be their mandatory integration with pedestrian flows – convenient pedestrian crossings, elevators, and escalators, allowing visitors to move easily from vehicles to shopping halls (Fig. 7, Fig. 8).

Analysis of the identified territories and advanced international and domestic experience

has made it possible to systematize the key methods for the construction of underground parking in Samara, each of which possesses distinct features of implementation and areas of applicability.

Fig. 7. Shchelkovsky Shopping Center, Moscow [10].

Fig. 8. Entrance to the underground parking [10]

The implementation of the proposed methods for the construction of underground parking should be carried out within the framework of an integrated concept that links all objects into a single system. This entails the standardization of wayfinding design, the establishment of a unified payment and management system, and integration with municipal digital services. Only such a comprehensive approach will enable the transformation of disparate parking structures into an effective instrument for the reconstruction and renovation of

Samara's public spaces [6], thereby contributing to the overall improvement of urban environmental quality.

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